

**ATTITUDINAL AND BEHAVIOURAL DIMENSIONS OF
THE BOTTOM OF THE PYRAMID CUSTOMERS
TOWARDS BRANDED ESSENTIAL PRODUCTS**

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DECLARATION

I, **Mrs. Keerthan Raj**, hereby declare that the thesis entitled “*Attitudinal and Behavioural Dimensions of the Bottom of the Pyramid Customers Towards Branded Essential Products*” submitted to the Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Management is a record of the original research work done by me under the supervision and guidance of **Dr. P. S. Aithal** and the research work has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, fellowship or any other similar title.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “*Attitudinal and Behavioural Dimensions of the Bottom of the Pyramid Customers Towards Branded Essential Products*” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Management is based on the original work done by **Mrs. Keerthan Raj** in the Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The thesis has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, fellowship or any other similar title.

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“Knowledge, in the end, is based on acknowledgment” Ludwig Wittgenstein

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SYNOPSIS

“Don’t find customers for your product; find products for your customers.”

-Seth Godin

Bottom of the Pyramid is the population, where the majority of the world's population growth takes place, could increase to more than 6 billion people over the next 40 years, according to World Bank predictions. Most Tier 4 residents reside in urban slums and shantytowns or rural villages, and they sometimes lack a legal title or right to their possessions (e.g., dwellings, farms, businesses). In India, the BoP market has a population of about 924 million and a purchasing power parity of 6,550 thousand crores of rupees. At the base of the pyramid, India has 114 million homes. This represents 60% of India's total population and 76% of the rural population. Let's say a marketer in India only sells to 60% of the population because they are not targeting the BoP. The BoP category is recognised as a potentially significant worldwide market because to its \$5 trillion yearly family income. As can be seen in the slums of Dharavi (Mumbai, India), and elsewhere, the world's BoP is now a group of active consumers who are buying a greater range of goods and services, including consumer goods and mobile phone contracts. India's population and market make up by far the largest portion of the pyramid's base. According to the McKinsey report, 5 out of 6 Indians, or 1.05 billion people, were BoP as of 2005, which means that they were making an average household income of less than INR 2,00,000 per year, or INR 16,667 per month. BoP is deemed to have a yearly household income of less than INR 3,000 in metropolitan India, where the cost of living is higher. This translates to a household income of less than INR 25,000 per month. BoP in rural India is defined as a household with an annual income of less than INR 1,60,000 or a monthly income of INR 13,333. Although advances and a rapidly expanding middle class have been fueled by tremendous economic growth, the report notes that BoP remains at 78% of India's population, or 997 million people, as of 2015. Considering the above background this study attempted to study the impact of the attitude of BoP consumers towards branded essential products with the mediation of promotional strategy. Through this objective the study also attempts to analyse whether promotional strategies adopted by the marketers significantly contributes in influencing consumer attitude towards their

purchase behaviour. The study also explored the driving factors of BoPR to serve the BoPC market. It is envisaged that the results of the study would help the corporates to develop innovative strategies to reach these consumers.

Literature review conducted by the researcher revealed the studied area and scope of future research. To better understand literature review was categorised various segments; firstly, in order to identify the constructs and get a depth notion about study area, research conducted a review of related works on the BoP, related works on BoPR, related works on branded products. Secondly, based on the reviews many constructs were identified, on the ground of which review related works on identified constructs has been undertaken which covers attitudinal dimensions, promotional strategies and purchase behaviour of BoP consumer. Understanding these constructs also directed a researcher to make one more category under literature review to analyse the relationship between identified constructs which consists review of Related Works on Consumer Attitudes and Behaviour, Related works on Attitude and Promotional Strategies, Related works on Promotional strategies and purchase behaviour and Related works on Promotional strategy as a mediator between Consumer Attitude and Purchase behaviour. Lastly summary of review was provided at the end of the chapter.

Furthermore, review of this article highlighted a concealed gap in this domain. Since most of the study has been done on international forums hence literature review predominantly focused on international papers. The studies in the Indian context focused on the rural BoP. However, for some reason, an interesting proposition about the urban bottom of the pyramid has been missed. An understanding of the Indian BoP and how it can be measured, and their purchase behaviors are missing entirely in any of the studies earlier. This rather unexplored area which needs a good amount of research formed the basis of the proposed research topic which is –Attitudinal and Behavioral Dimensions of Bottom of the Pyramid Customers towards Branded Essential Products.

After the exhaustive review of various articles, the concepts and theories pertaining to the study were discussed. Concept understanding of various identified constructs such as attitudinal dimension of BoPC, promotional strategies and their purchase behavior directed the researcher towards various hypothetical relationships. After examining the various

conceptual framework and theories, the researcher proposed a conceptual model for further testing in the present study in the context of BoP Customer domain.

Three research instruments were developed, one for BoPC, second for BoPR and third research instrument was framed for a focused group interview. After examining the validity and reliability of the instruments 218 responses were collected from the Bottom of the pyramid customers, 100 responses were collected from the retailers. Thereafter, analysis was done through SPSS 26.0 software by adopting appropriate statistical tests such as one-way ANOVA, Fishers Exact test, Chi-square test, independent sample t-test, simple regression and multiple regression analysis. Furthermore, to test the proposed conceptual model AMOS 23.0 was adopted and the model was tested using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

As per the data collected from Bottom of the Pyramid customers, majority of them found to be localites and also majority of them are above 40 years of age category. Most of the BoPC have only school level education and majority of them are wage labourers. Percentage analysis of collected data has also shown that majority of the BoPC have 3-5 family members and in majority of the BoPC households, there are only 2 to 3 earning members. Moreover, BoPC prefer government ration stores and Kirana store to purchase daily use essentials and FMCG products. It was also found that having seen and heard about the product, Credit availability of the product, Convenience of the place of purchase, Others' opinion of the store, Offerings by the Seller, seller recommendation, Attractive Prices are highly preferred and Opted statement by the customers. In addition the data collected from BoPR demonstrated most of the respondents to be localites and majority of them are above 45 age category. It was also found that majority of them are male and graduates. Retailers consider selling loose products is profitable and offering low price for the product is important in selling. Furthermore, they also agree that majority of the customers can differentiating between Branded and Un-Branded products.

Testing of various hypothetical relationships demonstrated that demographic factors of BoP customers have influence on their purchase behaviour concerning Essential product categories of FMCG (Tooth Paste, Shampoo, Soap, Face Powder/Cream). It was further witnessed that various attitudinal dimensions of BoP customers such as Awareness,

Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors influences the promotional strategies adopted by the marketers which in turn helps the customers in determining the significant purchase behaviour. Overall the proposed conceptual model found to be significant and true for BoP customers. As far as retailers perception is concerned, the attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influenced by the tenure of business, number of walk-ins per day, duration of stock purchase, and percentage of the known customer and also the attitude of BoPR toward branded essential products is negative.

For a smooth understanding of this mega research the chapter has been categorised into seven chapters consisting of Introduction, Review of Literature and Conceptual Framework, Research Methodology, Data Analysis and Interpretation, ABCD Quantitative Framework and Discussion, Findings and Discussion and Recommendations, Proposed Model and Conclusion, which is further discussed as follows:

CHAPTER SCHEME

This doctoral thesis is systematically organized into seven chapters. A brief snapshot of each chapter is presented below.

Chapter 1: Introduction

The study's key themes are introduced in the first chapter, which also provides some background on the term "Bottom of the Pyramid," which C. K. Prahalad popularised internationally [1]. The study's primary ideas address attitudes and views; however they are only applicable to Bottom of Pyramid (BoPC) Consumers with regard to a few Essential Products (EP). Additionally, this chapter highlights two additional crucial aspects of the study that are essential to Bottom of Pyramid Retailers (BoPR). The chapter discusses the study's goals, postulates, and hypotheses in addition to the research questions.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature and Conceptual Framework

In order to identify the research gap and develop a conceptual framework for the model that will be tested through a methodical quantitative and qualitative approach in search of the best solution to the research problem, this chapter reviews the prior literature on the key concepts and study dimensions.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

The research technique and design used in this study are covered in the third chapter. The chapter provides more information on the methods used to test the conceptual model as well as the approaches used for sampling, data collection, and data analysis that are most suited to address the main research issue.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis and Interpretation

This chapter focuses on an extensive cross-sectional multi-dimensional sample research of BoPC and BoPR as well as an investigation of the multi-variant impacts of the three dimensions on the BoPC attitudinal dimensions and viewpoints.

Chapter 5: ABCD Quantitative Framework and Discussion

The ABCD analytical framework and statistical analysis techniques are included in the fifth chapter. The study's goals and hypotheses served as the foundation for the findings and discussion. The data and analysis from a thorough ABCD research included in this chapter serve as the basis for the final chapter's recommendations.

Chapter 6: Findings and Discussion

In chapter six, which builds on the previous chapter, more discussion and analysis of associations and conclusions that come from the empirical study of the key concepts and dimensions are conducted in order to design and recommend an integrated, refined framework for BoPB that can be used as a tactical tool to increase penetration into the BoPC segment exponentially.

Chapter 7: Recommendations, Suggested Model and Conclusion

The final chapter offers a summary of the full investigation into the stated goals. The pools of the multi-dimensional analysis from mixed methodologies are summarised along with their theoretical and practical contributions. Based on the analyses and findings of the study, a prescriptive model is suggested. The model makes an effort to address the commercial consequences for marketers in the BoP industry and the potential for additional study. The thesis is concluded by a brief statement.

The companies that produce branded essential products may benefit from the identification of the distinctive traits, socio-economic motivators, and other factors influencing the purchase of branded essential goods by better understanding and customising their product offerings, strategies, promotional campaigns, and other marketing initiatives at the BoP with particular market environments created around the very specific and distinctive needs of this group of customers. Along the value chain, the businesses would be able to develop scalable and sustainable business models. Understanding BoP purchasers' preferences for promotional strategies and their efficacy would be helpful. This metric of client acquisition may not be equivalent in the BoP as compared to the ToP consumer because attitudes take time to build and, once formed, is a reason for customer loyalty.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGFI	: Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index
ABCD	: Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages
AMOS	: Analysis of Moment Structures
ANOVA	: Analysis of Variance
BCG	: Boston Consulting Group
BoP	: Bottom of the Pyramid
BoPB	: Bottom of Pyramid Brands
BoPC	: Bottom of the Pyramid Customer
BoPR	: Bottom of the Pyramid Retailer
CFA	: Confirmatory Factor Analysis
CFI	: Comparative Fit Index
CSTV	: Chi-square Test Value
df	: Degree of Freedom
EFA	: Exploratory Factor Analysis
FAO	: Food and Agriculture Organization
FETV	: Fisher's Exact Test Value
FMCG	: Fast Moving Consumer Goods
GFI	: Goodness-of-Fit Index
IFMR	: Institute for Financial Management and Research
INR	: Indian Rupee
MFP	: Main Food Products
MNCs	: Multinational Corporation
TOP	: Top of the Pyramid
MR	: Mean Rank
NCAER	: National Council of Applied Economic Research
PCP	: Personal Care Products
PHH	: Priority Household
PHRC	: Priority House hold Ration Card
PPP	: Purchasing Power Parities

PPP	: Public Private Partnership
RMSEA	: Root-Mean-Square Error of Approximation
SECC	: Socio-Economic Caste and Census
SEM	: Structural Equation Modeling
SFP	: Supplementary Food Products
SPSS	: Statistical Package for Social Science
UGC	: University Grant Commission
UNICEF	: United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
USD	: United States Dollar
VIF	: Variation Inflation Factor

NOTATIONS

p-value	: Significance Level
R²	: Coefficient of Determination
B	: Beta Coefficient
t	: t- Statistics
Z	: Z Test Value
Sig.	: Significant
χ^2	: Chi-square Test
F	: F- Statistics
H	: Hypothesis
H₀	: Null Hypothesis
H₁	: Alternative Hypothesis
0.01	: 1 % Level of Significance
0.05	: 5 % Level of Significance
N	: Number of Observations
%	: Percentage
MRR	: Multiple Response Rate
Min.	: Minimum
Max.	: Maximum
S.D.	: Standard Deviation
Post Hoc	: Statistics
R	: Correlation
S.E.	: Standard Error
C.R.	: Critical Ratio
S. Estimate	: Standardized Estimate
U. Estimate	: Unstandardized Estimate
AVE	: Average Variance Extracted
MSV	: Maximum Shared Squared Variance

CHAPTER-I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In economic terms, the Bottom of the Pyramid markets refers to the poorest two-thirds of the human economic Pyramid. The term Bottom of the pyramid was first used by U.S. President Franklin D. Roosevelt on April 7, 1932, in a Radio address, The Forgotten Man, where he said-these unhappy times call for the building of plans that rest upon the forgotten, the unorganized but the indispensable units of economic power that build from the bottom up and not from the top down, that put their faith once more in the forgotten man at the bottom of the economic pyramid. The bottom of the pyramid (BoP) approach as propounded by C.K. Prahalad and Stuart L. Hart in ‘The Fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid’ (2002) used the 4-tiered pyramid to represent the global distribution of wealth and the capacity to generate income. Right at the top of the world economic pyramid are 75 to 100 million affluent Tier I consumers from around the world. This is a cosmopolitan group composed of middle- and upper-income people in developed countries and a few rich elites from the developing world [1]. In the middle of the pyramid, in Tiers 2 and 3, are poor customers in developed nations and the rising middle classes in developing countries, the targets of MNCs’ past emerging-market strategies. They categorized 4 billion people in Tier 4 i.e., at the bottom of the pyramid. Their annual per capita income based on purchasing power parity in U.S. dollars is less than \$1,500, the minimum considered necessary to sustain a decent life. For well over a billion people roughly one-sixth of humanity’s per capita income is less than \$1 per day.

As per World Bank projections, the population at the bottom of the pyramid could swell to more than 6 billion people over the next 40 years, this is because the bulk of the world’s population growth occurs there. Most Tier 4 people live in rural villages, or urban slums and shantytowns, and they usually do not hold legal title or deed to their assets (e.g., dwellings, farms, businesses).

Annual Per Capita Income*	Tiers	Population in Millions
More Than \$20,000	1	75-100
\$1,500-\$20,000	2 & 3	1,500-1,750
Less Than \$1,500	4	4,000

* Based on purchasing power parity in U.S.\$

Figure 1.1: Four Consumer Tiers [2]

Source: U.N. World Development Reports (Adapted from Prahalad & Hart, 2002)

Most people who earn less than \$2 per day are categorized as Tier 4 and live mostly in underdeveloped countries, where they dwell in rural villages and shanty towns. Prahalad and Hart argue that the private sector and specifically large multinationals is central to transforming the poor into consumers. They argue that multi-nationals by serving this bottom of the pyramid segment will not only contribute towards global poverty eradication but can create employment opportunities in local markets while generating profits for themselves in a multitrillion-dollar market segment. It consists of more than four billion people in the world. These markets are often invisible and unorganized. Most of the developing countries are emerging BoP markets. The top twenty emerging economies of the world include more than 700 million such households, with a total annual income estimated at some \$1.7 trillion, and the spending power is approximately equal to Germany's annual gross domestic product [3]. In a study on households of 110 countries it was revealed that out of the 5575 million population, 72% constituted BoP in countries like Africa, Asia, Eastern Europe, Latin America, and the Caribbean [2].

Considering India's case, the BoP market has over 924 million with a purchasing power parity of rupees 6,550 thousand crores. There are 114 million households in India at the bottom of the Pyramid. The number is 76 percent of the rural population and 60 percent of India's total population. So, suppose a marketer in India is not marketing to BoP, in that case, it is only selling to 60 percent of the population. A total annual household income of \$5 trillion a year establishes the BoP segment as a potentially important global market. Within that market are significant regional and national variations in size, population structure income distribution, and other characteristics. The BoP spends most of its household budget on food followed by transportation and telecommunications [4]. They don't have access to electricity, sanitary services, clean drinking water, or affordable health care. They struggle to make a living because they lack access to legitimate markets where they can sell their goods. When compared to the wealthy, the poor typically pay substantially greater prices for products and services. Compared to other top-tier markets, this market has distinct needs. Most of their requests go unfulfilled because they were previously disregarded. The true essence of marketing lies in the fact that it recognizes the needs of a particular market and positions itself so that this unmet need is met. Hence, this study should identify the characteristics of the BoP market, and consumers in the BoP market, and then move on to how it can effectively leverage the bottom of pyramid marketing.

The International Labour Organization estimates that more than 70 percent of the workforce in developing countries operates in the informal or underground economy, suggesting that most BoP livelihoods come from self-employment or from work in enterprises that are not legally organized businesses [5]. This informal economy is a significant fraction of the size of the formal economy. According to a detailed study by economist Friedrich Schneider, the informal economy averages 30 percent of official GDP in Asia, 40 percent in Eastern Europe, and 43 percent in both Africa and Latin America, and the Caribbean [6].

Figure 1.2: A Tale of Two Pyramids

Source: U.N. World Development Reports (2002 data); James Davies, Rodrigo Lluberias, and Anthony Shorrocks, Credit Suisse Global Wealth Report 2018 (2017) [7][8][9]

Today, the world's BoP is a set of active consumers and they are now purchasing a wider range of goods and services, including consumer products and cell phone plans as are evident in the slums of Dharavi (Mumbai, India) and elsewhere. Due to this slight increase in income levels over the last 15 years since the theory was first propounded about the BoP, there is increased focus on this segment as a highly potential segment to cater to in the next few years. A comparison of the world economic pyramid between 2002 and 2017 shows some interesting facets. The new pyramid has fewer people at the BoP (3.5 billion, compared with 4 billion in 2002) as illustrated in Figure 1.2 [7][8][9]. By 2017, the income levels had climbed so much that it's difficult to compare them directly on the two graphs. The richest 20% of the world's population accounted for nearly 85% of worldwide revenue in 2000. Interestingly, by 2017, there was a new concentration of wealth at the top. Nonetheless, the pyramid is still attracting attention from marketers to understand this bottom segment to tap the potential here.

If we were to further segment this category based on their living standards and categorize it into baskets of income earners, the income level of USD 1 a day separates the extremely poor from everyone else. The people above that can be demarcated as those earning USD 1 to USD 3 a day and those earning USD 3 to USD 5 a day. Adults (roughly 1.4 billion people) who live with an earning of USD 3 to USD 5 a day usually hold a couple of years of secondary school and the necessary skills to enter the labour market. Majority of them with irregular incomes or semi-regular incomes such as construction workers, petty traders, drivers, odd job wage earners, and so on. This category may deal in both formal and informal markets, and dwell close to or among the people who live in the next layer of the pyramid, those with daily wages of little over USD 5. This category may typically own bicycles, pressure cookers, televisions, and cell phones. They continuously strive for adequate housing, credit access, and better health care and hold aspirations of better education for children to be able to attain stable, better-paying jobs.

1.2 BoP MARKET IN INDIA

The base of the pyramid is by far the biggest percentage of the population and market in India. The McKinsey report states that as of 2005, 1.05 billion people (5 out of 6 Indians) were BoP, which is on average they were living on an annual household income of less than INR 2,00,000 per year or INR 16,667 per month. In urban India, where the cost of living is higher, BoP is considered to have an annual household income of less than INR 3,00,000. This is equivalent to less than INR 25,000 monthly household income. In rural India, an annual household income of less than INR 1,60,000 or a monthly household income of INR 13,333 is considered as BoP. Tremendous economic growth has fuelled improvements and a fast-growing middle class, the report, however, states that BoP still stands at 78% of India's population or 997 million people in 2015.

The Rangarajan Committee after re-examining the issue of poverty in India proposed to the government of India to adjust for urban and rural differences by creating two poverty line thresholds-one, less than INR 47 (\$0.69) per capita expenditure per day in urban areas and INR 32 (\$0.47) per capita expenditure per day in rural areas. This is much lesser than the \$2 per day benchmark. This again is the upper layer of the poor as defined by the Rangarajan committee [10]. As per the McKinsey report [11],

in 1985, 93 percent of the population had an annual household income of less than INR 90,000 or less than \$1,970 per year, this income bracket was categorized by McKinsey as ‘deprived’. By 2005, this had dropped to 54 percent of the population, which means that more than 103 million people in India had moved out of desperate poverty. This definition of poverty as less than INR 90,000 household income is also the measure used by NCAER. The forecast shows that the deprived segment will further drop from 54 percent in 2005 to 22 percent in 2025. ‘Aspirers’, are categorized as people who have an annual household income of INR 90,000 (\$1,970) to INR 2,00,000 (\$4,376), although they cannot be termed as deprived, nonetheless, they struggle to live comfortably, typically spending more than half their income on necessities. As people move out of desperate poverty India’s income pyramid will also change and India will have a significant sizeable and large middle class. They have classified the middle class to comprise two economic segments-‘seekers’ with a real household income of INR 2,00,000 (\$4,376) to INR 5,00,000 (\$10,941) at PPP terms. What is significant to note in the McKinsey report is that, as incomes rise the class structure of consumption would change significantly. Consumption is largely dominated by the deprived and aspirer segments which control about 75 percent of spending. Today, despite their lower incomes the rural households account for a major share of consumption. Further on in the classification are ‘Strivers’, people with an annual household income of INR 5,00,000 (\$10,941) to INR 10,00,000 (\$21,882), and ‘Global Indians’, having an annual household income of more than INR 10,00,000 (\$21,882).

Figure 1.3: Household Incomes–Estimated 2025 [McKinsey Global Institute Report]

Source: McKinsey Global Institute Report, 2007[11]

According to the McKinsey study report, the spread of population has been divided across Tier 1, 2, and 3 cities. India comprises 5,161 cities and towns across 35 states and Union territories and close to 600 districts across the country. McKinsey has classified these cities and towns based on population spread. Large multinationals and Indian corporations have a wide presence across Tier 1 and 2 cities while they have been gearing up to target the rising middle class in these cities. Tier 3 and 4 cities comprise smaller cities and towns, upcoming urban centers, and tiny settlements. In tier 3 and 4 cities and towns, there is the presence of a large informal economy. While urban centers are the fastest-growing market in India, rural areas account for 70 percent of the country's population and have accounted for more than half of India's consumption. As per the survey, even with continued urbanisation, it is expected that 63 percent of the population will be in rural areas in 2025. As of today, 6,00,000 villages of varying sizes are home to close to 800 million Indians.

Figure 1.4: Classification of Towns and Cities in India [11]

Source: McKinsey Global Institute Report, 2007[11]

Characteristics of BoP Segment:

London, T., & Hart, S. L. [12][13] defined the characteristics of the BoP segment as follows:

1. BoP segments are most times heterogeneous in nature.
2. BoP segments need to be consisting of a population with minimum income in a particular geographical region.
3. Lives primarily in the informal economy.
4. BoP segment consists of the maximum number of population.

Though indeed, BoP markets do not have enough money to compete with the rich of society, some examples quoted here will prove this to be wrong. Even the poor indeed buy luxury products. In one of Asia's biggest slum areas, Dharavi in Mumbai, 85% of the households possess a television, pressure cooker, and a mixer owned by 75%, gas stoves by 56%, and approximately 21% are owners of telephones. The reason is that most of the consumers living at the Bottom of the Pyramid realize that they would never be able to invest in buying a house or other so called aspirational amenities and hence spend on affordable necessities if available, as a means of satiating their quest for luxury in life.

1.3 ATTITUDE

Social psychologists reserve the term attitude to refer to our relatively enduring evaluation of something, where the something is called the attitude object. The attitude object might be a person, a product, or a social group [14]. Research has found that while some of our attitudes are inherited, at least in part, via genetic transmission from our parents [15], most other attitudes are learned mostly through direct and indirect experiences with the attitude objects and these learned attitudes—such as our preferences for different objects or styles—are more individualized. Human beings hold attitudes because they are useful. Particularly, our attitudes enable us to determine, often very quickly and effortlessly, which behaviours to engage in, which people to approach or avoid, and even which products to buy. Attitudes are important because they frequently (but not always) predict behaviour. Our attitudes are not the only factor that influences our decision to act. The three key variables that affect the attitude-behaviour relationship are the attitude toward the behaviour (the stronger the better), subjective norms (the support of those we value), and perceived behavioural control (the extent to which we believe we can perform the behaviour) [16]. These three factors jointly predict our intention to perform the behaviour, which in turn predicts our actual behaviour. The theory helps to predict what intentions will turn into actions and the degree of control a person has over what intentions turn into actions [17]. Because attitudes often predict behaviour, people who wish to change behaviour frequently try to change attitudes through the use of persuasive communications or other promotional measures. Marketers desire the ability to better understand consumers' attitudes towards their products and services. However, attitudes are complex and a consumer may have a range of attitudes (favourable and

unfavourable) towards a single product or service-not just one. In addition to the various qualities held by a product or service, consumers are also faced with the added complexity of seeking approval, whether that comes from friends, family, or society. Attitude models are designed to help identify the different factors that would influence a consumer's evaluation of attitude objects. Due to the complexity surrounding attitudes, researchers use multi-attribute models to explain them. Multi-attribute models provide a framework that can be used to measure consumers' attitudes towards specific products or services. The model identifies how consumer attitudes are informed by measuring and evaluating the attitudes of a product; the beliefs about those attributes; and the relative importance we give those attributes. Such models say that we form attitudes about a product based on several attributes of that product, our beliefs about those attributes, and the relative importance we assign to those attributes [18].

1.4 CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

Consumer behaviour reflects the totality of consumers' decisions concerning the acquisition, consumption, and disposition of goods, services, and so on. It consists of how the consumer's emotions, attitudes, and preferences affect buying behaviour [19]. Behavioural characterizations on the one hand are based on aspects of recurrent purchase behaviour, the frequency of purchase, amount of purchase, and amount of offered brand switching. The attitudinal approach comprises consumer preferences, attitudes, and brand dispositions and in turn, allows greater insight into loyal behaviour [20]. Behavioural dimensions illicit customer actions and involves the past purchase measurement of the same brand and the measurement of future purchase probabilities of past purchase behaviours. On the other hand, attitudinal dimensions are, are the psychological disposition of the consumers for the object involving the measurement of various influencing variables that shape the consumer attitudes. Behavioural and Attitudinal dimensions both are important and need to be intertwined for understanding long-term customer relationships, especially when predicting customer future patronage. Behaviour and attitude are two measures or kinds or dimensions of loyalty [21]. Behavioural measures or dimension characterizes consequential actions (i.e., as a result of loyalty); such as; volume or purchasing frequency, repeated purchasing, debt, returns, customer retention, longevity, and complaints and interactions, whereas, the attitudinal measures or dimension,

characterizes formative behaviours as commitment (i.e., a desire to maintain a valued relationship) that could be seen in the willingness to recommend, intent to purchase, repurchase.

1.5 BOTTOM OF PYRAMID CONSUMERS (BoPC)

For purpose of this study is to understand the attitudes and perspectives of the BoPC toward branded products and hence, we are considering the PHRC holders as the BoPC of our study. They are the Indian equivalent of the global definition of people living on less than USD 2 per day. The Government of India has implemented a scientific, objective, and fool-proof mechanism for identifying, classifying, and follow-up of issuing ration cards to PHH.

Figure 1.5: Multi-dimensional View of the Key Concepts

1.6 BOTTOM OF PYRAMID BRANDS (BoPB)

A brand is a name, term, design, symbol, or any other feature that identifies one seller's good or service as distinct from those of other sellers. The term has been extended to mean a strategic personality for a product or company so that "brand" now suggests the values and promises that a consumer may perceive and buy into. Over time, the practice of branding objects extended to a broader range of packaging and goods offered for sale including oil, wine, cosmetics, and fish sauce, and, in the 21st century, extends even further into services. Primarily, all consumers irrespective of income need certain necessities to live. Today, these necessities also are torn away from humble offerings that can be procured directly from nature to over-the-counter small serving sizes of products, especially in the context of the urban consumer. To enable focalized research, we have considered all the brands (local, domestic, national, and international) which are offering essential products defined in this study.

1.7 RESEARCH GAP

The researcher went through a wide range of books, research papers published in International journals, and dissertation thesis and also did an extensive study of the material available on the web related to the Bottom of Pyramid markets and the penetration of business establishments serving these markets. Since, most of the study has been done on international forums hence literature review predominantly focused on international papers.

A thorough review of these topics revealed that substantial work has been done in these areas independently, and mainly focused either on secondary research, case studies, or qualitative research. Most of the research papers/articles talked about the inclusion of the customers in the business process to penetrate the BoP segment to gain consumer acceptance at the Bottom of the Pyramid. The studies in the Indian context focused on the rural BoP. However, for some reason, an interesting proposition about the urban bottom of the pyramid has been missed. An understanding of the Indian BoP and how it can be measured, and their purchase behaviours are missing entirely in any of the studies earlier. During the researchers; observational interactions with BoP the spending habits of the BoP in India are found to be interesting not having any other context of inquiry. Herein, further study is required to analyze the role of demographics, and the impact of the attitudinal dimensions on purchase behaviour is elicited. There is a strong belief that the topic would open up new arenas, which would unleash limitless possibilities where the different stakeholders can focus their energies and gain substantially.

This rather unexplored area which needs a good amount of research formed the basis of the proposed research topic which is-Attitudinal and Behavioural Dimensions of Bottom of the Pyramid Customers towards Branded Essential Products.

1.8 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Planning Commission of India in its vision statement 2020 has clearly stated that an essential requirement for envisioning India's future in the new century is to recognise that the parameters which determine national development have changed in recent years and will change further in the future. This will open greater possibilities than ever before. As envisaged in the document published by the IFMR, the BoP consumer is a very potential and interesting phenomenon of study, the market

complexity of finding, reaching, and retaining the BoP consumer is mentioned below in the figure.

Figure 1.6: BoP Market Complexity–Contributing Factors [22]

There is a large (66 percent) gap between segment expenditure on food and the next largest expenditure, on energy needs, which accounts for roughly 12 percent of the Indian BoP annual expenditure.

Figure 1.7: Indian BoP Expenditure by Sector [22]

The potential is also huge for marketers as according to Socio-economic Caste and Census 2011, people living in slums are 60.90 million and categorized as urban poor. SECC had taken several questions in record and on the basis of source of generation of income defined urban poor as household whose main source of income is begging rag-picking, domestic work, street vendor/cobbler/hawker/other service provider working on streets; construction worker/plumber/mason/labor/painter/welder/security guard/coolie and other headload worker; sweeper/sanitation worker/mali; home-based worker/artisan/handicrafts worker/tailor; transport worker/driver/conductor/ helper to drivers and conductors/cart puller/rickshaw puller; shop worker/assistant/peon in small establishment/helper/delivery assistant/attendant/waiter; electrician/mechanic/

assembler/repair worker; washer-man/chowkidar; other work/non-work; non-work (pension/rent/interest, etc.) In their report, UNICEF reported that out of these persons living in urban India one is a migrant, by 2026, 40% of the Indian population will live in Urban areas. The majority of this population will come under the bottom of the pyramid bracket.

The Global Wealth Report (2016) [7] in their final approach stated that the next emerging market is BoP and they termed it as "next billion". The urban BoP is exposed to the various modern technologies, media, latest fashion trends, and customs. They aspire to imitate the affluent people living in these towns and cities. Hence, it gets worthwhile to do segmentation based on demographics and psychographics like income levels, geography, occupation, education, values, and attitudes. While there have been some studies on the BoP and the rural BoP, there is no structured study to understand the composition and purchase habits of the Indian urban BoP especially focussed on only the essential products which account for close to 70 percent of their daily expenditure. This market segment is not a homogenous segment and incomes range across various regions and countries. In India, we also have a large class of migratory population who have settled in large cities for purposes of employment. The people here depend largely on an informal economy and have access only to poor-quality products at a high price (comparatively). It is envisaged that the results of the study would help the corporates to develop innovative strategies to reach these consumers. Reviewing the literature highlighted gaps in existing knowledge and the identification of the research questions for the current study.

1.9 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The consumers at BoP are characterized fundamentally by low incomes and low literacy levels. Population consists of this segment are permanent residents of urban areas, usually living in rented accommodation in high-density areas like slums or low-income category housing areas. However, having exposure to modern technologies, media, latest fashion trends, and customs. they aspire to imitate the affluent people living in these towns and cities. they aspire to have the same products as seen on television, and better levels of personal care by using the same type of personal care products that are used by top of the pyramid (ToP) market consumers. Manufacturers of top-end brands see this trait of aspiration as an exclusive opportunity to develop

products that cater to the wants of the BoP. Are these consumers lured by the attractiveness and appeal of brands, and what is the motivator to choose or not to choose a product, what drives the purchase behaviour is important to understand which leads us to the following research questions.

RQ1: What are the key drivers of purchase for the BoP segment consumers?

RQ2: What is the extent of Marketers' influence through branding exercises on purchase elements and decisions?

RQ 3: What is the attitude of the BoPC towards brands?

RQ 4: What is the approach of retailers towards BoPC?

1.10 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Research objectives define the scope of the thesis. If the objective is too large we spend a lot of time collecting information that is not useful whereas if the objective is too narrow we tend to get inadequate information [23]. To address the research questions stated above, the following objectives have been set for the study:

1. To understand the effect of demographics of the BoP customers towards branded essential products concerning the area under study.
2. To study the impact of the attitude of BoP customers towards branded essential products.
3. To study the influencers on BoPC towards the purchase of branded essential products.
4. To explore the driving factors of BoPR to serve the BoPC market.
5. To develop a tested model for BoPR to successfully engage BoPC.

1.11 POSTULATES

The Inductive Approach was used to formulate the Postulates of the study. When a researcher starts with a set of observations and moves on to develop a general set of propositions from those observations, when following an inductive approach, beginning with a topic, a researcher tends to develop empirical generalizations and identify preliminary relationships as he progresses through his research. No hypotheses can be found at the initial stages of the research and the researcher is not sure about the type and nature of the research findings until the study is completed. Inductive reasoning is often referred to as a “bottom-up” approach to knowing, in which the researcher uses observations to build an abstraction or to describe a picture of the phenomenon that is being studied, and thus using this set of observations can

create a conceptual framework of the study. This inductive approach has evolved the postulates and thereon the hypothesis for this study. The review study has identified the below postulates:

P₀₁: Consumer behaviour is determined by their attitude.

P₀₂: The attitude of the consumer influences the Promotional Strategies adopted by the marketers.

P₀₃: Promotional strategies adopted by the marketer influence consumers' purchase behaviour.

P₀₄: Promotional strategy plays a significant role in the relationship between Consumer Attitude and Purchase behaviour.

P₀₅: Promotional strategies of marketer play a significant role in influencing a BoPC purchase decision by BoPR.

1.12 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

To derive suitable answers to the research questions and to develop a measurable vector for the postulates identified that are driven towards addressing the objectives of the study, the following hypothesis has been formulated:

H1: Demographic factors of BoP customers will influence the purchase of branded essential products.

H2: Attitudinal dimension factors have an impact on purchase behaviour towards branded essential products.

H3: Occupation and income level of BoP customers tend to moderate the relationship between attitudinal dimensional factors and purchase behaviour towards branded essential products.

H4: Promotional strategies of the marketer have a direct effect on the purchase behaviour of branded essential products by the BoP customer.

H5: Occupation and income tend to moderate the relationship between promotional strategies and purchase behaviour of branded essential products by the BoP customer.

H6: The Purchase behaviour towards branded essential products is highly influenced by the seller's recommendation.

H7: Lower prices and referral purchases of the branded essential product will have more influence on the promotional strategies of the marketer.

H8: Awareness and affordability in the attitudinal dimension will have more effect on the purchase behaviour of BoP customers.

H9: Promotional Strategies of Marketer mediate the relationship between the attitudinal dimension and purchasing behaviour of branded essential products by the BoP Customer.

H10: Attitudinal dimension, purchase behaviour, promotional strategies of marketers and brand impact on the essential product are influenced by demographic factors.

H11: The attitude level of BoP customers toward branded essential products will have an impact on promotional strategies, purchase behaviour, and brand impact on essential products.

H12: The attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influenced by the tenure of business, Number of Walk-ins per Day, duration of a Stock purchase, and percentage of the known customer.

H13: Attitude of BoPR toward Branded Essential Products is Negative.

1.13 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to provide researchers and other stakeholders with information through which effective strategies could be devised to reach the BoP customer. The identification of the unique characteristics, socio-economic drivers, and factors affecting the purchase of branded essential goods may assist the companies of branded essential products to further understand and customize their offerings, strategies, promotional efforts, and other marketing efforts at the BoP with specific market-environments designed around very specific and unique demands of this category of customers. The companies would be able to build sustainable and scalable business models along the value chain. It would further help to understand BoP buyers' preference for promotional measures and their effectiveness. Attitudes are slowly formed and once formed are a cause for customer loyalty, this measure of customer acquisition may not be similar in the BoP as compared to the ToP customer.

Another facet of the study is the BoPR who is an opinion leader in the segment and understanding his motives, drives, and attitudes towards branded products bridges the gap that is there currently in reaching the pockets of the BoPC. The present study would be significantly helpful in formulating marketing, advertising, and promotional strategies by providing an understanding of what entices the BoP customer. Hence, the main inquiry of the present study concerns the understanding of the attitudinal and behavioural dimensions of the BoPC towards branded essential products.

1.14 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study has certain limitations that must be acknowledged. Attitudes and buyer behaviour are a vast, complex, and dynamic field of study. BoP is an unexplored segment of the population in India. The subjects chosen were urban BoP customers residing in an urban location, whether there is any mediating effect of location has not been studied and could be the subject of any future research. It was also challenging to conduct interviews with the respondents due to the non-availability of the main bread earner/decision-maker during the day because of their work commitments. However, substantial efforts were made to reach out to them and make sure the authentic information is elicited.

1.15 CHAPTER SCHEME

This doctoral thesis is systematically organized into seven chapters. A brief snapshot of each chapter is presented below.

Chapter 1: Introduction

The first chapter in addition to giving an insight into the nomenclature “Bottom of the Pyramid”, which was globally popularised by C. K. Prahalad [1], introduces the concepts under the study in the Indian context. The key concepts under the study are attitudes and perspectives, nevertheless limited to the Bottom of Pyramid Consumers (BoPC) concerning a few select Essential Products (EP). Furthermore, this chapter also introduces other two key dimensions of the study Bottom of Pyramid Retailers (BoPR) that are an integral part. The chapter addresses the research questions, objectives of the study, and postulates and hypotheses.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature and Conceptual Framework

This chapter reviews the existing literature on the key concepts and dimensions of the study to identify the research gap and adopt a mixed method exploratory approach to design a conceptual framework of the model which will be tested through a systematic quantitative and qualitative approach toward finding an ideal solution to the research problem.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

The third chapter deals with the research design and methodology adopted in this study. The chapter throws further light methodology adopted to test the conceptual model, and the sampling; data collection; data analysis techniques adopted that are most suitable to answer the key research question.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis and Interpretation

This chapter draws from the in-depth cross-sectional multi-dimensional sample study of BoPC and BoPR and an analysis of the multi-variant effects of the three dimensions on the BoPC attitudinal dimensions and perspectives using statistical tools and analysis techniques.

Chapter 5: ABCD Quantitative Framework and Discussion

The fifth chapter is an assimilation of the statistical analysis tools and the ABCD analysis framework. The results and discussion are based on the objectives and hypotheses formulated in the study. The findings and discussion based on a detailed ABCD study enlisted in this chapter form the foundation for the next chapter of suggestions.

Chapter 6: Findings and Discussion

Chapter six is an extension of the previous chapter that goes further to discuss the results and analyse the associations and determinations that emerge after the empirical study of the key concepts and dimensions to design and recommend an integrated refined framework for BoPB that can be used as a strategical tool to exponentially grow penetration into BoPC segment.

Chapter 7: Recommendations, Suggested Model and Conclusion

The last chapter provides a summary of the entire study about the stated objectives. The theoretical and practical contributions from the pools of the multi-dimensional analysis from mixed methods are summarised. A prescriptive model is suggested based on the analysis and results of the study. The model attempts to address the business implications for marketers in the BoP market and the scope for further research is addressed. A short conclusion brings the thesis to an end.

CHAPTER-II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1.1 INTRODUCTION

Any form of research begins with an analysis of the literature and studies that have already been done [24]. The literature review in this chapter provides an overview and analysis of previous studies on theoretical foundations and framework which form the basis and is used to position the study within the domain of academic research as well as to arrive at the research gap, but will also be used as a key source of data. This research uses a meta-analysis of prior articles to identify key attributes that will be used to give a better definition to describe the market opportunity at the base of the economic pyramid. Interdisciplinary research published in three focal areas of this study, namely, BoP, consumer behaviour in the area of branded products (which encompasses concepts in attitudes of consumers), and products and categorization are covered. This three-dimensional approach forms the basis of a clearly laid-out structure for the further study of attitudes of consumers in BoP towards branded essential products.

2.1.2 RELATED WORKS ON THE BoP

For further analyzing the BoP concept in a multi-disciplinary way, we have used the Scopus database to extract articles relating to the BoP. The keyword protocol that was used to retrieve the information was *TITLE-ABS-KEY ("base of the pyramid" OR "pyramid base" OR "base of pyramid") AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE, "j")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "DECI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "PSYC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "MULT"))*.

In the above keywords, filtration techniques were adopted, after which a selection of all articles from 1950 onwards yielded 275 articles. Selection of only journals and articles was done, and this yielded in the last ten years from 2010 to 2020 gave us 255 articles. From this repository, we excluded conference papers, books, and book chapters. This yielded the data as represented in figure 2.1. Almost half of the articles have been published by authors from the Business and Management discipline followed by Social Sciences and Economics.

Figure 2.1: Level of Focus on BoP Among Researchers Across Multiple Disciplines

Source: Scopus Metrics Data Search

Economic Perspective: The economic perspective of the BoP can be understood right through the work of economists like Adam Smith, and authors like Stuart L. Hart, C.K. Prahalad, and Eric Kacou [28] in their seminal work on the Wealth of Nation [25][26], Capitalism at the Crossroad [27], the Fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid [2], and Entrepreneurial Solutions for Prosperity in BoP Markets [28]. Economists have throughout the years talked about the deprived section of society and emphasized the need for corporate organizations as well as policymakers to join hands to uplift the economic standards of this segment by having innovative approaches and aligning them as collaborators in the process of production, marketing to develop the BoP market. The BoP is considered a viable segment to focus on from a country's economic growth aspect as well.

Socio-Psychological Perspective: It is opined that the BoP population is always more susceptible to exploitation because of the lack of formal education and information. Hence, certain thinkers believed that the BoP market should be served by those organizations that offer utilitarian products and services and help in alleviating the BoP status by offering them employment opportunities and fostering entrepreneurship. Also, when businesses invest to spur better health, improve education, and generate higher productivity, they expand their consumer base and increase the purchasing power for their goods and services [29].

Technological Perspective: As we can understand from a global viewpoint, the wealth pyramid representation depicts at the top of the pyramid around 2 billion people with the highest levels of income (i.e., North America, Western Europe, and the Pacific Rim), the middle of this pyramid represents close to 3 billion people (which comprises of the so-called emerging economies such as India, Brazil, and China), and the BoP represents approximately 2 billion people who live on less than USD 2 per day (which includes most of Sub-Saharan Africa, certain parts of Asia including India). This BoP represents low-income markets in which technology pervasiveness and access to adequate health services are very often seen to be inadequate primarily the problem being accessibility and affordability. As per previous studies, in the BoP, there are only 7 hospital beds and 15 health care workers for every 10,000 people. Over the last few years, however, more than seventy-five percent of people in these low-income markets have access to mobile phones (estimated at three out of five). Mobile phone adoption by the BoP has seen phenomenal growth over a period.

Business Management Perspective: The business management perspective has drawn the interest of a large number of authors and thinkers. A large body of research considers business-led efforts to improve the socio-economic well-being of the people living in the BoP communities. Extensive studies have revealed that marketers who create strategies catering to BoP businesses need to look at innovation and rethink structured paradigms. The poorest also spend money on the same things that the wealthy do, however, they spend it differently as they cannot buy large quantities of luxury goods or convenience goods, but they buy quality goods and credit availability and brands do lure them. It is further reiterated that the BoP is a huge consumer market with an aggregate gross domestic product of over USD 12.5 trillion.

Another study acknowledges and recognizes the BoP approach as an emerging business concept, and it has the potential to impact billions of poor people in the world. Studies also presented a framework that promoted selective consumption by the poor to avoid “undesirable inclusion” (marketing and selling of products that are not likely to improve their wellbeing) and avoiding “undesirable exclusion” (not offering products that are likely to enhance their wellbeing). This was further enhanced as a business angle by many thinkers on the business approach in BoP.

The literature review thus covers the emergence of the BoP proposition as originally introduced by Prahalad and Hart through the various phases of improvement and refinement that led to the recently introduced BoP protocol second edition [30] with specific reference and focus on case studies that were successfully implemented at BoP.

Since citation counts are considered important measures of intellectual influence, their analysis can lay out underlying patterns in the theoretical structure of a stream of literature [31]. We conduct citation analysis by mapping the citation counts of articles in our sample that were listed on the ISI Scopus database (a final set of 50 articles). Among these studies, the average number of citations was 152. A subtotal of 10 articles had more than that average number of citations, constituting 62.31% of the total citations.

Table 2.1: Core Studies in the Research Stream: Top 10 Most Cited Articles

Sl. No.	Author	Sources of Publication	Total Citation	Year
1	A Karnani [32]	California Management Review	1159	2007
2	CK Prahalad [33]	Journal of Product Innovation Management	864	2012
3	S Ansari, K Munir, T Gregg [34]	Journal of Management Studies	630	2012
4	A Kolk, M Rivera-Santos, C Rufin [35]	Business and Society	580	2014
5	DA Pitta, R Guesalaga, P Marshall [36]	Journal of Consumer Marketing	280	2008
6	KD Martin, R Paul Hill [37]	Journal of Consumer Research	253	2012
7	AG Karnani [38]	California Management Review, Forthcoming	252	2006
8	N Sinkovics, RR Sinkovics, M Yamin [39]	International Business Review	249	2014
9	M Olsen, E Boxenbaum [40]	California Management Review	227	2009
10	R Kuriyan, I Ray, K Toyama [41]	The Information Society	187	2008

The review of literature also describes the conceptual elements from an analytical standpoint; it looks at the content and approaches of various kinds of literature on the BoP over the years. This analysis aims at understanding the depth of study on the BoP so far in terms of content and approaches, to identify the research gap.

Figure 2.2: Literature Map

Source: Created by the Author

1. C. K. Prahalad, (1999) [1] The concept of BoP was propounded by C.K. Prahalad in his seminal work in 1999, later published work which theorized that there exists a huge, untapped, consumer market at the bottom of the economic pyramid and companies could stand to make substantial gains by tapping this market to sell products and services to the poor.

2. Prahalad and Hart, (2002) [2] The exploratory work published in 2005, in the book ‘The Fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid: Eradicating Poverty through Profits’ popularized the concept of the BoP and through case studies of some MNCs who succeeded or failed at the BoP, it brought focus to the BoP as a viable target segment for businesses while simultaneously asking for cooperation to make it an act to uplift the wellbeing in this segment. And innovation was the key to reaching out to this segment which has tremendous potential to be served.

3. Hart S. L., Christensen C. M. (2002) [42] In this prescriptive approach, the authors explore solutions to the argument that multinationals should balance social equality with profitability. The authors illustrate their point with examples of companies that are already profitably disrupting such industries as telecommunications, consumer electronics, and energy production

4. Hart, S. L., & London, T. (2005) [43] in their case study exploratory work of 24 case studies of firms working in this segment were studied and concluded that businesses using the same strategies as in other segments were not successful and this called for second-generation researchers to build stronger empirical and theoretical foundations.

5. A. Karnani (2005) [44] in his critical analysis of the BoP proposition has said that it is only a harmless illusion and potentially a dangerous delusion. His work critiqued that the BoP argument is riddled with inaccuracies and fallacies, and proposed an alternative perspective on how the private sector can help alleviate poverty by viewing the poor as producers, and emphasizing buying from them, rather than selling to them and it was the only way to alleviate poverty by raising the real income of the poor.

6. A. Karnani (2006) [38] In his analytical work has argued that the opportunities at this base of the pyramid are merely a mirage and there are numerous challenges in marketing socially useful goods to the poor which Prahalad has not considered. Karnani concludes that any effort to alleviate poverty needs to consider the poor as producers and companies should devise their supply chains and emphasize buying from them instead of selling to them.

7. A. Karnani (2007) [32] In his continued work of a case study approach empirically examined the proposition by studying in depth the case of 'Fair & Lovely,' a skin whitening cream marketed by Unilever in many countries in Asia and Africa concluded that companies had to find a match between private profits and public welfare and only then good could be created for the poor.

8. DA Pitta, R Guesalaga, P Marshall (2008) [36] The authors of a prescriptive approach examine the bottom of the BoP proposition, where private companies can both be profitable and help alleviate poverty by attending to low-income consumers. The paper prescribes managers' guidance on how to modify their marketing tactics to sell to the BoP market, as well as what kind of relationships they should form to succeed.

9. Bang and Joshi (2008) [45] Discussed the importance of market expansion as an important strategic option in developing economies. They also emphasized how marketing to the BoP has highlighted the issue of direct involvement of corporations in expanding markets.

10. S Vachani, NC Smith (2008) [46] The authors delve into how rural markets are large; ignored in intense heavy competition, and prescribe strategies for reaching BoP.

11. Hahn, R. (2009) [47] Later examined and understood the nuances of this low-income market. He built an ethical rationale for creating business opportunities for the poor by integrating concepts of BoP, sustainable development as well as corporate citizenship.

12. M Olsen, E Boxenbaum (2009) [40] Through an exploratory approach the authors propound that the leading global companies of 2020 will be those that provide goods and services and reach new customers in ways that address the world's major challenges including poverty, climate change, resource depletion, globalization, and demographic shifts. The authors explore the segment to align business strategies in BoP.

13. J Cross, A Street (2009) [48] Another exploratory study by the authors explores what anthropology has to say about contemporary business strategies for market expansion among poor consumers in Africa and Asia. Focusing on the activities of global consumer goods company Unilever in India, they prescribe how anthropology can lead to reaching this connected segment.

14. London T., Anupindi R., Sheth S. (2010) [49] In this exploratory approach of the base of the pyramid (BoP) literature grounded in the proposition of mutual value creation, an important but not yet well-tested relationship between businesses is the BoP producers angle. The authors analyze the BoP from the producer's perspective and suggest strategies.

15. Santos and Rufin (2010) [50] systematically applied the analytical frameworks of international business and strategic management to explore the differences, in business and social networks, in the TOP (Top of the Pyramid) and BoP. They conclude by developing a network model, to allow MNCs to develop appropriate products for the BoP markets at a profit.

16. Karamchandani, A., Kubzansky, M., & Lalwani, N. (2011) [51] The authors in this work emphasized that while the BoP market has vast untapped potential it also poses numerous challenges which make it unique, and hence despite the willingness

it is not viable for every product or company. They argued this as very few companies from a few industries such as telecommunications, FMCG, and pharmaceuticals have been truly successful in this market. Hence, it is safe to conclude that the bottom of the pyramid is not meant for every company, however, motivated it might be to engage with this population.

17. Rangan, V. K., Chu, M., & Petkoski, D. (2011) [13] The author's work emphasizes that BoP is a risky place for business, but decent profits can be made there if companies link their financial success with their constituencies' well-being. Success requires appreciating the diversity at the base of the pyramid and the importance of scale in undertaking ventures there.

18. A Agnihotri (2012) [52] In an analytical study, the author's work is a compilation of various debates in favor of and against the BoP Market.

19. Prahalad, C. K. (2012) [33] In his continued exploratory work the author building on the dialogue of the BoP as a viable segment identifies the bottom of the pyramid markets as a new source of radical innovation. Managers can create an exciting atmosphere for innovation by focusing their emphasis on establishing awareness, access, affordability, and availability (4 As).

20. S Ansari, K Munir, T Gregg (2012) [34] The authors through a prescriptive approach provide a systemic framework to understand the social impact of business-driven ventures in the BoP. They argue that any business initiative in the BoP should be driven by and evaluated based on whether it advances the capability to transfer and enhances social capital, drawing heavily from the capability approach given by Amartya Sen.

21. A Kolk, M Rivera-Santos, C Ruf (2014) [53] In an exploratory approach the authors trace a decade of various thinkers' views on the BoP business strategy and review the work done.

22. Goyal, S., Sergi, B. S., & Jaiswal, M. (2015) [54] The authors study for-profit social enterprises, which bundle entrepreneurial attitude with the passion to design and implement inclusive business models targeting the basic needs at the Base-of-the-Pyramid (BoP). They draw out an understanding of the challenges and strategic choices required for inclusive business models at the BoP.

23. Chatterjee S. (2016) [55] The study through an exploratory approach attempts to examine some of the BoP texts to understand how and to what ends globalization is constituted within the BoP project. Extrapolating from themes like markets, capitalism, poverty, and technology, the article attempts to highlight what remains unsaid and inexplicit about globalization. Critically examines some of the underlying themes of the BoP proposition.

24. Sinha, P. K., Gupta, S., & Rawal, S. (2017) [56] In an exploratory approach, the authors develop a framework to understand how the bottom of the pyramid (BoP) retailers adopt brands that sell to a very different set of customers and are served through long indirect channels. The analysis brought out six criteria used by the retailers in selecting brands with demand for the brand as the most dominant factor.

25. Mathur, M. K., Mehta, R., Swami, S., & Bhatnagar, S. (2018) [57] In an exploratory approach, the authors use an empirical study conducted to understand the urban BoP consumers of Mumbai city. The study assumes importance as it focuses on the urban BoP as a realistic option to operate in the BoP by removing the dynamic barriers of the rural BoP. Additionally, it provides insight into the urban BoP market and its consumer behaviour.

26. Choudhury, N., Mukherjee, S., & Datta, B. (2019) [58] In an analytical approach factors affecting decision-making at the BoP and propose a framework of the consumer decision-making process at the base of the pyramid (BoP). It was observed that the consumers at the Bop make constrained choices due to their vulnerability and try to minimize transaction costs while selecting the retailers. The constrained retail choice leads to a limited selection of products and brands.

27. Lappeman, J., Ransome, K., & Louw, Z. (2019) [59] The authors aim to show that a generic bottom-of-the-pyramid (BoP) segmentation strategy does not represent a multi-country BoP consumer profile. A series of multinational entry failures have clearly shown that a one-size-fits-all strategy is inappropriate for an emerging market.

28. Nagy, M., Bennett, D., & Graham, C. (2019) [60] The authors test the premise that brand growth can come from targeting the poorest consumers at the bottom of the economic pyramid (BoP). This study is the first that uses quantitative marketplace data covering BoP consumer purchase records.

29. Chmielewski, D. A., Dembek, K., & Beckett, J. R. (2020) [61] The last two decades of research brought up a lot of strategies in BoP, the author's reason that as a result, there is a growing academic and practitioner push for a third iteration-BoP 3.0-that moves closer to a sustainable development model of poverty alleviation. Through a grounded theory study of 21 Philippines-based organizations implementing poverty alleviation initiatives at the community level, this paper seeks to add to the existing suite of tools and guidance in the BoP field. It does so by questioning how these organizations approach the development and implementation of market-based approaches to poverty alleviation.

30. Aman, S., & Seuring, S. (2021) [62] In an interesting analytical approach to performance measurement using (Sustainable) supply chain performance management as a theoretical basis, 91 BoP-related papers are analyzed, applying content and contingency analysis to determine if innovation enables sustainable competitive advantage at the BoP and operational performance measures dominate the body of literature. The BoP literature has very many approaches associated with trying to look at BoP from various angles. Further conceptual understanding can be gained in the second part of this chapter.

2.1.3 RELATED WORKS ON BoPR:

Though there has been a considerable amount of research on BoP in the global context, especially in the western market. Little research has been done to understand brand adoption in BoP markets, more so in the Indian context where there is a huge unorganized retail market catering to the needs of consumers, especially BoP.

31. Simanis & Duke, (2014) [63] This article explores many ways businesses might help the world's poorest people-those at the base of the pyramid-by putting a priority on doing good business rather than just doing good. The authors argue that a regular stream of revenues from controllable businesses will open the door for eventual investments in grandiose projects that benefit society. The authors identify two key obstacles to economically selling to the base of the pyramid: altering customer behaviour and altering the production and delivery of goods. They have created an "opportunity map" that categorizes opportunities along a spectrum from the least difficult and resource-intensive to the most, to assist businesses in understanding how

these issues affect different business chances. Opportunities for targeted marketing in developed markets are at the simpler end. Opportunities in growth markets, such as initiatives to rethink products or expand or develop new distribution channels, are in the middle. Frontier-market initiatives, on the other end of the spectrum, aiming to establish new markets, grow into greenfield markets, develop new business models, or take market share from rivals. The writers illustrate each kind with examples and go over how businesses might chase several possibilities at once. They can promote their social missions and make money if they make the right decisions.

32. McGrath, Kayser, & Dalsace, (2021) [64] Concerns about the dearth of vendors offering useful goods at the base of the pyramid were brought up in this article (BoP). This is not just a tale of businesses dying; it is a dramatic one as low-income people lose out on things that could enhance their quality of life. Instead, they carry on drinking contaminated water, using dangerous kerosene lamps to light their houses, cooking on stoves that kill over 1 million people year and becoming sick from mosquito bites. The authors made the case that adopting a particular perspective toward BoP clients is crucial to an organization's performance based on a multi-year field study program carried out in 25 nations. Many businesses begin with the premise that BoP customers are unemployed, uneducated, and/or without jobs. Successful businesses, in contrast, begin with the premise that customers can and will pay if they are given a good response to their demands and reassurance over the degree of risk involved. They outlined the many value proposition, communication, and distribution strategies that result from this mentality shift and demonstrated how these activities can make or break the organization's capacity to sustain it financially.

33. Kumar, Kumra, & Singh, (2022) [65] The difficulties that the BoP manufacturers confront are the main focus of this article. Contrary to the producers' perspective, the consumer perspective has dominated the Base of the Pyramid (BoP) narrative. The body of research on the challenges that BoP producers face in situations where resources are few is still dispersed and fragmented. As a result, this works thoroughly analyses and combines earlier research on the restrictions faced by producers at the base of the pyramid. They offered eight hypotheses about the limits faced by BoP manufacturers by synthesizing diverse lines of research. They also offer a thorough taxonomy of the restrictions that BoP manufacturers must deal with. Three

categories make up this enlarged typology: institutional restrictions, organizational constraints, and psycho-social constraints. The research offered a conceptual framework for advancing a multi-level, recursively connected, and process-based understanding of these restrictions, drawing on the marketing system view. The article explains various consequences for academics, managers, and policymakers, as well as helpful ideas for future research.

34. Rajagopal, (2009) [66] In Bottom-of-the-Pyramid (BoP) markets, this article attempted to present new models of brand management that took into account the characteristics, appearance, technology, and reputation of the companies that are connected to the brands. After reviewing earlier research studies, the paper promoted new methods for boosting the performance of multinational brands in BoP market segments, enhancing brand positioning techniques, assessing brand attributes, measuring brand performance and consumer value, and highlighting brand dynamics in a cutthroat industry. The study made the case that high transaction costs and issues with coordination along the brand promotion, consumption, and consumer value chains limit the performance of global brands in low-profile consumer market niches. Therefore, companies intending to manage brands in BoP target markets must lower brand costs by raising sales volume and enhancing consumer value. BoP market segments' brands are deeply ingrained in society and culture. They are positioned using the power of the premium market's brand equity and jointly developed by businesses and consumers. BoP brands, as opposed to conventional brands, might be sufficiently adaptable to enable brand perceptions in the rural and semi-urban consumer categories.

2.1.4 RELATED WORKS ON BRANDED PRODUCTS

The literature concerning the dimension of branded products in the study can be considered in two domains - one from literature purely on studies across concepts of branding - acceptability of branded vs. unbranded products, region-specific studies available on the same, and two - from the literature on branding in itself.

Table 2.2: Summary of the related works on the Branded Products

Author	Approach	Abstract	Title	Year
35. LM Kathuria, P Gill [67]	Empirical	The study was conducted to understand brand awareness among consumers and analyze the attitude of consumers towards selected branded commodity food products. An attempt was also made to examine the factors influencing the purchase of selected branded commodity food products.	Purchase of branded commodity food products: empirical evidence from India	2013
36. D Ubilava, KA Foster, JL Lusk [68]	Exploratory Approach	Because brands can signal reputation and serve as proxies for trust, consumer preferences for credence attributes may differ for branded and non-branded products.	Differences in consumer preferences when facing branded versus non-branded choices	2011
37. AA Berger [69]	Exploratory Approach	The author accomplishes bringing forth what brand means and its various dimensions.	The branded self	2011
38. SA Hasan, MI Subhani, M Osman [70]	Exploratory Approach	Cointegration was used to understand and judge the co-variation between branded and me too (unbranded) products. Exclusive insights were revealed between the two different classes of products that an increase in consumers' income level urges consumers to increase their consumption of branded products.	A battle between branded and me-too brands (unbranded) products	2012

After an extensive review of various kinds of literature, many constructs were identified. Based on the identified constructs this chapter has been divided into related works concerning individual constructs and their relationship with each other to get a better understanding of the variables and to establish hypothesized relationships among them intending to propose a model.

2.1.5 RELATED WORKS ON IDENTIFIED CONSTRUCTS

A review of the selected constructs is very essential to understand their significance for a particular population. These previous studies help the researchers to understand the existing understanding of the topic directing them to find knowledge gaps and propose a research model.

2.1.5.1 Attitudinal Dimensions

39. Dibsall *et al.*, (2003) [71] The major goal of this study was to identify the attitudes and behaviours of low-income consumers toward fruits and vegetables, with a focus on concerns of availability, affordability, and incentive to consume these foods. 680 low-income men and women, ages 17 to 100, responded to a questionnaire survey that was addressed to residences controlled by a significant UK housing association. Research has supported the UK Government's policy, which is based on the idea that low-income populations have trouble accessing and affording fruits and vegetables. Access and affordability were only a minor part of the "issue" surrounding low fruit and vegetable consumption, according to the findings from this particular group. These were the three main hurdles. Thus, it is necessary to find more potential factors that could have a bigger impact.

40. Adams, (2015) [72] The nature and prognostic value of attitudes and purchasing intentions as aggregate time series data were the focus of this article. The attitude data showed a variety of attitudinal dimensions, although there is a great deal of informative overlap between them. The most significant element of the time series variation in attitudes is consumer expectations regarding the near-term business scenario. The contradictory results of previous time series and cross-section studies may be explained by the fact that this attitudinal component is predicted to appear better in time series than in cross-sections. Regression analysis of attitudes and purchasing intentions as consumer durable expenditure predictors reveal that attitudes significantly influence the forecasting of durable expenditures. Purchasing insurance does not increase the connection after attitudes and income are factored into the equation, leading to the impression that in time series, the orthogonal components linked to purchasing insurance have little predictive significance. These findings support the idea that attitudes are an important predictor of customer expectations.

41. Kim, & Chung, (2011) [73] This study aimed to further explore the moderating impact of perceived behavioural control on the attitude intention relationship by observing the impact of customer perceived value and previous experiences on buyer intention to purchase organic personal care products using the theory of planned behaviour (TPB). 207 members of an online panel participated in a survey that was performed online, and multiple regression analysis was utilized to examine the correlations between the variables. The findings showed that attitudes toward

purchasing organic personal care products are positively influenced by environmental consciousness and appearance consciousness. The TPB model was enhanced by the inclusion of prior experiences as a determinant of purchasing behaviour and perceived behaviour control as a moderator of the attitude-buy intention link. According to this study, shops can improve consumer intent to purchase organic personal care products by creating effective marketing tactics that emphasize natural beauty, consumer safety, and reasonable prices.

42. Lee, Suh, & Whang, (2003) [74] To overcome barriers to interpersonal interaction in online shopping malls, this study proposed the idea of situation awareness. It also used a laboratory experiment with a 232-factorial design to test the impact of situation awareness information on user attitudes. User awareness and workspace awareness were classified as two independent variables for situation awareness information. The emotional states of pleasure, arousal, and dominance were used as mediating variables. The dependent variable used was user attitude. The findings are as follows: first, even while the number of people currently on the site had no discernible effects on these variables, the situation awareness information-equipped online mall created higher levels of enjoyment, arousal, and dominance. Second, the knowledge about user awareness increased pleasure, arousal, and dominance. Last but not least, the study shows that emotional states had a big impact on customers' attitudes: higher pleasure and arousal made people feel better about going to the mall.

43. Srivastava, Mukherjee, and Jebarajakirthy, (2021) [75] the foundations of the social comparison theory and the trickle-down effect theory were used in this study to examine the factors influencing the aspirational consumption of the Indian base of the pyramid (BoP) consumers. For this study, a qualitative phenomenological methodology was used. Thematic analysis of 35 in-depth interviews with BoP consumers in Kharagpur, India, revealed that aspirational consumption at the BoP is sparked by BoP people's propensity to engage in within-group and across-group social comparison, as well as their need for safety, comfort, advancement, and wellbeing. By creating a theoretical framework that demonstrates the causes of aspirational consumption at the BoP, this study made a significant contribution to the literature on the BoP market. Both the trickle-down impact theory and the social comparison theory were advanced by this study.

44. Batra, R., & Ahtola, O. T. (1991) [76] Theoretically, it has been proposed that consumer attitudes have different hedonic and utilitarian components and that the proportion of these two components that make up consumers' overall attitudes varies among product categories. The three studies cited in this paper validate measurement scales for these constructs and using them, they demonstrate that these two attitude dimensions do appear to exist, are based on various types of product attributes, and are theoretically consistent in their differential salience across various consumer products and behaviours. Although the scales used in the three studies were slightly different, the overall evidence leads us to believe that the utilitarian component can be most accurately assessed using the SD items of useful/useless, valuable/worthless, beneficial/harmful, and wise/foolish, and the hedonic component using the items pleasant/unpleasant, nice/awful, and agreeable-disagreeable. Good/bad, positive/negative, like/dislike, and favorable/unfavorable SD items, it would seem, most clearly measure overall attitudes, but they occasionally load on the hedonic element. It is clear that some qualities-such as pleasant, attractive, agreeable, cheerful, intriguing, comfortable, and soothing-are almost always hedonistic, whereas others-such as valued, wise, safe, ordered, and sane-are virtually always utilitarian. Also take note of the fact that some items (such as positive, good, favorable, and rewarding) load most frequently on both components, thus representing what we may refer to as general sentiments.

The above review has directed toward the various indicators of attitude such as awareness, affordability, accessibility, visibility, relationship with the seller, and brand factors. These parameters will be considered as various indicators to measure the attitude which will be proposed in the model further testing will be done in the coming chapters.

2.1.5.2 Promotional Strategies

45. Chikweche & Fletcher, (2013) [77] This essay's goal was to investigate how customer relationship management (CRM) is used at the base of the pyramid (BoP). The study on the use of CRM at the BoP was carried out utilizing qualitative interaction research techniques and case studies. The main conclusions demonstrated that at the BoP, CRM is an important strategic tool that businesses can utilize and that is made possible by ties and connections they have with customers' social networks.

The study may need to be replicated in additional BoP marketplaces to increase generalizability utilizing larger samples. Managers can learn from the study about the value of CRM at the BoP and how well-executed planning and management are essential for the concept's success.

46. Mishra & Jaikumar, (2021) [78] Although consumers at the bottom of the pyramid (BoP) have been extensively studied in the literature that is currently available, there appear to be some gaps in our knowledge of the unique cognitive traits of low-income consumers as a result of their resource-constrained environments and uncertain upbringings. In this work, they made an effort to fill this gap by concentrating on executive functions, a group of crucial cognitive processes, and how poverty-induced peculiarities affect them (EFs). Through several hypotheses and a conceptual framework, we specifically explore the potential effects of such EF anomalies on a BoP consumer's information processing skills, decision-making processes, and consumption patterns. The two basic EFs of inhibition and working memory are the main emphasis. They tend to make BoP consumers more susceptible to persuasive messages because they lack the necessary levels of self-control, goal-directed behaviour, analogy processing, and comparative evaluation skills. The study's management, policy, and research implications are then presented.

47. Beninger & Robson, (2015) [79] To advance knowledge of marketing in the Base of the Pyramid (BoP), this paper suggested that there is a compelling case for why marketing practitioners and academics should be interested in these markets. The authors analyzed the body of research on BoP customer behaviour and marketing promotions while describing the BoP market. Then they highlighted discrepancies between what happened in reality and the available academic research and provided several contemporary practitioner methods for marketing in the BoP. To educate marketing professionals about potentially effective strategies and missed opportunities, they offered four key takeaways in their conclusion: mobile marketing, non-traditional marketing options, the importance of nurturing word-of-mouth, and the existence of creative consumers in the BoP.

48. Purohit, Paul, & Mishra, (2021) [80] This study's goal is to rethink the traditional marketing mix for Bottom of the Pyramid (BoP) markets and suggest a redesigned framework by rearranging the components following the viewpoint of the

consumer while maintaining the fundamentals of services marketing. A survey was used to gather primary information from 400 participants from the BoP's urban and rural marketplaces. Findings showed that the BoP members' requirements and perspectives differ from those of the Middle of the Pyramid (MoP). This fact should be taken into account by managers when creating marketing mix plans for BoP markets. A redesigned marketing mix approach for clients in the BoP markets is presented in this study for the first time in its type. The five Ps of the framework are personalization, product, place, service delivery procedure, and price. As a result, in the context of service marketing and the BoP, a theoretical contribution is made.

49. Sharma & Bumb, (2021) [81] To target the Bottom of the Pyramid (BoP) markets, marketers must overcome a plethora of obstacles relating to awareness, pricing, availability, and accessibility. The goal of this research was to list the difficulties faced by marketers when trying to sell their goods to rural customers during COVID-19. The study focuses on 25 issues that previous research on marketing in rural areas identified as problems. In addition to the issues being identified through literature research and marketing strategies, an effort is made to contextually relate the challenges to one another. Three intensive focus group talks with a total of six specialists were held for this purpose. According to the findings, the variables "Living Standards," "Habits," "Price Sensitive," "Reachability," "Counterfeit Products," "Seasonal Demand," "Quality," "Buying Decision," and "Brand Loyalty" are referred to as the dependent problems. Independent variables, the final type of variable, have a strong influence or driving strength and little dependence. Infrastructure, Cultural Differences, Patriarchal Society, Language, Packaging, Influence of Intermediaries, Distribution Channels, Family Size, Sex Ratio, Lifestyle, and Product Awareness are some of the issues that need to be addressed.

50. Sheth, (2021) [82] This study examined major historical advancements in consumer behaviour, marketing analytics, and marketing strategy. The second portion of the report outlined brand-new fields of study in consumer behaviour, marketing analytics, and marketing strategy. The creation of value for customers, brand value, selling discipline, pricing science, reverse marketing, and the function of marketing in society were all topics covered in this study. The report ended by speculating that although in the past techniques sought out data, in the future data will seek out techniques, including video analytics.

51. Gupta, Pirsch, & Pirsch, (2013) [83] Marketing to the world's poor is advantageous for businesses and can result in significant revenue growth, according to Bottom of Pyramid (BoP) research. But marketing to BoP consumers can also be harmful, raising moral questions about unethical marketing techniques. The average (non-BoP) consumer's ethical assessment of marketing to the BoP is measured in this article, along with the consumer's willingness to hold a corporation accountable for unethical marketing practices. Findings reveal that as long as marketing strategies are deemed to be fair to BoP consumers, non-BoP consumers do not believe businesses are acting unethically when they market to the BoP. Non-BoP customers will, however, take legal action against businesses they believe are marketing to BoP customers unethically.

2.1.5.3 Purchase Behaviour

52. Subrahmanyan & Gomez-arias, (2008) [84] This article sought to investigate the relatively new field of consumption and how businesses may best meet those requirements. With examples of both goods and businesses in Asia, Africa, and Latin America, the writers categorized the goods and services consumers at the base of the pyramid use. The authors discovered that BoP consumers are educated and inventive despite having limited resources and finances. They are driven by more than just physiological and survival requirements; instead, they also try to satisfy higher-order demands to develop their social and cultural capital or as a form of self-preservation. Additionally, they discover that businesses have a better chance of succeeding when their products also address these higher-order demands, particularly when these items are connected to opportunities for employment and education.

53. Sharma, B. R., & Gupta, N. (2021) [85] This study sought to understand how BoP customers shopped to pinpoint the factors that influenced and hindered their purchasing choices. By conducting in-depth one-on-one interviews with 100 BoP customers who were present at Vishal Mega Marts (VMMs) in a northern Indian city, the study adopted a qualitative methodology. The findings showed that BoP customers want a better shopping experience just like wealthy customers, but their limited budgets prevent them from purchasing premium items. Exorbitant discounts, gifts, coupons, peer pressure, and seasonal incentives by VMMs all work to influence BoP buyers.

54. Barki & Parente, (2010) [86] The goal of this paper is to combine Brazilian low-income values with well-known marketing concepts, such as the "halo effect," "relationship marketing," "brand loyalty," and "value proposition," to not only recognize and describe the unique attributes of Brazilian poor shopping and consumer behaviour but also to describe the determinants of such behaviour. The empirical, qualitative research that formed the basis of this study included in-depth interviews and focus groups with low-income consumers. They discovered that the Brazilian BoP had different configurations of value perception than their wealthier countrymen, a stronger need to make up for an integrity deficit and poor self, a stronger preference for individualized connections, a high ambition to feel socially involved in society, and a preference for stores with a populated and overcrowded interior.

55. Chikweche, Stanton, & Fletcher, (2012) [87] The bottom of the pyramid (BoP) family purchase decision-making process is claimed in this research to be dynamic, heterogeneous, and an evolving process that can be modified by contextual macro-environmental limitations. This Zimbabwean study seeks to offer a divergent viewpoint because conventional conceptions of family buying decision-making are mostly derived from western marketplaces. The research was conducted using qualitative data collection techniques such as in-depth, one-on-one customer interviews, focus groups, ethnographic observations, and case studies. The key discoveries of this paper were the identification of shifting and multiple families' buying patterns, which are affected by the consumers' restricted experience at the BoP, as well as the specific roles of children, which differ from those that are typical in affluent western countries.

2.1.6 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONSTRUCTS

2.1.6.1 Related Works on Consumer Attitudes and Behaviour

56. Belch & Belch (2004) [88] define consumer behaviour as "the process and activities people engage in when searching for, selecting, purchasing, using, evaluating, and disposing of products and services to satisfy their needs and desires". The study of consumer behaviour borrows very heavily from psychology, social psychology, anthropology along with other disciplines. Hence, any study of the attitudes of consumers would be incomplete without a study of consumer behaviour in its whole sense.

57. Wilcock *et al.*, (2004) [89] It has been demonstrated that consumer attitudes can affect and predict behaviour. The different consumer attitudes regarding food safety are highlighted in this review. Consumer diversity is influenced by several variables, including demography and socioeconomic condition. This article also examines the relationship between customer attitudes, knowledge, and behaviour regarding food safety. It shows that various attitudes do not always translate into actions that improve the safety of the food consumed. Conclusion: Consumers who have questions about food safety should seek professional guidance.

58. Karam, (2015) [90] Brand awareness has developed into a significant factor that affects how customers perceive a brand. Success in brand management results from a knowledge of and careful management of brand loyalty and image to develop powerful traits that will influence consumers when they make decisions. This thesis focused on the significance of five aspects of customer-built brand equity (brand awareness, brand loyalty, brand image, and consumer behaviour) in light of consumers' impressions of a brand. This is founded on the premise that all of these customer-driven brand image and loyalty factors will affect how consumers perceive the company. The goal of this study was to determine which of these three factors—brand image, brand loyalty, and consumer behaviour—seems to have the least brand equity in restaurants, as well as whether there are any differences in customer-based brand equity between fast food and restaurants in terms of each of the four brand awareness, brand image, consumer behaviour, and brand loyalty characteristics. Brand loyalty appears to have the lowest brand equity ranking among the three aspects among customers. However, the dimension appears to affect how consumers perceive a brand. The authors of this paper also offered a media-based strategy for brand recognition that could assist retailers in promoting their goods in light of customer behaviour.

59. Notani, (1997) [91] The significance of affordability concerns, which should be equally crucial, has been overlooked by consumer researchers, although they have established that attitudes and buying intentions are significant predictors of purchase. This study looked at how affordability perceptions affect both purchasing intention and actual behaviour. They discovered that, in contrast to attitude and subjective norms, perceptions of affordability enhance the prediction of purchase intent.

Additionally, affordability perceptions do not depend on attitudes to influence them; rather, they have a direct impact on purchase intentions. However, this improvement in prediction is only seen when consumers believe the product to be relatively expensive. In addition, when a product is perceived to be relatively expensive, the effect of affordability perceptions on actual purchase is not completely mediated by purchase intent; however, when a product is perceived to be more easily affordable, purchase intent is completely mediated; and perceptions of affordability moderate the attitude-intention, subjective norm-intention, and the purchase intention-purchase relationships.

60. Panda, Masani, & Dasgupta (2021) [92] This study looked at whether Bottom of the Pyramid (BoP) customers can establish consumer categories based on how they perceive certain packaging qualities while making a packaging-influenced purchase (PIP) decisions for Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) products. This study aimed to provide a significant contribution to the literature on "BoP consumer behaviour," where a clear research deficit exists, in addition to making targeting easier for marketers. Due to the minimal engagement of the FMCG sector, most purchases are made within time constraints. Therefore, packaging, as the point of contact between goods and consumers, has enormous potential to affect buying decisions. A sample of 1530 BoP consumers from West Bengal, an Indian state with a high Human Poverty Index, has been taken into consideration. A Self-Organizing Map (SOM) has been used for validation and visualization together with clustering methods. The outcome demonstrated the presence of distinct segments, as well as the diversity of packaging characteristics, affects.

Table 2.3: Summary of the related works on Consumer Attitudes and Behaviour

Author	Approach	Abstract	Title	Year
61. Ajzen, I., & Cote, N. G. (2008) [93]	Exploratory Approach	Personality variables and environmental attitudes as predictors of consumer behaviour	Consumer attitudes and behaviour	2008
63. JP Bray [94]	Prescriptive Approach	Prescriptive Cognitive Models were first developed in the 1960s when marketing researchers increasingly focused on beliefs and attitudes as determinants of consumer buying behaviour.	Consumer behaviour theory: approaches and models	2008
62. V Wanick, J Stallwood, A Ranchhod, G Wills [95]	Exploratory Approach	This paper aims to investigate the relationship between advergame design, advergame experience, and consumer behaviour across cultures. For this purpose, a study was designed to compare behaviour patterns across Brazilian and British cultures	Can visual familiarity influence attitudes towards brands? An exploratory study of advergame design and cross-cultural consumer behaviour	2018
63. L Zarantonello, BH Schmitt [96]	Exploratory Approach	This study investigates the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention and further classifies the customers on the above basis.	Using the brand experience scale to profile consumers and predict consumer behaviour	2010
64. MR Solomon [97]	Analytical Approach	The author explains through an exploratory approach consumer behaviour predominantly in Europe.	Consumer behaviour: A European perspective	2010
65. Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M [98]	Prescriptive Approach	Examines research on the relationship between attitude and behaviour considering the correspondence between attitudinal and behavioural entities. Such entities are defined by their target, action, context, and time elements. A review of available empirical research supports the contention that strong attitude-behaviour relations are obtained only under high correspondence between at least the target and action elements of the attitudinal and behavioural entities.	Attitude-behaviour relations: A theoretical analysis and review of empirical research	1980

2.1.6.2 Related works on Attitude and Promotional Strategies

66. Nthenge, (2015) [99] This conceptual study aimed to investigate the connection between consumer perception, product positioning, and marketing methods. The segmentation, targeting, and positioning (STP) theory, the bottom of the pyramid (BoP) theory, and the black box theory of consumer behaviour serves as the foundation for this study. The Bottom of the Pyramid (BoP) market has recently received attention in marketing, and several successful efforts have demonstrated how the poor may be served fairly and successfully by creating a clear marketing plan. This study examined the reality that any marketing strategy's effectiveness will be determined by the perception of the consumer, which can be gauged by how much of a sacrifice they believe the product to be. The success of marketing tactics at the base of the pyramid is heavily influenced by positioning, which involves creating a specific marketing mix to affect a potential customer's overall perception of a product. For evaluating the correlation between the three factors-marketing tactics, product positioning, and consumer perception at the base of the pyramid-a conceptual framework is offered. The author draws a critical conclusion by discussing the BoP market, portraying it as not having the success that has been advertised.

67. Chikweche, (2013) [100] The goal of this study was to analyze the factors that keep businesses operating in a challenging bottom of the pyramid (BoP) environment, detailing the difficulties in developing a market orientation and the essential elements of strategic marketing needed to successfully engage this market. Data from two local companies and two MNC subsidiaries that produce food and personal hygiene items in Zimbabwe were gathered using a mixed research technique approach that included qualitative research methods approach using case studies and ethnography observations. The presence of various macro environmental challenges, both newly identified and previously cited by BoP researchers, was confirmed, as were the BoP's attraction and viability. Multiple drivers for continued presence were also identified, and a strategic framework for effectively serving the market was then proposed. The focus is limited to the food and personal hygiene sector may limit the ability to generalize the results to a larger population. The sample chosen is modest but reflective of the bulk of sales of food and personal hygiene items in a developing country. The report went beyond the integrated marketing debate, which had been the main focus of earlier studies, to consider additional potential marketing techniques for the BoP.

68. Raj & Aithal, (2018) [101] This article aims to provide a thorough assessment of the literature on the consumer base, the base of the pyramid, its ramifications, and coverage in India. This topic has been the subject of years and years of research. The requirements of BoP customers sometimes overlap at different levels and are not always driven by lower-order needs. BoP consumers are typically driven by their requirements and their circumstances, therefore branding initiatives must be creative and adapted to their sociocultural demands and circumstances to be accepted. If sustainability and loyalty are to be built, branding in BoP segments needs to involve consumers from the segment product inception stage to the final delivery and after-sales stages. This cannot be achieved by simply elongating services and products sold in other markets using creative local media and word of mouth. Companies need to understand that co-creation and the need to think beyond the present to consider long-term sustainability is the next levels, as highlighted by research studies. The notion that BoP consumers are not simply consumers, but also the makers and sellers of some categories of goods and services, is another crucial factor that has received very little research.

2.1.6.3 Related works on Promotional strategies and purchase behaviour

69. Jaiswal & Gupta, (2015) [102] The goal of this study was to look at, pinpoint, and clarify aspects of consumer behaviour that demonstrate how marketing to BoP has an impact. The presentation also discussed the existing research on the advantages and disadvantages of marketing to BoP. The study's findings point to two major conclusions that describe the nature of BoP marketing and how it influences BoP consumer behaviour. First, BoP marketing has a significant impact on how the poor will behave when making purchases. Secondly, in India, the underprivileged show a high level of sensitivity to marketing campaigns. According to the research, BoP consumers have high brand knowledge, significant spending on products outside of their core bundle of consumption, are susceptible to advertising and sales promotions and make decisions based on aspirations.

70. Petrescu *et al.*, (2013) [103] A overlooked sector of the retail business, flea markets, were examined in detail in this essay. It considered the importance of this type of retail in contemporary society and how it might be developed for bottom-of-the-pyramid sectors after analyzing the flea market consumer profiles. A content

analysis was performed on 17 interviews gathered from customers and vendors of flea markets in the US and Romania using a qualitative approach through grounded theory. The findings show that (a) low prices and the opportunity to score a deal or a bargain are these forms of retailing's main selling points, and (b) consumer desires and necessities include not only cheap products but also the rush of discovering used and old "treasures," (c) people and diverse cultures represent a significant portion of flea markets' advantages, satisfying the human need for social communication and social interaction, and (d) the distinctions between consumption and consumption practices.

71. Lappeman & Kabi, (2017) [104] This study considered how sales promotions, which account for a sizeable portion of overall marketing spending, have been identified as a critical factor in customers switching brands. In the under-researched South African Bottom of the Pyramid market, this study discovered consumers' post-switching behaviour, in particular, the probability to stockpile after a consumer has switched brands. All of the constructs showed positive significant associations, and it was discovered that the kind of promotion had no moderating effect on the association between sales engagement and brand switching. However, brand switching did act as a mediator in the relationship between stockpiling and sales involvement.

72. Roy & Debnath, (2021) [105] This study's goal was to evaluate the unmet requirements of low-income Indian consumers. The study also identified the key subgroups of low-income consumers as well as the key variables affecting their purchasing behaviour. The study's final recommendation is to use the right marketing channels and methods to tap into the market potential of these segments. They conducted 102 in-depth structured interviews with low-income consumers from three eastern Indian areas. The respondents' living circumstances and unmet requirements were examined using an inductive content analysis method. A factor analysis was done to identify the main factors affecting consumer behaviour. The consumer segments were then determined depending on the fundamental constructs using cluster analysis. Regression analysis was then used to investigate how these constructs affected purchasing decisions. According to this report, the top three unmet needs are more affordable college, better housing, and adequate sanitation. Three significant low-income client segments were discovered by the investigation. The results showed

that market potential might be increased by road shows, flexible retail distribution methods, spot discounts, and flexible credit facilities from local shops. This study created insight into low-income clients' categorization and related marketing tactics based on their living circumstances, unmet demand, and media preference for the first time in India.

2.1.6.4 Related works on Promotional strategy as a mediator between Consumer Attitude and Purchase behaviour

73. Teng & Laroche, (2011) [106] The goal of this study was to demonstrate how the dual mediation model has been applied to account for consumer reactions to advertisements and brands. This study looked at the impact of advertising on consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions in multiple-ad and multiple-brand situations to incorporate advertisement effect and competitiveness into the framework. An experiment carried out in North America yielded 165 usable data in total. The results showed that a focal advertisements evaluation rises dramatically when there are more affective reactions to it. Additionally, according to their research, information regarding a competing advertisement and brand is processed similarly, and assessments of the competing advertisement and brand have a detrimental effect on assessments of the focal advertisement and brand. Advertisements effect is a significant factor in the construction of advertisement attitude and may be included in the dual mediation model to describe the impacts of advertising on customer behaviour, which are significant conceptual contributions of this work.

74. Na & Joseph, (2014) [107] The main factors influencing the purchasing attitudes and behaviours of the rural and suburban households were examined in this study, including the product features, media, sales promotion, and HH expenditure. Investigate the impact of attitude and buying motivation on purchasing behaviour. The consumer's purchase behaviour is heavily influenced by their consuming reason, personality, and lifestyle. Consumers in rural and suburban areas are more worried about the quality, brand name, and brand benefits of the personal care items they buy, according to a study on FMCG products like soaps and detergents. Further research revealed that once rural customers discovered which brands worked best for them, they were less likely to switch because of peer pressure, lack of access to their preferred brands, and societal pressure. When their favourite personal care brand isn't

available at the store where they frequently shop, they frequently visit another retail location to buy it since they don't give in easily. Along with product qualities, motive, attitude, and shop attributes also have a big impact on how rural and semi-urban consumers behave while buying FMCG. Local merchants were discovered to be crucial, particularly when the respondents lack literacy. These shop owners welcome customers and educate them about the brand, its advantages, and any current promotions. To reach rural consumers who lack literacy, the marketer must build strong relationships with the local merchants. Gaining an advantage over regional brands offered in rural areas is also made possible by the support and collaboration of neighborhood shopkeepers. Friends and social groups were found to have a significant impact on respondents who were single because they participate in brand discussions to make purchasing decisions. Younger respondents are significantly influenced by the package element because they like appealing package colors and designs, but illiterates frequently associate a brand with its packaging color rather than its name. There are various reasons why the level of loyalty in the FMCG industry is still low. The most crucial aspect in determining a purchase is quality, while pricing plays a significant role. Schemes consistently entice more and more customers to a specific brand. It also provides information on the aspects that customers consider the most when purchasing a product. The two main offers/schemes that customers have encountered at the time of purchase are price off and extra quantity. CTV is the ideal mass media outlet for marketing a product that will appeal to the bulk of the rural and semi-urban viewership. The newspaper is used as a marketing tool for the product on the second spot. There are more popular and well-known free schemes on the market, like 1+1, 2+1, and others. If they come across better promotional plans that fit their budget and offer more quantity, lower costs, and good quality, people are willing to switch to another brand. Additional quantity at the same or lower cost, higher levels of happiness, quality, and other considerations can cause customers to switch to other brands.

75. Chou *et al.*, (2020) [108] This study on customer attitudes and purchasing behaviour were carried out for various populations. The objective of this empirical study is to validate the proposed research model in the Taiwanese context of explaining consumers' willingness to be environmentally friendly by operationalizing the relationship of green marketing's influence on consumer attitudes through the

mediating role of marketing mix towards green products. The model's structural equation modeling (SEM) foundation is made off of information gathered from 977 internet shoppers. The results showed that attitudes about green products significantly and indirectly influenced intentions for green consumption. Perceived quality also has a major and advantageous impact on the marketing mix and customer propensity to care about the environment. The consumer attitudes of the cognitive, emotional, and behavioural models (C-AB model) are less effective when a restaurant has high consumer social responsibility (CSR) for its marketing mix. The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) has been revived in part as a result of these findings, which provide a thorough understanding of consumer attitude, social responsibility, marketing mix, and perceived quality impact that a restaurant has on the capacity to increase consumer willingness to purchase green goods or food.

2.1.7 SUMMARY OF REVIEW

This chapter presented various key findings on related articles to visualize the existing forethoughts comprehending under-researched areas to fill up the knowledge gap. The first section under this chapter demonstrated various types of research about the Bottom of the Pyramid market which addressed Core studies in the research stream with the top 10 most cited articles. The review illustrated that there exists a huge, untapped, consumer market at the bottom of the economic pyramid and companies could stand to make substantial gains by tapping this market to sell products and services to the poor [1]. The studies are riddled with inaccuracies and fallacies [44] which directs to the question that how the private sector can help alleviate poverty by viewing the poor as producers. As a result, Bang and Joshi (2008) [45] discussed the importance of market expansion as an important strategic option in developing economies, by tacking these groups. In this regard, very few companies from a few industries such as telecommunications, FMCG, and pharmaceuticals have been truly successful in this market [51]. BoP is a risky place for business, but decent profits can be made there if companies link their financial success with their constituencies' well-being [13]. However, managers can create an exciting atmosphere for innovation by focusing their emphasis on establishing awareness, access, affordability, and availability [33]. Furthermore, it was observed that the consumers at the BoP make constrained choices due to their vulnerability and try to minimise transaction costs while selecting the retailers. In addition, much literature concerning Bottom of the

Pyramid retailers was also reviewed to assess their perception, which identified two key obstacles to economically selling to the base of the pyramid: altering customer behaviour and altering the production and delivery of goods [63]. Moreover, they also face various other constraints such as institutional restrictions, organisational constraints, and psycho-social constraints [65]. One study states that adopting a particular perspective toward BoP clients is crucial to an organization's performance [64]. A further literature survey was also done on branded products indicating the various factors influencing the purchase of selected branded commodity food products [67]. This also manifested that the brand serves as a proxy for trust, and consumer preferences for credence [68]. As discussed above many researchers have addressed the prospects and concerns on BoP, which gives us further direction to explore and understand their attitude, perception, and purchase behaviour. Hence, further critical review has been categorised and summarized below;

As a major part of the research, Related Works on Identified Constructs has discussed which the major construct was Attitudinal Dimensions. The previous research on attitude pondered that low-income populations have trouble accessing and affording fruits and vegetables [71]. Hence, Attitudes are an important predictor of customer expectations [72]. One study showed that emotional states have a big impact on customers' attitudes [74]. Attitude toward consumption at the BoP is sparked by BoP people's propensity to engage in within-group and across-group social comparison, as well as their need for safety, comfort, advancement, and well-being. Furthermore, consumer attitudes have different hedonic and utilitarian components-the utilitarian component can be most accurately assessed using the SD items of useful/useless, valuable/worthless, beneficial/harmful, and wise/foolish, and the hedonic component using the items pleasant/unpleasant, nice/awful, and agreeable-disagreeable. Good/bad, positive/negative, like/dislike, and favorable/unfavorable SD items, it would seem, most clearly measure overall attitudes, but they occasionally load on the hedonic element [76]. The above review has directed toward the various indicators of attitude such as awareness, affordability, accessibility, visibility, relationship with the seller, and brand factors.

In addition articles on promotional strategies were also reviewed which illustrated the use of customer relationship management (CRM) at the base of the pyramid (BoP)

[77]. To educate marketing professionals about potentially effective strategies and missed opportunities, the research has offered four key takeaways in their study which consists of mobile marketing, non-traditional marketing options, the importance of nurturing word-of-mouth, and the existence of creative consumers in the BoP [78]. A redesigned marketing mix approach for clients in the BoP markets is presented while discussing the five Ps of the framework which includes personalisation, product, place, service delivery procedure, and price [80]. Moreover, marketers must overcome a plethora of obstacles relating to awareness, pricing, availability, and accessibility [81]. The creation of value for customers, brand value, selling discipline, pricing science, reverse marketing, and the function of marketing in a society are all essential concepts under marketing [82]. The study related to Purchase Behaviour showed that BoP customers want a better shopping experience just like wealthy customers, but their limited budgets prevent them from purchasing premium items. But exorbitant discounts, gifts, coupons, peer pressure, and seasonal incentives by VMMs all work to influence BoP buyers [85]. The bottom of the pyramid (BoP) family purchase decision-making process is dynamic, heterogeneous, and an evolving process that can be modified by the contextual macro-environment [87]. The study of consumer behaviour borrows very heavily from psychology, social psychology, anthropology along with other disciplines. Hence, any study of the attitudes of consumers would be incomplete without a study of consumer behaviour in its whole sense [88]. It has been demonstrated that consumer attitudes can affect and predict behaviour [89]. Brand awareness as a component of attitude also acts as a significant factor that affects how customers perceive a brand [90]. The significance of affordability concerns, which should be equally crucial, has been overlooked by consumer researchers, even though they have established that attitudes and buying intentions are significant predictors of purchase [91]. One more study has also stated that Personality variables and environmental attitudes act as a predictor of consumer behaviour [93]. A review of available empirical research supports the contention that strong attitude-behaviour relations are obtained only under high correspondence between at least the target and action elements of the attitudinal and behavioural entities [98]. The success of marketing tactics at the base of the pyramid is heavily influenced by positioning, which involves creating a specific marketing mix to affect a potential customer's overall perception of a product [99]. TOP marketing has a significant impact on how the poor will behave when making purchases. Secondly, in

India, the underprivileged show a high level of sensitivity to marketing campaigns. According to the research, BoP consumers have high brand knowledge, significant spending on products outside of their core bundle of consumption, are susceptible to advertising and sales promotions and make decisions based on aspirations [102]. One study conducted in 2017 considered how sales promotions, which account for a sizeable portion of overall marketing spending, have been identified as a critical factor in customers switching brands [104]. Furthermore, the studies looked at the impact of advertising on consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions in multiple-ad and multiple-brand situations to incorporate ad effect and competitiveness into the framework [106]. The consumer's purchase behaviour is heavily influenced by their consumption reason, personality, and lifestyle as, consumers in rural and suburban areas are more worried about the quality, brand name, and brand benefits of the personal care items they buy, according to a study on FMCG products like soaps and detergents.

Overall, the previous studies gave direction to various constructs such as attitude, purchase behaviour, and promotional strategies. Based on the reviewed article it can be inferred that attitude has a significant contribution to the purchase behaviour of the BoP customers. At the same time, promotional strategies also play a significant role in influencing purchase behaviour by playing a mediating role between the attitude and purchase behaviour of the BoP customers.

2.2 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 BoP: The sheer vastness of the low-income (BoP) market, unfamiliarity with its customers, and the lack of ready means to reach them have all abetted in ensuring that marketers continue to be unaware of what drives them [109]. Moreover, the BoP market is not a homogenous market that companies can merely import or manufacture products for and try to sell to without appreciating the diversity and complexity of their consumers' needs, challenges, preferences, and aspirations [110]. The attraction of this market for companies increases as the consumers of this segment progress up the economic pyramid. As a growing segment in terms of population growth, especially in countries such as India, consumers of this segment are already forming their opinions and attitudes towards marketers. Hence, the need to find out the buying behaviour of the consumer at the urban BoP is more pronounced.

However, after reviewing the related literature on business models, it is observed that there is a lack of consensus on any one definition. Some authors focus on just some of the components such as the revenue model alone or the organization of delivering the firm's value proposition. There have been considerable studies on the potential of this market, and accordingly, various theoretical models and strategies have been proposed. In the BoP framework, a successful business strategy can also be a sound development strategy [111]. Prahalad also emphasizes the rising purchasing power and sound decision-making ability of the BoP consumers, which according to him, have been ignored by the companies. It is believed that much of the success of the organization in the BoP segment is dependent on its ability to deliver a product or service which contributes positively to the development of the BoP.

Sugawara (2010) [112] classified BoP business in terms of three types. Type 1 is concerned with identifying the specific needs of the BoP and fulfilling them.

The objective of this business is to first satisfy the needs of this sector at reasonable prices, even though independence and income are not generated for them at this stage. This, in turn, leads to the removal of the BoP penalty. The BoP penalty is the additional price the BoP market has to pay for basic needs. The Type 2 business aspires to not only satisfy the BoP sector needs and remove the BoP penalty; it also helps generate income and economic as well as social independence for them. At this stage, the BoP segment starts to fall in the middle-income bracket with higher disposable incomes. Here, the problem faced in doing business with low-income people is reduced. For example, the ability to read and write, and higher disposable income are easily fulfilled by people in the middle-income bracket. Taking the concept further, Sugawara states Type 3 business also. Here people in the low-income bracket can be turned into small entrepreneurs building on the concept of social entrepreneurship. In the last three years, there has been some work related to an understanding of the BoP consumer in one or two cities of the vast landscape of the country. India is very diversified in its socio-economic conditions, also with a large migratory population in the urban areas, BoP is undoubtedly a nascent opportunity for the marketer. But an understanding of the basket of services that this consumer chooses within his limited capabilities and how the consumer apportions his income

among the basket of products and services is going to be a key driver of purchase intention and finally purchase. A lot of socio-cultural and economic considerations are primary in the specific country context and herein a study of this kind is significant to shed light on the consumer and marketer.

2.2.2 ESSENTIAL PRODUCTS: Philip Kotler, an economist, devised a model that recognizes customers have five levels of need, ranging from functional or core needs to emotional needs. The model also recognizes that products are merely a means to satisfy customers' varying needs or wants. He distinguished three drivers of how customers attach value to a product:

***Need:** A lack of a basic requirement.*

***Want:** A specific requirement of products to satisfy a need.*

***Demand:** A set of wants plus the desire and ability to pay for the product.*

Customers will choose a product based on their perceived value. Satisfaction is the degree to which the actual use of a product matches the perceived value at the time of the purchase. A customer is satisfied only if the actual value is the same or exceeds the perceived value. Kotler attributed five levels to products.

Figure 2.3: Philip Kotler Five-Level Model

Source: Kotler, P. (2003) [113]. A framework for marketing management. Pearson Education India.

The five product levels are:

Core Benefit: The fundamental need or want that consumers satisfy by consuming the product or service. For example, the need to process digital images

Generic Product: A version of the product containing only those attributes or characteristics necessary for it to function. For example, the need to process digital images could be satisfied by a generic, low-end, personal computer using free image processing software or a processing laboratory.

Expected Product: It is the set of attributes or characteristics that buyers normally expect when they purchase products. For example, the computer is specified to deliver fast image processing and has a high-resolution, accurate color screen.

Augmented Product: The inclusion of additional features, benefits, attributes, or related services that serve to differentiate the product from its competitors. For example, the computer comes pre-loaded with high-end image processing software for no extra cost or at a deeply discounted, incremental cost.

Potential Product: This includes all the augmentations and transformations a product might undergo in the future. To ensure future customer loyalty, a business must aim to surprise and delight customers in the future by continuing to augment products. For example, the customer receives ongoing image processing software upgrades with new and useful features.

Goods can be classified based on the shopping habits of the customers. We can distinguish them as convenience, shopping, and specialty goods [114].

Convenience Goods are those the customer usually purchases frequently, immediately, and with a minimum of effort. Examples include tobacco products, soaps, and newspapers. Convenience goods can be further divided. Staples are goods consumers purchase regularly.

Impulse Goods are purchased without any planning or search effort. Candy bars and magazines are impulse goods. Emergency goods are purchased when a need is urgent umbrellas during a rainstorm; boots and shovels, during the first winter snowstorm. Manufacturers of emergency goods will place them in many outlets to capture the sale.

Shopping Goods are goods that the customer, in the process of selection and purchase, characteristically compares on such bases as suitability, quality, price, and style. Examples include furniture, clothing, used cars, and major appliances. Shopping goods can be further divided.

Homogeneous Shopping Goods are similar in quality but different enough in price to justify shopping comparisons.

Heterogeneous Shopping Goods differ in product features and services that may be more important than price. The seller of heterogeneous shopping goods carries a wide assortment to satisfy individual tastes and must have well-trained salespeople to inform and advise customers.

Specialty Goods have unique characteristics or brand identification for which a sufficient number of buyers are willing to make a special purchasing effort. Examples include automobiles, stereo components, photographic equipment, and men's suits. A car is a specialty good because interested buyers will travel far to buy one. Buyers invest time only to reach dealers carrying the wanted products. Dealers do not need convenient locations; however, they must let prospective buyers know their locations.

The consumer product market is a market for convenience goods, shopping goods, and specialty goods, which is usually categorized as a fast-moving consumer goods market, and market for consumer durable goods including automobiles.

Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) and the Market: Products that have a quick turnover, and relatively low cost are known as Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG). FMCG products are those that get replaced within a year. These products are purchased by the customers in small quantities as per the need of the individual or family. These items are purchased repeatedly as these are daily used products. The price or value of the products is not very high. Besides, these products have a short life. They include perishable and non-perishable products, durable and non-durable goods. Examples of FMCG generally include a wide range of frequently purchased consumer products, such as toiletries, soap, cosmetics, tooth-cleaning products, shaving products, and detergents, as well as other on-durables such as glassware, bulbs, batteries, paper products, and plastic goods. FMCG may also include pharmaceuticals, consumer electronics, packaged food products, soft drinks, tissue paper, and chocolate bars.

The Indian FMCG sector can be further described in detail. According to Kotler and Armstrong, the basic model of the consumer decision-making process comprises three major components, viz., marketing, and other stimuli (these act as influences), the buyer's black box (these are related to the consumer), and the buyer responses (this is the response part).

Figure 2.4: Consumer Behaviour Model by Philip Kotler [115][116]

The components/processes, as well as the working dynamics, are explained as follows:

Marketing and other stimuli: A consumer is confronted with a stimulus in the environment. This stimulus could be of two kinds.

- a) One that is presented by the marketer through the marketing mix or the 4Ps, product (attributes, features, appearance, packaging, etc), price (cost, value, esteem, prestige, etc), place (location and convenience, accessibility) and promotion (advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, publicity).
- b) The other that is presented by the environment could be economic, technological, political, and cultural.

Buyer's Black Box: The stimuli that are presented to the consumer by the marketer and the environment are then dealt with by the buyer's black box. The buyer's black box comprises two sub-components, viz., the buyers 'characteristics and the buyer's decision process. The buyer's characteristics could be personal, psychological, cultural, and social.

Personal: Age & life-cycle stage (family life cycle: single, newly married couples, full nest I, full nest II, full nest III, empty nest I, empty nest II, solitary survivor); Occupation(occupation affects consumption patterns); Economic situation; Lifestyle (pattern of living as Activities, Interest, Opinions); Personality (personality is defined in terms of traits; these are psychological characteristics which lead to relatively

consistent patterns of behaviour towards the environment) & self-concept (self-concepts reflective of identity; how a person perceives himself including attitudes, perceptions, beliefs, etc). Products and brands also have a personality; consumers are likely to choose such brands whose personalities match themselves.

Psychological: Motivation (motives; urge to act to fulfill a goal or satisfy a need/want); Perception (ability to sense the environment and give meaning to it through the mechanisms of selection, organization, and interpretation); Learning (a relatively permanent change in behaviour as a result of one's experience; relates to memory; learning could be experiential, based on direct experience or conceptually based on indirect experience; consumer learning could be based on marketing communication/seller-provided information, personal word of mouth and/or experiential); Beliefs (thoughts that a person holds about something; these are subjective perceptions about how a person feels towards an object/person/situation) and attitudes (a favourable or unfavourable disposition/feeling towards an object, person or a situation).

Cultural: Culture (a total of values, knowledge, beliefs, myths, language, customs, rituals, and traditions that govern a society). Culture exerts the broadest and the deepest influence, e.g., influences on our eating patterns, clothing, day-to-day living, etc. Cultural influences are handed down from one generation to the next and are learned and acquired; Sub-culture (a subset of culture: smaller groups of people within a culture with shared value systems within the group but different from other groups; identifiable through demographics).

Social Class: ordered and relatively permanent divisions/stratifications in the society into the upper, middle, and lower classes; members in a class share similar values, interests, lifestyles, and behaviours; the division is based on a combination of occupation, income, education, wealth, other variables.

Social: Family-The most important influence; (there occurs in a family what is referred to as socialization; family of orientation: parents and siblings; family of procreation: spouse and children; further some decisions are husband-dominated, some are wife dominated and some are joint; roles played by family members), family life cycle (stages through which a family evolves; People's consumption priorities change and they buy different goods and services over a lifetime); Friends and peers,

colleagues; Groups - reference groups - these are people to whom an individual looks as a basis for personal standards; they are formal and informal groups that influence buying behaviour; reference groups could be direct (membership groups) or indirect (aspirational groups); reference groups serve as information sources, influence perceptions, affect an individual's aspiration levels; they could stimulate or constrain a person's behaviour; Opinion leaders (they influence the opinion of others based on skills, expertise, status, or personality); Roles and status - 'role' refers to the expected activities and 'status' is the esteem given to role by society.

2.2.3 BoPR: Even though BoP has been the subject of a lot of research globally, particularly in the western market, In India, where there is a sizable unorganized retail industry serving the needs of consumers, notably BoP, little study has been done to assess brand adoption in BoP markets. There are substantial differences in functional dynamics between organized and unorganized retailers. Heeler *et al.*, (1973) [117] found a list of 13 items that affected the choice of a product by supermarket chains. They also found that these could be explained by an additive or compensatory model. Montgomery (1975) [118] explored the relationship between 18 variables and a supermarket buyer's decision to accept or reject a new product. Rao and McLaughlin (1989) [119] indicate how different variables influenced the decisions of the intermediary. Most of these studies focused on product adoption rather than brand adoption. Keller's work on customer-based brand equity has been able to bring to the fore the concept of brand knowledge on customers' responses to a brand. Here, a retailer is considered the first customer of a brand. It is found that prior brand knowledge possessed by retailers has a significant influence on the retailer carrying the brand and the brand adoption process by the consumer. Ailawadi (2001) [120] found that trade promotions, consumer promotions, and private brands were used by retailers and manufacturers to attract consumers. Further, the work was extended by Kumar and Steenkamp (2007) [121] argued that retailers tended to adopt private labels to counter the manufacturers and increase profitability. Retailers would introduce premium store brands that offered shoppers quality that equaled or surpassed that offered by manufacturer brands. Most of these studies related to brand adoption have been conducted in developed markets where organized retailing dominates. However, unorganized retailers in developing markets and more so those retailers serving BoP markets would rely on heuristics or personal judgments because

of a lack of access to any form of reliable data. Marketers have recognized the untapped potential of BoP markets; hence it is imperative and of critical need for upcoming literature to determine ways to serve these markets. Although no study has highlighted specific factors that govern the brand buying behaviour of BoP retailers, recent literature has thrown light on the retailing dynamics of rural markets, where a majority of the BoP population resides in developing economies like India (Planning Commission, Government of India, 2013) [122]. The closest attempt to decipher the buying behaviour of BoP retailers has been attempted by certain authors who have in studies proposed a heuristics framework that could provide a basis to study the choice behaviour of rural retailers.

2.2.4 THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK ON ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIOUR

The study of attitude formation studies how people form evaluations of persons, places, or things. The attitude of any person is determined by psychological factors like ideas, values, beliefs, perceptions, etc. All of these elements play a significant role in determining a person's attitude. Values are ideals, guiding principles in one's life, or overarching goals that people strive to obtain [123]. Beliefs are cognitions about the world's subjective probabilities that an object has a particular attribute or that an action will lead to a particular outcome [124]. Attitude may influence the attention to attitude objects, the use of categories for encoding information, and the interpretation, judgment, and recall of attitude-relevant information. This influence will be more powerful for strong attitudes which are accessible and based on an elaborate supportive knowledge structure. The durability and impact of influence depend upon the strength formed from the consistency of heuristics. Thus, we can conclude that attitudes can guide encoding information, attention, and behaviours, even if the individual is pursuing unrelated goals, and influence behaviour very strongly.

One of the most widely quoted attitude models is the Attitude component model. An influential model of attitude is the multi-component model, where attitudes are evaluations of an object that has affective, behavioural, and cognitive components (the ABC model).

- Affective component: The affective component of attitudes refers to your feelings or emotions linked to an attitude object. Affective responses influence attitudes in

several ways. For example, many people are afraid/scared of spiders. So, this negative affective response is likely to cause you to have a negative attitude towards spiders.

- Behavioural component: The behavioural component of attitudes refers to the way the attitude we have influenced how we act or behave.
- Cognitive component: The cognitive component of attitudes refers to the beliefs, thoughts, and attributes that we would associate with an object. Many times, a person's attitude might be based on the negative and positive attributes they associate with an object.

MODE MODEL

This is the theory of attitude evaluation (motivation and opportunity as determinants of the attitude-behaviour relation). When both are present, the behaviour will be deliberate. When one is absent, the impact on behaviour will be spontaneous. The MODE model was developed by Fazio. A person's attitude can be measured in two different ways.

- Explicit measure
- Implicit measure

Explicit measures are attitudes at the conscious level, that are deliberately formed and easy to self-report. Implicit measures are attitudes that are at an unconscious level, that are involuntarily formed, and are typically unknown to us. Both explicit and implicit attitudes can shape an individual's behaviour. Implicit attitudes, however, are most likely to affect behaviour when the demands are steep and an individual feels stressed or distracted.

Russell H. Fazio, (1990) [125] proposed an alternative theory called "Motivation and Opportunity as Determinants" or MODE. Fazio believes that because there is a deliberative process happening, individuals must be motivated to reflect on their attitudes and subsequent behaviours. Simply put, when an attitude is automatically activated, the individual must be motivated to avoid making an invalid judgment as well as have the opportunity to reflect on their attitude and behaviour.

Attitude-Behaviour Relationship

The effects of attitudes on behaviour is a growing research enterprise within psychology. Icek Ajzen has led research and helped develop two prominent theoretical

approaches within this field: the theory of reasoned action and, its theoretical descendant, the theory of planned behaviour. Both theories help explain the link between attitude and behaviour as a controlled and deliberative process.

Theory of Reasoned Action

The theory of reasoned action (TRA) is a model for the prediction of behavioural intention, spanning predictions of attitude and predictions of behaviour. The subsequent separation of behavioural intention from behaviour allows for the explanation of limiting factors on attitudinal influence [126]. The theory of reasoned action was developed by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen (1975, 1980) [124][126], and derived from previous research that started as the theory of attitude, which led to the study of attitude and behaviour. The theory was "born largely out of frustration with traditional attitude-behaviour research, much of which found weak correlations between attitude measures and performance of volitional behaviours" (Hale, Householder & Greene, 2003, p. 259) [127].

Theory of Planned Behaviour

The theory of planned behaviour was proposed by Icek Ajzen in 1985 [128] in his article "From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behaviour." The theory was developed from the theory of reasoned action, which was proposed by Martin Fishbein together with Icek Ajzen in 1975 [124]. The theory of reasoned action was in turn grounded in various theories of attitude such as learning theories, expectancy-value theories, consistency theories, and attribution theories. According to the theory of reasoned action, if people evaluate the suggested behaviour as positive (attitude), and if they think their significant others want them to perform the behaviour (subjective norm), this results in a higher intention (motivation) and they are more likely to do so. A high correlation of attitudes and subjective norms to behavioural intention, and subsequently to behaviour, has been confirmed in many studies. The theory of planned behaviour contains the same component as the theory of reasoned action but adds the component of perceived behavioural control to account for barriers outside one's control.

A counter-argument against the high relationship between behavioural intention and actual behaviour has also been proposed, as the results of some studies show that,

because of circumstantial limitations, behavioural intention does not always lead to actual behaviour. Namely, since behavioural intention cannot be the exclusive determinant of behaviour where an individual's control over the behaviour is incomplete, Ajzen introduced the theory of planned behaviour by adding a new component, "perceived behavioural control." By this, he extended the theory of reasoned action to cover non-volitional behaviours for predicting behavioural intention and actual behaviour. In 1928 Louis Leon Thurstone [129] published an article titled "Attitudes Can Be Measured" in it, he proposed an elaborate procedure to assess people's views on social issues. Attitudes can be difficult to measure because the measurement is arbitrary. After all, attitudes are ultimately hypothetical constructs that cannot be observed directly. But many measurements and evidence-proofed scales are used to examine attitudes. A Likert scale taps agreement or disagreement with a series of belief statements Following the explicit-implicit dichotomy, attitudes can be examined through direct and indirect measures.

Prescriptive Cognitive Models were first developed in the 1960s when marketing researchers increasingly focused on beliefs and attitudes as determinants of consumer buying behaviour [130]. The most influential work in this area was forwarded by Martin Fishbein who proposed a model of attitude formation that became known as the 'Fishbein model'; the first of a breed of 'expectancy value' models [131-134]. The Fishbein model proposed that a person's overall attitude toward an object is derived from his beliefs and feelings about various attributes of the object [130] [135].

Figure 2.5: Fishbein Model

Source: Fishbein and Ajzen 1975[124], Loudon and Della Bitta 1993[135]

Behaviour is said to be approximately equal to behavioural intention, which can be derived from a combination of the consumer's attitude toward purchasing the product and the subjective norms about the behaviour. Through the concept of 'subjective norm,' the theory acknowledges the power of other people in influencing behaviour [136]; explicitly, it accounts for the thoughts of others toward certain behaviour, and is moderated by the extent to which the consumer is motivated to comply to these views. The relative contributions of attitudes and subjective norms will not necessarily be equal in predicting behaviour [137], depending on the individual consumer's propensity to care about other's views, the consumption situation, or the product type under consideration, with conspicuously consumed products tending to be influenced to a greater degree by the subjective norm variable than less conspicuous products, would be [138].

The TRA and TPB have been widely applied in Western cultures, however, it is not clear that the assumptions underpinning them are well suited to other cultures [136]. Very few cross-cultural studies have been undertaken; however, the limited findings suggest that the theories are not equally effective in different cultures [139].

For every decision, a consumer makes there is the logical (cognitive) angle, the emotional (behavioural) angle and the humanistic angle, these new approaches can be described as humanistic as they seek to explore concepts introspective to the individual consumer rather than describe generic processes [140]. Due to its recency and explicit the model of goal-directed behaviour is seen to emerge from one strong standpoint of attitude, variables of past behaviour (both frequency and recency), and emotions (both positive and negative), and in the structure of behavioural causality passing through desire and onto intention which itself is now seen as only one of a possible four variables that are influencing a purchase [141].

Figure 2.6: Bagozzi Model

Source: Bagozzi, Gurhan-Canli et al., 2002 [142]

Several different approaches to modelling consumer decision-making can be adopted. The area is subject to ongoing dynamic research and it is expected that new insights and approaches still lie unexplored providing a potentially rich area for study. The review of the decision-making models undertaken here highlights the complexity of consumer choices and identifies the key processes that lead to behaviour. A wide range of variables have been posited across the models, and each has evidence to justify its inclusion in attempts to explain behaviour. Any one single model cannot claim to include all the considerations and factors that influence consumer choice, or it cannot apply to all classes of segments, however, the conceptual model proposed and adopted by this research has reflected upon the work falling into each of the philosophical approaches in the study of attitudes in consumer behaviour, the BoP consumer-his capabilities, his socio-economic circumstances, and his attitudes as well as the concept of brand and its meaning, importance and lure to this segment of consumers in an attempt to provide a holistic view of their decision-making process.

2.2.5 CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE STUDY

Insights from a deeper evaluation of existing literature on the BoPC, BoPR, BoPB, and EP concerning the key research problem under the study lead to the following theoretical and conceptual model illustrated in Figure 2.7 and 2.8. This conceptual model is tested through a qualitative and quantitative survey to design an integrated strategical model for Brands that would act as a useful tool for them to penetrate the BoP in an economically viable manner.

2.2.5.1 BoPC attitudes leading to purchase behaviour

Figure 2.7: A Conceptual Model of BoPC Attitude Toward Brands Influencing Purchase Behaviour

The conceptual framework depicted in Figure no 2.7 illustrates the different factors and their variables that affect the BoPC Attitude toward the Purchase of Branded essential products. The literature study, detailed observations, learnings, and experiences have elicited different variables of the study that is impacting the BoPC purchase behaviour towards branded essential products are mediated by the promotional strategies of the marketer.

2.2.5.2 Mediating the role of Promotional Strategies in the relationship between Consumer Attitude and Purchase Behaviours

Figure 2.8: A Conceptual Model of Consumer Attitude, Purchase Behaviour, and Promotional Strategies

Whether the variables considered are mediating variables or moderates must be tested under statistical conditions. Here, the conceptual framework also helps to understand the social factors such as occupation, working class, education, family size, income size of purchase behaviour, and attitude towards the brand. The objectives and hypothesis of the study were raised based on this conceptual framework.

The first chapter in addition to giving an insight into the nomenclature “Bottom of the Pyramid”, which was globally popularised by C. K. Prahalad [1], introduced the four key concepts under the study in the Indian context. The key concepts under the study are attitudes and perspectives of the BoPC concerning a few select EP offered by the BoPB through a BoPR. It is now essential to survey the available literature across all the key concepts under the study, investigate the insights, and understand research designs, sampling methodology, sampling size, theories, frameworks, models, validity, and generalizability. Post-survey, identify the gap, incorporate the recommendations of previous studies and design this research.

2.2.5.3 Conceptual Definition of Proposed Conceptual Model

It is imperative to define all the concepts under the study in addition to describing the context, circumstances, and boundaries that enable us to focus on the research problem. It is inevitable to understand the attitudes and perspectives of the BoPC unless we understand the association and determination of other concepts directly or indirectly affecting these. Figure 2.7 illustrates a schematic diagram of many of the concepts that are an integral part of the study. It is found (hypothetical) that two concepts are responsible for connecting the BoPB and the BoPC i.e., the BoPR and the EP in a multi-dimensional manner. This illustration is an attempt to simplify and narrow down the number of concepts that are required to be studied to answer the key research question.

Essentials Products (EP):

For this study, we have defined EP as the products that are required by the BoPC to survive and they are *consumed daily*. Though there are many such products, we have chosen the following Eps.

- i. Main Food Products (MFP)
 - a. Rice
 - b. Wheat
 - c. Sugar
- ii. Supplementary Food Products (SFP)
 - a. Salt
 - b. Tea/Coffee Powder
 - c. Cooking Oil
- iii. Personal Care Products (PCP)
 - a. Tooth Paste
 - b. Soap/Shampoo
 - c. Talcum Powder/Face Cream

Bottom of Pyramid Retailers (BoPR):

The retailers who are often found at the tail-end of a lengthy product supply chain in India are the fourth and last concept of this study. Furthermore, the BoPR is selected based on the following criteria.

- i. Products are not directly supplied by the BoPB
- ii. Family-run single stores
- iii. Located in the vicinity of BoPC residential areas
- iv. Not authorized to sell products subsidized by the Government

Demographic Factors and Selected Constructs: Demographic factors of BoP customers and purchase of Branded Essential Products. Age is a frequently used segmentation variable for the market [143][144]. Age is constantly used with other demographic factors like gender, income, and race while researching consumer behaviour Kim and Kim, (2004) [145] Cole and Balsubramanian (1993) [146] found that younger consumers would not like to spend more money on purchasing national brands because their brand loyalty is weaker than older consumers and suggested that the age of customers has a significant influence on purchase behaviour.

Occupation and income level of BoP Customer moderation between attitudinal dimensions and their purchase behaviour. Daneshvary and Schower (2000) [147] found that purchase intention has a relationship with demographic factors like age, gender, occupation and education. Occupation and income moderation between promotional strategies and BoP Customers' purchase behaviour. Dibsall *et al.*, 2003 [71] found that age, employment, gender, smoking, and marital status all affected attitudes towards access, affordability, and motivation to eat fruit and vegetables.

CHAPTER-III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The key objectives of the study made it easy for designing the research methodology that would help find the answers to research questions scientifically. According to Bryman (2008) [148], epistemological issues address the matter of what is, could, and be adequate knowledge for a subject. Usually, epistemological problems concentrate on what knowledge is, and what can be accepted as knowledge for the study. Bryman (2008) [148], and other researchers (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2009, p. 54) [149] stated that there are three possible distinctions: positivism, realism, and interpretivism. Ontology shows the authors in what way the study aligns the nature of social entities, and answers questions such as “what is it?” and so on. The choice of ontology is a choice of how social entities should be regarded in terms of relation to social constructions; either as objective entities that possess an outer reality or as constructions based on the subjective actions, and perceptions of these entities [150].

One can conclude that this study will be based on objective ontology. Since it is argued that social phenomena and their related meanings exist independently of social factors and that social phenomena and related categories are not dependent on other factors [150], the best way to approach the subject of attitudes and behavioural dimensions of the BoPC toward the BoPB is to regard social entities in the economic sphere as they are – as objective entities with objective actions, and relations to one another. According to Kaplan, the understanding of the causal relationships among the variables of research helps to make inferences about the behaviour of objects, and their effect on the subject of research. Solving a problem in real life without any theory can give extreme unexpected results which may seem not applicable. Theories are widely used by researchers in the research process depending on the research type, objective, and scope. The role of the research is to test theories and provide material, and findings for the development of laws [151].

According to other scientists, there are two main ways of scientific approaches to theories of the research studies that can be found: the first is deductive, and the second is inductive [149][151][152]. As the deductive approach enables one to test the theory instead of trying to create the theory [150] this study will mainly be conducted with a deductive approach, trying to verify, and falsify several scientific models the authors have investigated based upon different theories, which will be further presented in the next chapter.

The deductive approach is also named “testing theory”, and it starts with an analysis of already existing theories that are relevant to the research [151][152]. Thus, the researcher can create some hypotheses about the investigated topic. After this, empirical data is collected and analyzed to test if discovered hypotheses are true or false. If the hypotheses are false, the researcher should propose a revision of the existing theory [148]. An inductive approach is also called ‘building theory, and it is conducted oppositely. It starts with some specific observations, and moves to broader generalizations, and the formulation of theories (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2009) [149].

Moreover, it can be argued that it is important to distinguish between a qualitative, and a quantitative approach when writing a thesis, and performing research. Quantitative research is commonly associated with surveys or experiments and is considered the mainstay of the research industry for collecting marketing data. Quantitative research places heavy emphasis on using formalized questions, and predetermined response options in questionnaires administered to a large number of respondents [153].

A quantitative study was found to be the most suitable option for this specific research problem since we wanted to see the problem from a wider standpoint, where a more general perspective of the problem can be emphasized. It was hence decided to distribute a questionnaire to different respondents to conduct the study. The choice of doing that is mainly based on the decision to perform a quantitative study where a broader, and more generalized approach is meant to be achieved.

In questionnaire research practices, researchers need skills in construct development, scale measurement, questionnaire design, sampling, and statistical data analysis. Besides, researchers must have a solid ability to translate numerical data into meaningful narrative information. Data reliability and validity issues are serious concerns with quantitative research [153].

Where an empirical study involves collecting information from a larger number of cases by using questionnaires, it is usually described as a survey. A survey may be cross-sectional (data collected at one time) or longitudinal (collected over a period). Because of the larger number of cases, a survey will generally involve some

quantitative analysis. The issue of generalizability is usually important in presenting survey results, so it is vital to report how samples were chosen, what response rates were achieved, and to comment on the validity, and reliability of any instruments used.

Since they used a statistical tool (SPSS) for their survey, the qualitative data they have gathered through questionnaires are converted into numbers, and cannot be interpreted in any other way than their values. Thus, the information we gather is absolute, which implies that the nature of this study is strictly positivistic [150].

Most consumer attitude and perspective measurements are taken by surveys. These can be written questionnaires, telephone, or face-to-face interviews, and focus groups. An intercept measurement is simply when a researcher stops a consumer as they enter or leave a place of business, and begins to ask questions. The customer is “intercepted”. The intercept technique can be either a written survey or oral interview or both [154].

The research technique and framework used for the study are provided by the research design. It provides information on the research methodology, the kinds of data that were gathered for the study, and the research design. Additionally, it contains various explanations of the study's variables and several tests that were performed to determine the validity and reliability of the data that was gathered for analysis. Additionally, it includes information on the statistical software and tools that were utilised to analyse the data. The key objectives of the study made it easy for designing the research methodology that would help find the answers to research questions scientifically. Thus, before describing the research design and methodology it is inevitable to list the key objectives of this research study. Even though the main objective of the study was to understand the attitude and perspectives of BoPC toward BoPB, it was necessary to understand other concepts that are directly/indirectly affecting/mediating/moderating the attitudes and perspectives of the BoPC toward BoPB. The main intention of this study was to understand and define the characteristics of the base of the pyramid concerning the area under study. Moreover to study subsistence marketplace behaviours from a consumer perspective and to study the impact of the attitude of BoP consumers towards branded essential products. In addition, this research intended to study the BoPC purchase behavioural

dimensions towards branded essential products-to explore the driving factors of BoPR to serve the BoPC market. Lastly, the research intended to develop a model for marketers to successfully engage BoPC. Overall, the model tested mediating role of promotional strategies in the relationship between attitude and purchasing behaviour of Bottom of the Pyramid Customers for which appropriate statistical tools were used which is again discussed in this study.

3.2 DATA SOURCE

To satisfy the research objectives data from primary as well as the secondary source has been collected; which are further discussed as follows:

3.2.1 Primary Data

Based on the literature review, and on the assumptions from the scientific methodological approach this research study measures the attitude and behavioural dimensions of BoPC toward the BoPB under the study by applying two independent instruments that are designed to collect data from three key concepts in the study such as BoPC and BoPR, limited to EP. Consequently, assessing the attitude and behavioural dimensions of BoPC toward the BoPB requires examining all these three dimensions. Research instruments developed for the BoPC were to mainly assess their attitude level concerning awareness, affordability, accessibility, visibility, relationship with the seller, brand factor and brand impact on essential products; furthermore, their perception towards various promotional strategies undertaken by marketers was also assessed. Moreover, the collected data also includes their purchase behaviour. In addition, the 2nd research instrument intended to measure the perception and attitude of Bottom of the Pyramid retailers towards the BoPC with respect to branded essential products. The rationale for this data collection method is based on the theory that respondents are more attentive to the task of completing a questionnaire, and provide more meaningful responses when they are completing a questionnaire, and provide more meaningful responses when they are contextualized in the environment that they are evaluating [155].

3.2.2 Secondary Data

At the same time secondary data has also been collected through various published sources. In order to review the existing knowledge on BoPC and BoPR with special reference to their attitude and purchase behaviour, articles, magazines, thesis,

newspapers etc. has been surveyed from Google scholar, SSRN, Elsevier, Shodhganga, Emerald, Taylor and Francis, moreover many journals and articles have been referred from Scopus indexed and UGC care list journals.

3.3 DESIGNING THE SURVEY'S QUESTIONNAIRE

Data were collected employing two structured questionnaires separately designed to understand the attitudinal and behavioural dimensions of BoPC towards branded essential products and BoPR towards BoPC.

3.3.1 Questionnaire Instrument

Instrument 1 (BoPC)

Part 1 of the BoPC instrument is about respondent profile which includes the demographic data points such as age, gender, marital status, education level, occupation, income, number of earning members in the family, the primary mode of transportation, the primary mode of communication, and most importantly the type of ration card held by them.

Part 2 of the BoPC instrument is all about gathering specific information about the frequency and place of purchasing the EPs that are sub-categorized as i) Essential Main Food Products (MFP) such as Rice, Wheat, and Sugar; ii) Essential Supplementary Food Products (SFP) such as Tea/Coffee Powder, Cooking Oil, and Salt; iii) Essential Personal Care Products (PCP) such as Tooth Paste, Shampoo, Soap, and Face Cream/Powder. This section also contains the 6 scale type of questions with respect to purchase behaviour.

Part 3 and Part 4 of the BoPC instrument is all about gathering specific information about the BoPC perception towards promotional strategies of the marketers and attitude of BoPC toward the BoPB respectively. All statements employed a five-point Likert scale ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”. Consumers should give their agreement levels for a specific question. Strongly Disagree would mean a Negative Attitude, Strongly Agree means a Positive attitude. The key reason why we have chosen to employ the five-point Likert scale is that this scale will provide a better normal spread of observations for conducting the research.

Details of the questions under the Instrument 1 which were asked to the respondents are given in Annexure 1.

Instrument 2 (BoPR)

Part. 1 of the BoPR instrument is about respondent retailers' profiles which includes the demographic data points such as age, gender, marital status, education level, number of employees working in the store, age of the store, level of digital-enabled payments, level of credit facility provided to consumers and most importantly whether the store is a Government authorized subsidized products seller or not. And also this part is all about gathering specific information about the frequency and place of purchasing the EP for their stores. The answers collecting for these questions would help the study in understanding the overall supply chain at the BoP.

Part 2 and part 3 of the BoPR instrument is all about gathering specific information about the Part-2 Retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products and Retailers' Perception on Brand Awareness. All statements employed a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree". Consumers should give their agreement levels for a specific question. Strongly Disagree would mean a Negative Attitude, Strongly Agree means a Positive attitude. The key reason why we have chosen to employ the five-point Likert scale is that this scale will provide a better normal spread of observations for conducting the research.

3.3.2 Construction of Research Instrument

As discussed above Questionnaire Instrument 1 consists of demographic profile and details with regard to purchase behaviour, promotional strategies and attitude of the Bottom of the Pyramid Customers which was constructed through various standardised measurement and related articles. The measurement scale and specific questions concerning purchasing behaviour were obtained from the standardized measurement of Dibsdall *et al.*, (2003) [71], Subrahmanyam & Gomez-arias, (2003) [85], Sharma, B. R., & Gupta, N. (2021) [85], Teng & Laroche, (2011) [106], Kumar, N. A., & Joseph, J. (2014) [107], Adams, (2015) [72], Watson *et al.*, (2009) [156], Barki & Parente, (2010) [86], Chou *et al.*, (2020) [108], Ahmmadi *et al.*, (2021) [157], Wilcock *et al.*, (2004) [89], Jaiswal & Gupta, (2015) [102], Petrescu *et al.*, (2013) [103], Lappeman & Kabi, (2017) [104]. For constructing questions related to promotional strategies standardized measurements were obtained from the following research- Fletcher, (1999) [158], Gupta *et al.*, (2014) [83], Teng & Laroche, (2011) [106], Mishra & Jaikumar, (2021) [78], Chou *et al.*, (2020) [108], Jaiswal & Gupta,

(2015) [102], Petrescu *et al.*, (2013) [103], Lappeman & Kabi, (2017) [104], Roy *et al.*, (2021) [105]. Moreover Attitude having 7 constructs such as awareness, affordability, accessibility, visibility, relationship with sellers, brand factors and brand impact on essential products were constructed from the standardised measurement given by Dibsdall *et al.*, (2003) [71], Kimenju *et al.*, (2005) [159], Rajagopal, (2009) [66], Teng & Laroche, (2011) [106], Batra, R., & Ahtola, O. T. (1991) [76], Adams, (2015) [72], Watson *et al.*, (2009) [156], Chikweche & Fletcher, (2013) [77], Wills *et al.*, (2012) [160], Chou *et al.*, (2020)[108], Srivastava *et al.*, (2020) [75], Wilcock *et al.*, (2004) [89], Karam, (2015), Notani, (1997) [90], Lee *et al.*, (2003) [74], Panda *et al.*, (2021) [92]. The 2nd instruments' constructs such as Retailers perception and brand awareness was obtained from Beninger & Robson, (2015) [21], Rahman *et al.*, (2013) [161], Roy *et al.*, (2021) [101] and Panda *et al.*, (2021) [92]. Some of the specific measurements were obtained pertaining to the exact constructs which is explained in a tabular form.

Table 3.1: Measurement Variables in Study

Measurement Variables	Corresponding Literature
Awareness	Strong, E. (1925) [162], Lavidge, R. J., & Steiner, G. A. (1961) [163], Howard, J. A., & Sheth, J. N. (1969) [164]
Affordability	Notani, A. S. (1997) [165], Singh, A., & Kathuria, L. M. (2016) [166]
Accessibility	Carvalho, B. L. D., Salgueiro, M. D. F., & Rita, P. (2016) [167]
Visibility	Sheth, J.N., (1985) [168]
Seller Relationship	Smith, J. B., (1998) [169], Claycomb, C., & Frankwick, G. L., (2010) [170].
Brand Factors	Stavkova, J., Stejskal, L., & Toufarova, Z., (2008) [171], Kathuria, L. M., & Gill, P., (2013) [67], Musharraf, M. B., & Ali, T., (2013) [172]
Promotional Strategies	Grewal, D., & Levy, M., (2007) [173], Ailawadi, K. L., Beauchamp, J. P., Donthu, N., Gauri, D. K., & Shankar, V., (2009) [174]

Details of the questions under the Instrument 2 which were asked to the respondents are given in Annexure 2.

3.4 PILOT STUDY

To get the best results possible from performing the questionnaire, a pilot study was made and carried out before the actual study was conducted. It can be argued that a pilot study is a useful tool in determining how adequate the questions and the instructions are. The instruments are developed through focus group interaction

insights and its content validity is tested with the help of subject experts. The opinions from the industry experts were solicited and this helped in developing instrument 2. Further a pre-test with a sample of 50 respondents for Instrument 1, 10 respondents for Instrument 2 was conducted. The insight of the pilot study was considered, necessary changes were incorporated and again a pre-test was done. Thus, the validity of the questionnaire was thoroughly checked before actually administering it to the respondents.

3.4.1 Development and Validation of Data Collection Instrument

A reliable and valid research instrument is vitally necessary for any study, and the present research activity utilised several different techniques in the questionnaire preparation process. In the current study, two types of data development and data validation were used. Validity and reliability testing comes first. Testing an instrument's validity entails determining whether it is capable of measuring what it is designed to. Content validity is tested as part of validity.

Content Validity

A research instrument must include a broad range of components and structures. These can be produced initially from the already accessible review of the literature. The statements contained in the study instrument needed to be clear and command the necessary content validity after the necessary variables had been generated. A thorough validation procedure was used for this. Twenty BoP customers were first given one set of instrument 1 and their feedback was gathered. Similarly, the instrument 2 was given to ten retailers and their feedback was elicited. Then five academicians with expertise in marketing, business management and psychology were asked to review the instrument and offer any recommendations to instrument 1. Instrument 2 was given to five FMCG company middle management officials and they were asked to review and offer their recommendations. The factors in the questionnaire were added, eliminated, and appropriately changed after full consideration of these recommendations. As a result, the topic experts' comments and recommendations were used to confirm the validity of the questionnaire's content, and some adjustments were made to the questionnaire to make it clearer, easier to comprehend, and more useful.

Reliability Test

A pilot survey was conducted among 50 Bottom of the Pyramid Customers from 7 taluks in the Dakshina Kannada district to identify any flaws that might have gone unnoticed and to finalise the interview schedule and measurement scale. Ten respondents from rural regions were chosen from each taluk. The reliability and validity of the scale were evaluated using the proper techniques following the completion of the pilot survey. The interview schedule and the measuring scales were modified as necessary. This procedure aided the researcher in making the necessary questionnaire adjustments. Following careful review and recommendations from knowledgeable people, the improvements were made. After the pilot study, the researcher used Cronbach's alpha test to confirm the accuracy of the data [176]. The most typical metric used to evaluate the data's internal consistency is Cronbach's alpha. Typically, an alpha value of 0.7 to 0.8 is regarded as an acceptable range. In order to finalize the questionnaire and its various measurement scales, reliability of the data must be examined for which pilot study was conducted among 50 customers in the region.

Table 3.2: Reliability and Validity Test Results of Instrument-1

Construct	No. of Items	Reliability		Validity			
		Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha	AVE	MSV	Convergent	Discriminant
Awareness	4	0.712	0.720	0.701	0.700	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Affordability	4	0.784	0.789	0.876	0.798	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Accessibility	4	0.748	0.734	0.698	0.628	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Visibility	6	0.769	0.763	0.742	0.718	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Relationship with Seller	6	0.825	0.842	0.804	0.792	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Brand Factors	6	0.790	0.747	0.832	0.749	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Purchase Behaviour	6	0.814	0.809	0.734	0.719	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Promotional Strategies	10	0.784	0.728	0.716	0.701	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Brand Impact on Essential Products	8	0.764	0.761	0.789	0.746	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE

Table 3.3: Reliability Test Results of Instrument-2

Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha
Attitude	5	0.748
Brand Awareness	10	0.761

As reliability test is conducted to check the internal consistency of the data the above test has been adopted where the study is considered to be reliable if the alpha value is

greater than 0.70. As all the construct tends to be reliable, all the items shall be retained in the questionnaire. table demonstrates that all the metric constructs have achieved discriminant validity as $AVE > MSV$ in all the cases. Furthermore, at last SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) [177] was run to test the proposed conceptual model along with ANOVA assessing demographic influence on the constructs using SPSS 26.0 and AMOS 23.0 software.

Correlation Analysis

The primary goal of this study is to examine the interplay between perception and the factors of Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, and Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour and promotional strategies. Three instances are presented in [178] to examine the existence of an interaction or moderating influence. Therefore, correlation and regression analysis should be used to determine whether there are any correlations between the variables [179]. To determine the connections and influences of moderator and independent variables on dependent variables, Pearson's correlation analysis was used. The following outcomes are shown in the tables.

Table 3.4: Correlation Results between Various Parameters

		Awareness	Accessibility	Affordability	Visibility	Relationship	Brand Factor	Purchase Behaviour
Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.292**	.331**	.534**	.533**	.380**	.330**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	218	218	218	218	218	218	218
Accessibility	Pearson Correlation	.292**	1	.402**	.169*	.390**	.287**	.140*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.012	.000	.000	.039
	N	218	218	218	218	218	218	218
Affordability	Pearson Correlation	.331**	.402**	1	.302**	.191**	.199**	.145*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.005	.003	.033
	N	218	218	218	218	218	218	218
Visibility	Pearson Correlation	.534**	.169*	.302**	1	.569**	.455**	.351**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.012	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	218	218	218	218	218	218	218
Relationship	Pearson Correlation	.533**	.390**	.191**	.569**	1	.472**	.516**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.005	.000		.000	.000
	N	218	218	218	218	218	218	218
Brand Factor	Pearson Correlation	.380**	.287**	.199**	.455**	.472**	1	.302**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.003	.000	.000		.000
	N	218	218	218	218	218	218	218
Purchase Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.330**	.140*	.145*	.351**	.516**	.302**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.039	.033	.000	.000	.000	
	N	218	218	218	218	218	218	218

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (HS)

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (S)

As per the correlation table it is clear that all the Parameter shows the positive correlation between various indicators and p value shows less than 0.01.

3.5 VARIABLES/FACTORS USED IN THE STUDY

As discussed above various factors and constructs have been identified and constructed based on the previous studies pertaining to the conceptual model. Research instruments for BoP customers and BoP Retailers consists of various factors and this study intends to assess the relationship between these constructs. The detailed description on these variables and factors has been discussed in a tabular form.

Table 3.5: Variables/Factors Used in Research Instrument-1

Sl. No.	Variables		
1.	Sample Profile	Name	
		Location	
		Origin	
		Age	
		Gender	
		Marital status	
		Education level	
		Occupation	
		Monthly family income	
		Priority House hold Ration Card (PHRC)	
		Number of members in the family	
		Number of earning members in the family	
		Primary mode of transportation	
		Primary mode of communication	
2.	Attitude	No. of Factors	No. of Items
		Awareness	4
		Affordability	4
		Accessibility	4
		Visibility	6
		Relationship with Seller	6
		Brand Factors	6
		Brand Impact on Essential Products	9
3.	Purchase Behaviour	6	
4.	Promotional Strategies	10	

Table 3.6: Variables/Factors Used in Research Instrument-2

Sl. No.	Variables	
1.	Sample Profile	Name
		Location
		Origin
		Age
		Gender
		Marital status
		Education level
		Operating duration
		Average Number of Walk-ins per Day
		Government Authorized Ration store

		Number of Employee
		Number of Stores in Operation
		Mobile banking transaction
		Percentage of Customers currently availing Credit facility
		Percentage of known customers shopping at store
		Place of purchase
		Credit Facility from the Suppliers
		Frequency of stock purchases
	Factor	No. of items
2.	Attitude towards selling the branded essential products	5
3.	Perception on Brand Awareness	10

3.6 POPULATION AND SAMPLE SIZE

The main purpose of this study is to understand the attitudes and perspectives of the BoPC toward branded products and hence, the study considered the the PHRC holders as the BoPC of our study. Some of the key qualifiers to be called BoPC of our study are listed below.

- i. They are the Indian equivalent of the global definition of people living on less than USD 2 per day (PPP).
- ii. The Government of India has implemented a scientific, objective, and fool-proof mechanism for identifying, classifying, and follow-up of issuing ration cards to PHH.

To ensure the study gets convincing and generalizable answers to the key research questions within the stipulated time, a calculated decision was made to choose the PHRC holders of Mangalore city located in the Dakshin Kannada district representing the Karnataka state of India as the population of our study. Based on the sources provided by the Deputy Director of Food and Civil Supply, the study has noted that the total number of PHRC holders in Mangalore city was 36,191 as illustrated in Table 3.7.

Using the below formula that considers finite population correction (Daniel WW (1999). Biostatistics: A Foundation for Analysis in the Health Sciences, 7th edition. New York: John Wiley & Sons) [180], the researcher has arrived at the sample size for Instrument 1 (BoPC).

$$n = N * X / (X + N - 1),$$

where,

$$X = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * P * (1 - P) / MOE^2$$

n = is the sample size required for Instrument 1.

N = is the whole target population in question (PHRC Holders in Mangalore City).

p = is the average proportion of records expected to meet the various criteria.

$1-p$ = is the average proportion of records not expected to meet the criteria.

MOE = is the margin of error deemed to be acceptable.

Z = is a mathematical constant defined by the Confidence Interval chosen i.e. (how sure we need to be of the result). Z-Value in the Z table.

Thus, the sample size for Instrument 1 is 195 at 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and 85% of respondents expected to meet the criteria defined for eligibility of PHRC.

Table 3.7: PHRC and NPHRC Holders in Dakshina Kannada District

ಆದತಾ, ಆದ್ಯತೆತರ ಮತ್ತು ಒಟ್ಟು ಪಡಿತರ ಚೀಟಿದಾರರು ದಿ. 31.03.2020ರ ಅಂತ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ (ಸಂಚಿತ) Non-Priority and Total Ration Card Holders as on 31-3-2020 (Cumulative)										
ಕ್ರ. ಸಂ. S. No.	ತಾಲೂಕುಗಳು Talukus	ಆದ್ಯತಾ Priority			ಆದ್ಯತೆತರ Non Priority			ಒಟ್ಟು ಪ. ಚೀಟಿದಾರರು Total R. Card holders		
		ನಗರ Urban	ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ Rural	ಒಟ್ಟು Total	ನಗರ Urban	ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ Rural	ಒಟ್ಟು Total	ನಗರ Urban	ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ Rural	ಒಟ್ಟು Total
1	2	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38
1	ಬಂಟ್ವಾಳ / Bantwal	6570	49519	56089	3612	16966	20578	10833	71784	82617
2	ಬೆಳ್ತಂಗಡಿ / Belthangady	900	43917	44817	634	13008	13642	1603	60212	61815
3	ಕಡಬ / Kadaba	0	19131	19131	0	9910	9910	0	30820	30820
4	ಮಂಗಳೂರು / Mangalore	36191	39480	75671	54498	28664	83162	92304	73445	165749
5	ಮೂಡಬಿದ್ರೆ / Mudabidri	3420	10488	13908	2028	3507	5535	5757	15069	20826
6	ಪುತ್ತೂರು / Puttur	5225	16887	22112	6908	10542	17450	12551	30007	42558
7	ಸುಳ್ಯ / Sullia	2119	16917	19036	1445	8923	10368	3748	26429	30177
ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಮೊತ್ತ / Dist. Total		54425	196339	250764	69125	91520	160645	126796	307766	434562

Source: Deputy Director of Food and Civil Supply, Dakshina Kannada District, Karnataka, India

Table 3.8: Description of the Sample Units Surveyed

Sl. No.	Geographical Divisions	Areas Covered	No. of Samples
1	South	Bendoor	16
2	West	Bejai	15
3	East	Bajal	15
4	West	Bengre	15
5	East	Dongerkerly	16
6	East	Alape	16
7	East	Kushekara	16
8	South	Kadri	15
9	North	Kavoor	16
10	East	Konchady	15
11	North	Kulai	16
12	South	Car Street	16
13	West	Panambur	16
14	West	Urva	15

Source: The table is constructed by the author for this study

The sample for questionnaires was based on stratified random sampling. The city jurisdiction wards were considered for selecting the area subset, each ward representing the four geographical ranges – North, South, East, and West was picked using a random basis of selection. Each member of the population has an equal chance of being chosen in simple random sampling. The selection of each unit is not affected by the selection of other units. BoPC had an equal chance to be chosen as our respondents during the survey process.

The retailers who are often found at the tail-end of a lengthy product supply chain in India are considered the BoPR of this study. Furthermore, the BoPR is selected based on the following criteria.

- i. Products are not directly supplied by the BoPB
- ii. Family-run single stores
- iii. Located in the vicinity of BoPC residential areas
- iv. Not authorized to sell products subsidized by the Government

The BoP retailers were the preferred stores of the respondents of Instrument 1 were selected for collecting responses to questions of Instrument 2 (BoPR). Hence, purposive sampling technique was used.

To enable focalized research, we have considered all the brands (local, domestic, national, and international) which are offering essential products defined in this study.

The selection of each unit is not affected by the selection of other units. BoPC had an equal chance to be chosen as our respondents during the survey process. The limitation of this random sample was that the survey was finished in a short period [181].

The structure and purpose of the study are on Indian consumers hence all the respondents are Indians and though the questionnaire was designed in English the respondents have explained each question in a personal interview method only employed to elicit responses on Instrument 1 and Instrument 2.

3.7 SAMPLE INCLUSION

The inclusion of sample is based on the areas i.e., the BoPC customers included in Mangalore Corporation only restricting to 60 wards. Data collection about retailers is also restricted to Mangalore. BoP Customers include food and civil supplies PHH Card holders and retailers from the Mangalore region have been targeted. The sampling technique used to collect the data for both the instrument is done through stratified sampling

Table 3.9: Sample Inclusion

	Body of Study	
Area Covered	Mangalore Corporation Limits - 60 wards	Mangalore Corporation Limits
Included	Food and Civil Supplies PHH Card Holders	Retailers in the areas covered
Approach	Stratified Random Sampling	Purposive Sampling

3.8 STATISTICAL ASSUMPTION

The gathered data must be assessed to check if it complies with specified statistical assumptions to ensure that it is appropriate for use in various statistical research. The data were validated in the current inquiry using the hypotheses of normality, homogeneity, linearity, and multicollinearity. Each of these suppositions is required for structural equation modeling (SEM). Linear and multicollinearity tests are required to validate the assumption of regression analysis. It is necessary to confirm that the data have a normal distribution before performing a parametric or non-parametric test. Structural Equation Modeling was conducted using multiple regression analysis (SEM).

3.8.1 Normality

The normality test is an essential step in the application of several statistical tests. The application of the validity tests is influenced by the normality of the data. If it is determined that the data are normal, SEM and other statistical tests may be used. If it is found that the data is not normal, the test results become unreliable; in this case, a non-parametric test can be used. Below is a list of the tests that were used in the current inquiry.

3.8.1.1 Histogram Test for Normality

The histogram test can also be used to determine normalcy. Whether or whether the distribution is bell-shaped can be determined by plotting the observed values against their frequency distribution. The bell-shaped plots indicate that the data has complied with the normality assumption.

Figure 3.1 and 3.2 makes it obvious that the chosen variables display a standard histogram curve. Thus, the data is consistent with the notion of normalcy.

3.8.2 Homogeneity

In the current investigation, Levene statistics were used to analyse the homogeneity of the data. The null hypothesis is that variance will always be equal. This requires two sets of data, one with dependent variables and the other with factor variables. The demographic data were used as factor variables, and the construct variables were used as dependent variables. The levene statistic value should be over 0.5 and the significant value must be greater than 0.05 when it can be argued that the variances are equal within the population distribution. In the current study, the demographic variables of the respondents' gender, marital status, and a maximum number of consecutive days worked were included.

3.8.3 Linearity

The linearity test is essential to determine whether the regression analysis's underlying assumptions are met. Regression analysis is used to describe the linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The linear relationship between two variables can be understood using a scatter plot (Attitudinal dimensions such as

Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Brand Factors, Relationship with Seller and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase Behaviour, and Promotional Strategies). Purchase behaviour was selected as the dependent variable in this case, with "attitudinal dimensions and promotional strategies" as the independent variables.

Figure 3.3: Test of Linearity between Attitudinal Dimension Factors and Purchase Behaviour

Figure 3.4: Test of Linearity between the Promotional Strategies and Purchase Behaviour

Test of the relationship between Attitudinal Dimension Factors and Promotional Strategies on Purchase behaviour

Figure 3.5: Test of Linearity between Attitudinal Dimension Factors and Purchase Behaviour

Figure 3.6: Test of Linearity between the Promotional Strategies and Purchase Behaviour

Figure 3.5 and 3.6 demonstrates that the drawn line is linear. The linearity assumption was satisfied and a linear relationship between the two variables was formed.

3.8.4 Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity is a serious issue in the normal distribution of data when the researcher uses multiple independent variables to predict a dependent variable in the study. Any relationship between the independent variables can reveal the multicollinearity problem. A component of the statistics of collinearity is tolerance and the variation inflation factor (VIF). If the tolerance level is less than 0.2 and the VIF value exceeds 5, multicollinearity is present. Between Attitudinal Dimension Factors and Purchase Behaviour, the multicollinearity test was utilised. Here, purchasing behaviour is the dependent variable and the attitude-related dimension factors are the independent variables.

Table 3.10: Results of Multicollinearity Test

Indicators	Tolerance	VIF
Attitudinal Dimension Factors		
Awareness	.586	4.768
Affordability	.412	3.767
Accessibility	.366	3.422
Visibility	.533	4.444
Relationship with Seller	.324	3.886
Brand Factors	.422	3.891

The results of the multiple regression analysis attest to the lack of any multicollinearity issues in the data set because the VIF value is less than five and the tolerance level value is greater than 0.2.

3.9 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS

Responses were coded and entered into the software based on the objectives. The data evaluation tool of choice is SPSS 26.0. The study used percentages, cumulative percentages, standard deviations, ranges, and means as descriptive statistics. The data that were gathered were examined using a variety of statistical methods, including:

1. Reliability and Validity Test
2. Percentage Analysis
3. Descriptive Analysis
4. Fisher's Exact test or Chi-square test
5. Friedman test
6. Independent sample t-test
7. One-way ANOVA
8. Correlation Analysis
9. Simple Regression Analysis
10. Multiple Regression Analysis
11. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and
12. SEM for Path Analysis

Explanation of the various analyses used

The primary information obtained from the questionnaire was tabulated and assessed using statistical tools. The data acquired from primary sources were evaluated and interpreted using several statistical techniques utilised in social science research, including univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analysis.

1. The Reliability Test using Cronbach Alpha: The link between the variables were measured using appropriate bivariate and multivariate analyses, which were then used to evaluate the theoretical model and analyse the measurement model using the SEM model.

2. Analysis by Percentages: Analysis by percentages was utilised to comprehend the demographic traits and nature of the BoPC and BoPR. The frequency and proportion of each study component, such as Attitude indicators – Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour and promotional strategies about customers and also brand awareness along with retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products concerning retailers were also evaluated at the same time.

3. Descriptive Analysis: In a descriptive analysis, the terms "mean," "minimum," "maximum," and "standard deviation" have been used to describe the degree of agreement among BoPC and BoPR regarding the perception of Attitudinal dimensions-Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour and promotional strategies with regard to customers and also brand awareness along with retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products concerning retailers. Through the use of SPSS software, the average value, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum of each component have all been calculated in this analysis.

4. Fisher's Exact Test or Chi-square Test: To determine the relationship or association between two variables, such as demographic characteristics and Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour and promotional strategies, the chi-square test and Fisher's exact test are used.

5. Friedman Test: To compare mean rank between the variables, the Friedman test computes the mean ranks across cases. It was used to determine the average ranking between perception level on Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, and Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour, and promotional strategies.

6. Correlation: The statistical metric known as correlation describes the strength and nature of a relationship between two or more variables. This method is useful in establishing a possible relationship between the variables. If a correlation is found, it may be found to be either positive or negative. This analysis is used for analyzing the direction of the relationship between Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with the Seller, Brand Factors, and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour, and promotional strategies.

7. Independent sample t-test: Independent samples t-test has been used to compare the means of only two groups, no more, no less. Usually, two population means are compared using this test to see if they differ. This procedure is an inferential statistical hypothesis test since it uses samples to infer information about populations. The independent samples t-test is also known as the two-sample t-test. In this study, an independent sample t-test was used to analyse the mean differences between origins and genders concerning Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors, and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour, and promotional strategies.

8. One-way ANOVA: One-way ANOVA ("analysis of variance") evaluates the means of two or more independent groups to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the linked population means are statistically significantly different. One of the parametric tests is the one-way ANOVA. The study used one-way ANOVA to evaluate research hypotheses 1, 2, and 3 by comparing the significant differences between the different demographic characteristics, which include more than two groups, about Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors and Brand Impact on Essential Products, Purchase behaviour and promotional strategies.

9. Simple Regression Analysis: In essence, a simple regression analysis is a statistical method used to measure the association between one independent variable and one dependent variable based on historical observations. In the simple linear regression model, the study examines the impact between the single independent variable and the dependent variable. The term "simple linear regression model" is frequently used to describe a linear regression model with only one independent variable. The simple regression analysis has been utilised in the current study to examine the effects of attitudinal dimensions on purchase behaviour as well as the impact of promotional strategies on purchase behaviour.

10. Multiple Regression Analysis: To determine how linearly related various independent variables and various dependent variables are to one another, a technique known as multiple regression is performed. The relationship is seen as linear because of the correlation between the variables. To determine the effect of various attitudinal dimensions on purchase behaviour, multivariate regression analysis was used in the current study.

11. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and Path Analysis: SEM, a multivariate statistical analysis method, is used to look at the structural relationships between quantifiable variables and latent components. Path analysis is used to quantify the causal relationships between the constructs. To ascertain how the attitudinal dimensions of BoP Customers affected purchase behaviour and, the significant influence of promotional strategies on relationship between attitude and purchase behaviour, SEM was used in the current investigation.

According to the explanation above, the research techniques used for this project are reliable and valid. To guarantee the authenticity and quality of the data, a thorough statistical analysis was necessary for the study.

Statistical tools are one of the main components used for being able to analyze and interpret the data that is collected through surveys. Statistical tests and analyses are needed to see correlations between some of the attributes that have been investigated. A correlation and determination matrix was created in the program SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences), where also several statistical analyses between different factors were conducted. ABCD factor analysis was also performed to identify the benefits constraints advantages and disadvantages to key stakeholders viz., BoP retailer (seller) and BoP consumer.

3.10 SOFTWARE USED

This study used a variety of research database software and heavily relied on cutting-edge statistical methods that included data and facts. In particular, IBM SPSS 26.0, IBM AMOS 23.0, Microsoft Excel 2010, and Mendeley were employed in this study. MS Excel 2010 has been used to compile and source data from several prior research, including Google Scholar, Science Direct, Web of Science, JSTOR, N-List, ABDC, etc. to demonstrate the simple frequency and two-way tables as well as two or three-dimensional charts and diagrams. Simple bar diagrams, pie charts, and other diagrams can be created using Microsoft Excel. IBM SPSS 26.0 programme is used for conducting descriptive and inferential analysis, where analysis such as chi-square, t-test, ANOVA, regression analysis, descriptive statistics, normality check, simple correlation, etc. has been employed, IBM SPSS 26.0 software is utilised. Path diagrams have been created using IBM AMOS 23.0 in conjunction with confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling.

CHAPTER-IV

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

India is the largest BoP market constituted of 379 million adults in 2015 [182]. BoP market is characterized by constraints like poverty, low literacy and computational ability resulting in peculiar consumption patterns in the form of loose unbranded products, cheaper alternatives, pouches, and second hand items [183]. Serving the BoP market mandated understanding the unusual consumption patterns and revisiting the marketing mix for peculiar BoP consumers. A previous study thesis conducted across different parts of rural and urban Punjab has elicited a lot of information on the basic consumption pattern of BoP in India [184]. The findings of this earlier study in Punjab exhibited certain basic consumption patterns of edible oil, food essentials, durables and nondurable items and the type of product consumed.

This chapter demonstrates the analysis of collected data from the quantitative survey, which are in accordance with the research design and methodology described in previous chapters. As the study intended to understand and define the characteristics of base of the pyramid consumer perception on marketplace behaviour. By understanding various dimensions of BoPC purchase behaviour with respect to branded essential product this study assessed the impact of BoPC attitude towards the dimensions of purchasing behaviour. Finally, the research provides a tested model for seller/marketer/BoPR to successfully engage BoPC. In order to accomplish these objectives; researcher used various appropriate and suitable statistical analysis procedure and tools. This chapter is a detailed discussion of various statistical analyses to derive at a research outcome.

This chapter is broadly divided into two parts-analyses on Bottom of Pyramid Customers and Bottom of the Pyramid Retailers. These two parts are further divided into three sections. The percentage analysis is presented in the first section. The second component is a descriptive analysis using a simple mean and standard deviation. In the third portion, statistical procedures such as the Friedman's test, Fisher's exact test or chi-square test, independent sample t-test, one-way ANOVA, correlation, simple regression, simple regression (multi-group and multiple regression analysis), and structural equation modeling are used to evaluate hypotheses (SEM). Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) software was used to conduct the path analysis utilising correlation and regression analysis. Results are shown in tabular and

pictorial formats. The data were examined using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 26.0 and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed using AMOS 23.0.

4.2 BOTTOM OF THE PYRAMID CUSTOMERS

Bottom of the Pyramid Customers are those customers who belong to poorest socio-economic group. Collected data on BoPC has been analyzed and demonstrated in three categories- the first section under this illustrates the demographic factor details of 218 BoP customers; second section describes the descriptive statistics on various research pertaining constructs such as altitudinal dimensions, purchase behaviour, promotional strategies and brand impact on essential products. Furthermore, in the third section, developed hypothesis were tested and inferred based on the results. Detailed discussion on these three sections is as follows;

4.2.1 Demographic Factors

The demographic profile of the respondents includes Bottom of the Pyramid customers' personal information like origin, age, gender, educational qualification, occupation, income level, number of family members of BoP customer and number of earning members of BoP Customer. The frequency and percentage details of each of the demographic factor are explained in the table 4.1 to 4.8.

Table 4.1: Origin Wise Distribution of the Respondents

Origin	Frequency	Percent
Localities	202	92.7
Migrant	16	7.3
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.1 depicts origin wise distribution of the respondents where the customers are categorized into localities and migrants. out of the total respondents 92.7 percent of the respondents are local respondents are localities and only 7.3 percent are migrants. The migrants are those involved in daily wage work predominantly. As per the percentage result, majority of them are localities and very few are migrants.

Table 4.2: Age Wise Classification of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
20 to 30 Years	15	6.9
31 to 40 Years	50	22.9
Above 40	153	70.2
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.2 depicted age wise classification of the respondents where they are categorized into 20-30 years, 31-40 years and above 40 years of age. It showed out of 218 respondents, 70.2 percent of the respondents are above 40 years, 22.93 percent are between the ages of 31 to 40 years, 6.9 percent are between the ages of 20 to 30 years. The respondents chosen through a purposive cluster sampling are Priority Card holders, and most of the respondents are localites.

Table 4.3: Gender Wise Classification of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	73	33.5
Female	145	66.5
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

As depicted in table 4.3 about the gender wise classification of the respondents, the sample data was for PHC holders and most of the PHH cards are in the name of the female member of the household and the interview was conducted seeking the name of the cardholder, hence, 66.5 percent of the respondents were female, and 33.50 percent were male respondents.

Table 4.4: Education Wise Classification of the Respondents

Education	Frequency	Percent
No Formal Education	32	14.7
School Level	140	64.2
Graduate Level	46	21.1
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

The education wise classification of the respondents is depicted in table 4.4 demonstrates that out of 218 Bottom of the Pyramid Customers, 64.22 percent of the respondents have school-level education, 14.67 percent have no formal education, and 20.64 percent have education up to undergraduate level.

Table 4.5: Occupation Wise Classification of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percent
No Employment	17	7.8
Daily Wage Labour	137	62.8
Salaried	64	29.4
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.5 depicts the occupation of respondents, 62.84 percent of respondents are daily wage labor, and they are comprised of varied occupations such as house helpers,

odd jobs in shops, contract laborers, and so on. While salaried composed of 29,358 respondents, the majority were in private employment as sub staff and so on, further, 7.79 percent have no employment.

Table 4.6: Income Level of Respondents

Income	Frequency	Percent
Below Rs 5,000	17	7.8
Rs 5,001 to 10,000	42	19.3
Rs 10,001 to 15,000	29	13.3
Rs 15,001 to 20,000	45	20.6
Above Rs 20,001	85	39.0
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.6 pertains to the monthly family income of the respondents, it can be seen that 39.0 percent of respondents have mentioned a monthly family income of above INR 20,000. 7.8 percent have a monthly family income of below INR 5,000, 13.3 percent have INR 10,000 to 15,000 monthly family income and 20.6 percent have an income of INR 15,000 to 20,000 and 17.3 percent have a monthly family income of INR 5,000 to 10,000.

Table 4.7: Number of Family Members of BoP Customer

Number of Members	Frequency	Percent
Below 3	54	24.8
3 to 5	136	62.4
5 to 8	21	9.6
8 to 10	7	3.2
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.7 demonstrated the number of members in the family of the respondents where the number of members were categorized into below 3, 3-5, 5-8 and 8-10. As per percentage and frequency table, out of 218 customers 62.4 percent of respondents have 3 to 5 members in their family, 24.8 percent of respondents have below 3 members in their families, 9.6 percent families have 5 to 8 members in their families.

Table 4.8: Number of Earning Members of BoP Customer

Number of Earning Members	Frequency	Percent
Only One	43	19.7
2 to 3	158	72.5
Above 3	17	7.8
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.8 depicted the number of earning members in the family, where the customers are categorized into only one, 2-3 and above 3. Out of 218 respondents, 72.5 percent of respondents have 2 to 3 earning members in the family, while 19.7 percent alone have only 1 earning member, 7.8 percent have above 3 earning members in the family.

4.2.2 Purchase Preference of Branded Essential Product

Purchase preference of branded essential products have been enquired by the BoP customers with respect to place of purchase of rice wheat, place of purchase of tea/coffee powder, cooking oil, salt and place of purchase of tooth paste, shampoo, soap, face powder/cream. BoP customers purchase preference of branded essential product is described in detail in the table 4.9 to 4.11.

Table 4.9: Place of purchase of Rice Wheat

Place of purchase	Frequency	Percent
Government Store	203	93.1
Neighborhood Kirana Store	15	6.9
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.9 depicted the place of purchase of rice and wheat where the preference of respondents were categorized into government store and neighborhood kirana store, it is observed that out of 218 respondents, 93.1 percent of respondents purchased their requirements of rice, and wheat from government ration stores and 6.9 percent visited neighborhood Kirana stores.

Table 4.10: Place of Purchase of Tea/Coffee Powder, Cooking Oil, Salt

Place of Purchase	Frequency	Percent
Neighborhood Kirana Store	131	60.1
Weekly Market	87	39.9
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.10 depicts the place of purchase of essential grocery items such as tea/coffee powder, cooking oil, and salt, 60.1 percent of respondents visited the neighborhood Kirana store to purchase daily use essentials such as tea/coffee powder, cooking oil, salt, etc., 39.9 percent purchased their essential grocery items from the weekly open market. This category of customers preferred the subsidized outlet and convenience stores in their neighborhood, and respondents who visited the weekly open market, famously known as Santhes where most products ranging from food grains to clothes are sold every week in pre-allotted areas of the city.

Table 4.11: Place of Purchase of Tooth Paste, Shampoo, Soap, Face Powder/Cream

Place of Purchase	Frequency	Percent
Neighborhood Kirana Store	169	77.5
Weekly Market	49	22.5
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Depicted above in table 4.11 is the place of purchase of daily FMCG essentials such as Toothpaste, Shampoo, Soap, Face Powder etc., 77.5 percent of the respondents purchase their daily need FMCG essentials from neighborhood Kirana stores considering the proximity to purchase and availability, 22.5 percent of respondents purchase it in the weekly open market.

4.2.3 Descriptive Statistics Attitude Dimension, Promotional Strategies, Purchase Behaviour and Brand Impact

This section describes the collected data in an accurate way to get a descriptive notion about the sample. Here descriptive analysis on attitude dimension, promotional strategies, purchase behaviour and brand impact is explained in detail for the purpose of easy understanding. Mean being a prominent measure of central tendency, it is used in assessing the averages along with standard deviation, minimum and maximum value. The descriptive statistics concerning Bottom of the Pyramid customer is presented in the form of table from table 4.12 to 4.21.

Table 4.12: Descriptive Statistics on Purchase Behaviour

Purchase Behaviour	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by credit availability	1.00	5.00	3.8119	.8832
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by seller recommendation	2.00	5.00	4.0505	.7987
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by product features	1.00	5.00	3.4679	1.2485
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced brand image	1.00	5.00	3.8073	.8900
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by promotion	1.00	5.00	3.7936	.7908
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by word of mouth	1.00	5.00	3.8899	.8296
Purchase Influencers			3.8032	.43807

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.12 demonstrates the descriptive statistics concerning purchasing influencers. Purchase influencer consists of 6 items with the mean value ranging from 3.4679 to

4.0505. As a result all the items showed above average values affirming agreement level on the various purchase influencers. as per the descriptive measures, seller recommendation (mean=4.0505), word of mouth (mean=3.8899) and credit availability (mean=3.8119) tends to be the highest agreed purchase influencers by the respondents as its mean value is higher compared to other purchase influencers. As far as lowest mean is concerned product feature being the purchase influencer (mean=3.4679) was found to be the least agreed item. However, seller recommendation found to be the major purchasing influencer of branded essential products. Overall, the agreement level on purchase influencers shows the mean and SD as 3.8032± .43807.

Table 4.13: Descriptive Statistics on Promotional Strategies of Marketers

Promotional Strategies of Marketers	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Product Features	1.00	5.00	3.9954	.7650
Attractive Prices	2.00	5.00	4.2339	.8005
Free Offers	2.00	5.00	3.8761	.6977
Credit facilities	2.00	5.00	3.8532	.6832
Volume discounts	1.00	5.00	3.9450	.8989
Return Policy	1.00	5.00	3.9495	.7325
Small serving sizes	1.00	5.00	4.0596	.8038
Referrel purchases	2.00	5.00	4.1193	.7707
Gifts	2.00	5.00	4.0872	.5970
Coupons and lucky draws	2.00	5.00	3.9587	.7331
Promotional Strategies of Marketers			4.0078	.3104

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.13 demonstrates the descriptive statistics concerning promotional strategies of marketers. It includes 10 indicators with the mean value ranging from 3.8532 to 4.2339. As a result, all the items showed above average values confirming the preferential level on the various promotional strategies of marketers. As per the descriptive measures, attractive prices (mean=4.2339), referral purchases (mean=4.1193) and gifts (mean=4.0872) tends to be the highly preferred promotional strategies of marketers by the respondents as its mean value is higher compared to other promotional strategies. As far as lowest mean is concerned, credit facilities by the marketers were found to be the least influential promotional strategy (mean= 3.8532). However, attractive prices offered by the marketers found to be the major influential promotional strategies by the marketers. Overall, the agreement level on promotional strategies shows the mean and SD as 4.0078±.31047.

Table 4.14: Descriptive Statistics on Awareness

Awareness	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Popularity of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	4.0596	.8038
Having seen and heard about the product is important consideration in purchase decision	2.00	5.00	4.1193	.7707
Other's opinion of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	2.00	5.00	4.0872	.5970
Seller's/Brand reputation of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	2.00	5.00	3.9587	.7331
Awareness			4.0562	.4198

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.14 depicts the descriptive statistics concerning purchase consideration/ awareness level of the respondents. It includes 4 indicators with the mean value ranging from 3.9587 to 4.1193. As a result, all the items showed above average values confirming the awareness level on various purchase consideration factors. As per the descriptive statistics, having seen and heard about the product (mean=4.1193), other's opinion of the product (mean=4.0872) and popularity of the product (mean=4.0596) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors by the respondents as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. The least preference for purchase consideration was given to seller's/brand reputation of the product (mean=3.9587). However, having seen and heard about the product offered by the marketers found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration. Overall, the awareness level on purchase consideration shows the mean and SD as 4.0562±.4198.

Table 4.15: Descriptive Statistics on Affordability

Affordability	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Price of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	3.9477	0.8345
Credit availability of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	4.4828	0.9390
Digital payment is an important consideration in purchase decision	2.00	5.00	2.9725	1.4369
Return, exchange and ease of buying process is an important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	3.9194	0.8834
Affordability			3.8306	.4919

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.15 illustrates the descriptive statistics concerning affordability of the product. It includes 4 items with the mean value ranging from 2.9725 to 4.4828. As a result all the items showed above average values confirming the attitude level on affordability

of the products. as per the descriptive statistics, credit availability of the product (mean=4.4828), price of the product (mean=3.9477) and return, exchange and ease of buying process (mean=3.9194) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors with regard to affordability, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. The least preference for purchase consideration concerning affordability of the product was given to digital payment (mean=2.9725). However, credit availability of the product found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration. Overall, the agreement level on affordable purchase consideration shows the mean and SD as 3.8306±0.4919.

Table 4.16: Descriptive Statistics on Accessibility

Accessibility	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Availability of the product is important consideration in purchase decision.	1.00	5.00	3.9679	.7703
Convenience of place of purchase	3.00	5.00	4.0872	.6046
Popularity of the store is important consideration in purchase decision.	1.00	5.00	2.9174	1.4973
Small quantity purchase availability is an important consideration in purchase decision.	1.00	5.00	4.0780	.9495
Accessibility			3.7626	.5176

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.16 illustrates the descriptive statistics concerning accessibility of the product. It includes 4 items with the mean value ranging from 2.9174 to 4.0872. As a result all the items showed above average values confirming the attitude level on accessibility of the products. as per the descriptive statistics, convenience of place of purchase (mean=4.0872), small quantity purchase availability (mean=4.0780) and availability of the product (mean=3.9679) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors with regard to accessibility, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. The least preference for purchase consideration concerning accessibility of the product was given to popularity of the store (mean=2.9174). However, convenience of place of purchase found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration. Overall, the agreement level on accessible purchase consideration shows the mean and SD as 3.7626±.5176.

Table 4.17: Descriptive Statistics on Visibility

Visibility	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Store appearance is an important consideration in purchase decision	1.50	5.00	3.9553	.5430
Product visibility in store is an important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	3.9404	.7864
Others' opinion of the store is an important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	4.0092	.9005
Taste/look of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	3.9679	.7763
Other's opinion of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	3.9128	.7897
Seller's/Brand reputation is important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	3.2752	1.4802
Visibility			3.7772	.5955

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.17 illustrates the descriptive statistics concerning visibility of the product. It includes 6 items with the mean value ranging from 3.2752 to 4.0092. As a result all the items showed above average values confirming the attitude level on visibility of the products. as per the descriptive statistics, others' opinion of the store (mean=4.0092), taste/look of the product (mean=3.9679) and store appearance (mean=3.9553) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors with regard to visibility, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. the least preference for purchase consideration concerning visibility of the product was given to seller's/brand reputation (mean=3.2752). However, others' opinion of the store found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration. Overall, the agreement level on accessible purchase consideration shows the mean and SD as 3.7772±.5955.

Table 4.18: Descriptive Statistics on Relationship with Seller

Relationship with Seller	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Offerings by seller is important consideration in purchase decision	2.00	5.00	4.0505	.7003
Service by seller is an important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	4.0000	.7559
Seller's/Brand reputation is important consideration in purchase decision	1.00	5.00	3.2431	1.4402
Complete information given by seller	1.00	5.00	3.3394	1.2788
Personal rapport and friendliness of seller	2.00	5.00	3.8853	.6724
Years of consumer seller association	2.00	5.00	3.9954	.6616
Relationship with Seller			3.7518	.4690

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.18 demonstrates the descriptive statistics concerning customer relationship with seller. it includes 6 indicators with the mean value ranging from 3.2431 to 4.0505. As a result all the indicators showed above average values confirming the attitude level on relationship with seller. as per the descriptive statistics, offerings by seller (mean=4.0505), service by seller (mean=4.0000) and years of consumer seller association (mean=3.9954) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors with regard to customer relationship with seller, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. the least preference for purchase consideration concerning customer relationship with seller was given to seller's/brand reputation (mean=3.2431). However, offerings by seller found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration. Overall, the agreement level on customer relationship with seller as a purchase consideration shows the mean and SD as 3.7518±.4690.

Table 4.19: Descriptive Statistics on Brand Factors

Brand Factors	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Brand means a well-known name, logo, packaging	1.00	5.00	4.0138	.7404
Brand means the product is of repute	1.00	5.00	3.9495	.8326
Brand means high quality	1.00	5.00	3.9954	.7828
Brand means high price	1.00	5.00	4.0550	.7098
Brand means higher social status	1.00	5.00	2.8853	1.4843
Brand means offers	1.00	5.00	4.0688	1.0689
Brand Factors			3.8284	.5387

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.19 demonstrates the descriptive statistics concerning brand factors. It includes 6 indicators with the mean value ranging from 2.8853 to 4.0688. As a result all the indicators showed above average values confirming the attitude level on brand factors. as per the descriptive statistics, brand means offers (mean=4.0688), brand means high price (mean=4.0550) and brand means a well-known name, logo, packaging (mean=4.0138) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors with regard to brand factors, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. The least preference for purchase consideration concerning brand factors was given to brand means higher social status (mean=2.8853). However, brand means offers found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration. Overall, the agreement level on brand factors as a purchase consideration shows the mean and SD as 3.8284±.5387.

Table 4.20: Descriptive Statistics on Brand Impact of Essential Products

Brand Impact of Essential Products	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
When purchasing daily need essentials such as rice, wheat, sugar I buy unbranded product	3.00	5.00	4.0459	.5495
When purchasing daily need essentials such as tea/coffee powder, cooking oil, salt I buy branded product	1.00	5.00	3.0459	1.3771
When purchasing daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, powder I buy branded product	2.00	5.00	4.1606	.9292
I purchase loose products (unbranded) when price is lower	2.00	5.00	3.7615	.9147
I buy loose products (unbranded) when credit facility is available	2.00	5.00	3.7752	.9056
I buy loose products (unbranded) when customer relationship with seller is important to me	1.00	5.00	2.926	1.4572
I regularly repurchase same brand products	1.00	5.00	4.2018	.9579
I will change the brand of purchase if seller recommends	2.00	5.00	3.7064	.8934
Brand Impact on Essential Products			3.7008	.4182

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.20 depicts the descriptive statistics concerning brand impact on essential products. it includes 8 indicators with the mean value ranging from 2.9266 to 4.2018. As a result all the indicators showed above average values confirming the attitude level on brand impact on essential products. as per the descriptive statistics, frequent repurchase of same brand products (mean=4.2018), purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, powder (mean=4.1606) and purchasing branded daily need essentials such as rice, wheat, sugar (mean=4.0459) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors with regard to brand impact on essential products, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. The least preference for purchase consideration concerning brand impact on essential products was given to purchasing unbranded products when customer relationship with seller is important (mean=2.8853). However, purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, powder found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration. Overall, the agreement level on brand factors as a purchase consideration shows the mean and SD as 3.7008±.4182.

Table 4.21: Descriptive Statistics on Overall Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies, Brand Impact on Essential Products

Particulars	Mean	S.D.
Awareness	4.0562	.4198
Affordability	3.8681	.4919
Accessibility	3.7626	.5176
Visibility	3.7772	.5955
Relationship with Seller	3.7518	.4690
Brand Factors	3.8284	.5387
Purchase Behaviour	3.8032	.4380
Promotional Strategies	4.0078	.3104
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.7008	.4182

Source: Survey Data

The above table 4.21 demonstrated the overall descriptive statistics on all the selected parameters; in which the customer perception and attitude on awareness (M=4.0562), affordability (M=3.8681), accessibility (M=3.7626), visibility (M=3.7772), relationship with seller (M=3.7518), brand factors (M=3.8284), purchase behaviour (M=3.8032), promotional strategies (M=4.0078), brand impact on essential products (M=3.7008) showed a mean values above average. Highest perception or attitude level was shown in awareness (M=4.0562), promotional strategies (M=4.0078) and affordability (M=3.8681) compared to other constructs.

4.2.4 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is a major part of any research to answer any research questions, to draw an inference; to understand the link between various selected variables. Hence it determines the research progress and failure. In this study, Friedman's test, Fisher's exact test or chi square test, independent sample t-test, one-way ANOVA, correlation, simple regression, simple regression with multi-group comparison, multiple regression analysis and structural equation modeling are used to evaluate hypotheses. In order to analyze the data concerning Bottom of the Pyramid Customers, 11 developed hypothesis were tested; which is discussed as follow;

H1: Demographic factors of BoP customer will have influence on purchase of Branded Essential Products.

H1.1: Demographic factors of BoP customers will have an influence on the purchase behaviour of branded Essential products in the food grains category (Rice Wheat and Sugar).

Table 4.22: Demographical Factors with respect to purchase of branded essential products: Test Statistics of Fisher’s Exact Test or Chi-square test

Demographic Variable	CSTV	P Value	Inference
Origin	3.797	P<0.05*	Significant
Age	1.229	P>0.05	Not Significant
Gender	.307	P>0.05	Not Significant
Education Level	2.226	P>0.05	Not Significant
Occupation	3.132	P<0.05*	Significant
Monthly Family Income	4.961	P<0.05*	Significant
Number of Members in the Family	0.735	P>0.05	Not Significant
Number of Earning Members in the Family	0.968	P>0.05	Not Significant

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The chi-square test in the table 4.22 depicts the association of demographic variables with purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to essential products (*rice, wheat and sugar*). Origin, occupation and monthly family income have significant influence on the purchase behaviour of priority group customers with regard to essential products (*rice, wheat and sugar*), as the p value in these case is less than 0.01. But majority of the demographic variables such as age, gender, education level, number of members in the family and number of earning members in the family does not show any association with purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to essential products. Overall, the study concludes that demographic factors of priority group customer will not have any influence on the purchasing behaviour of priority customer group with regard to essential products (*rice, wheat and sugar*). Hence, H1.1 is accepted.

H1.2: Demographic factors of BoP customers will have influence on purchasing behaviour with regard to Essential products category of daily consumables (Tea/Coffee Powder, Cooking Oil and Salt).

Table 4.23: Demographical Factors with respect to Essential products category of daily consumables: Test Statistics of Fisher’s Exact Test or Chi-square test

Demographic Variable	CSTV	P Value	Inference
Origin	0.106	P>0.05	Not Significant
Age	1.825	P<0.05*	Significant
Gender	0.110	P>0.05	Not Significant
Education Level	0.19	P>0.05	Not Significant
Occupation	2.257	P<0.05*	Significant
Monthly Family Income	1.591	P<0.05*	Significant
Number of Members in the Family	0.831	P>0.05	Not Significant
Number of Earning Members in the Family	.937	P>0.05	Not Significant

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The chi-square test depicts the association of demographic variables with purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to essential products (*tea/coffee powder, cooking oil and salt*). Age, occupation and monthly family income have significant influence on purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to essential products (*tea/coffee powder, cooking oil and salt*), as the p value in these case is less than 0.01. But majority of the demographic variables such as origin, gender, education level, number of members in the family and number of earning members in the family does not show any association with purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to essential products (*tea/coffee powder, cooking oil and salt*). Overall, the study concludes that demographic factors of priority group customer will not have any influence on the purchasing behaviour of priority customer group with regard to essential products (*tea/coffee powder, cooking oil and salt*). Hence, H1.2 is accepted.

H1.3: Demographic factors of BoP customers will have influence on purchase behaviour with regard to Essential product category of FMCG (Tooth Paste, Shampoo, Soap, and Face Powder/Cream).

Table 4.24: Demographical Factors with respect to Essential product category of FMCG: Test Statistics of Fisher’s Exact Test or Chi-square test

Demographic Variable	CSTV	P Value	Inference
Origin	.138 ^a	P>0.05	Not Significant
Age	4.825 ^a	P<0.05*	Significant
Gender	1.236 ^a	P>0.05	Not Significant
Education Level	6.624 ^a	P<0.05*	Significant
Occupation	2.341 ^a	P<0.05*	Significant
Monthly Family Income	6.789 ^a	P<0.05*	Significant
Number of Members in the Family	14.191 ^a	P<0.05*	Significant
Number of Earning Members in the Family	1.758 ^a	P>0.05	Not Significant

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

The chi-square test depicts the association of demographic variables with purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to non-essentials (*tooth paste, shampoo, soap, and face powder/cream*). Age, occupation, education level, number of members in the family and monthly family income have significant influence on purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to non-essentials (*tooth paste, shampoo, soap, face powder/cream*), as the p value in these case is less than 0.01. But few of the demographic variables such as origin, gender and number of earning members in the family does not show any association with purchasing behaviour of priority group customer with regard to non-essentials (*tooth paste,*

shampoo, soap, face powder/cream). Overall, the study concludes that demographic factors of priority group customer will have significant influence on the purchasing behaviour of priority customer group with regard to non-essentials (*toothpaste, shampoo, soap, and face powder/cream*). Hence, H1.3 is accepted.

H2: Attitudinal dimension have an impact on Purchase Behaviour of Branded Essential Products.

Table 4.25: Model Summary of Attitudinal Dimensions and Purchase Behaviour of Brand Essential Products

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.510 ^a	.261	.240	.38201

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Factors, Affordability, Accessibility, Relationship with Seller, Awareness, Visibility.

The model summary table 4.25 represents coefficient of correlation(r) as .510, indicating the relationship between independent variables (awareness, affordability, accessibility, and visibility, relationship with seller and brand factors) with dependent variable (purchase influencer). R square value (.261) represents the contribution of coefficient of determination on independent variable to dependent variable. It was found that awareness, affordability, accessibility, visibility, relationship with seller and brand factors contributes to purchase influencers by 26.1% and remaining 74.9% are not studied. The adjusted r square (.240) indicates the variation of variable.

Table 4.26: ANOVA result of Attitudinal Dimensions and Purchase Behaviour of Brand Essential Products

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	10.853	6	1.809	12.395	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.791	211	.146		
	Total	41.644	217			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Influencers.

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Factors, Affordability, Accessibility, Relationship with Seller, Awareness, Visibility.

In the above table 4.26 shows the ANOVA results which exhibits that the model is significant, as the p value is less than 0.01. As a result it can be argued that awareness, affordability, accessibility, visibility, relationship with seller and brand factors (IV) highly statistically significant with purchase influencers (DV). The research hypothesis holds true with this regard. Hence the customers' perception on awareness, affordability, accessibility, visibility, relationship with seller and brand factors of the products will have direct effect on its purchase influencers.

Table 4.27: Coefficients result of Attitudinal Dimensions and Purchase Behaviour of Brand Essential Products

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.308	.350		3.737	.000
	Awareness	.003	.076	.002	.034	.973
	Affordability	.092	.056	.104	1.660	.049
	Accessibility	.111	.052	.131	2.136	.034
	Visibility	.179	.055	.243	3.240	.001
	Relationship with Seller	.141	.066	.150	2.117	.035
	Brand Factors	.132	.053	.163	2.488	.014

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Influencers

From the coefficient table 4.27 it is observed that there is a positive slope coefficient between independent variables and dependent variable. Majority of the predictors (IV) such as Accessibility ($p=.034$), Visibility ($p=.001$), Relationship with Seller ($p=.035$), Brand Factors ($p=.014$) and Affordability ($p=.049$) found to be statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance except Awareness level ($p=.973$). Visibility of the product is the strongest predictor of purchase influencer ($B=.179$) as compared to Relationship with Seller ($B=.141$) followed by Brand Factors ($B=.132$), Accessibility ($B=.111$) and Affordability ($B=.092$). It indicates that improvement in the one unit of visibility contributes to 17.9% increase in the purchase influencers among the customers. Moreover, one unit increase in the customers perception on Relationship with Sellers, Brand Factors, Accessibility and Affordability would contribute to 14.1%, 13.2%, 11.1% and 9.2% increase in the customers perception of purchase influencers respectively. As majority of the explanatory variables are statistically significant except awareness ($P>0.05$). Hence, H2 is accepted. Therefore, Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors will directly affect purchase Influencers of the products.

H3: Occupation and Income level of BoP Customer tends to moderate the relationship between Attitudinal Dimensions and their Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products.

H3.1: Occupation level of BoP Customer tends to moderate the relationship between Attitudinal Dimensions and their Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products.

Table 4.28: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients results on moderation of occupation between Attitudinal Dimensions and BoPC's Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products

Occupation	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
No Employment											
Beta	-0.581	0.349	-0.264	0.37	0.376	0.509	.893 ^a	.798	.676	6.571	.005 ^b
t	-2.714	2.697	-1.673	2.741	2.604	3.279					
p	0.022	0.022	0.125	0.021	0.026	0.008					
Daily Wage Labour											
Beta	0.047	0.008	0.214	0.253	0.055	0.101	.554 ^b	.307	.275	9.603	.000 ^c
t	0.492	0.104	3.239	3.353	0.567	1.509					
p	0.624	0.917	0.002	0.001	0.572	0.134					
Salaried											
Beta	0.011	0.231	0.001	0.03	0.199	0.185	.519 ^c	.269	.192	3.501	.005 ^d
t	0.076	2.406	0.01	0.315	1.881	1.751					
p	0.94	0.019	0.992	0.754	0.045	0.049					

Predictor variable: P1-P6 (P1= Awareness, P2= Affordability, P3= Accessibility, P4= Visibility, P5= Relationship with Seller, P6= Brand Factors)

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Behaviour

To demonstrate the contribution that each dimension (P1 to P6) has on the dependent variable (purchase behaviour); the study referred beta Coefficients from. The above table 4.28 shows that, all the independent variables have statistically significant effect on the dependent in case of no employment status of the respondents except Accessibility (P3); when it comes to Daily Wage Laborers, perception towards Accessibility (P3) and Visibility (P4) is significant, since its p-value is below the alpha level which is 0.01. In case of salaried, perception towards Affordability (P2), Relationship with Seller (P5) and Brand Factors (P6) found to be significant. Contemplating the beta coefficients of no employment, the strongest predictor of the dependent variable is P1=Awareness and P6=Brand Factors (-0.581 and 0.509) respectively. From this result, one can infer that, one unit increase in the perception of customers towards P1=Awareness would lead to 58.1% decrease in purchasing influencers. Similarly, one unit increase in P6=Brand Factors would lead to 50.9% increase in purchasing influencers. Furthermore one unit increase in P5= Relationship with Seller, P4=Visibility, P2=Affordability would lead to 37.6%, 37% and 34.9% increase in purchasing influencers respectively. Referring to the beta coefficients of daily wage laborers, the strongest predictor of the dependent variable is P4=Visibility P3=Accessibility and P6=Brand Factors (0.253, 0.214 and 0.101) respectively. From this result, one can infer that, P3= Accessibility is the major contributor of purchasing influencers; this implies that a one unit increase in P4=Visibility would lead to 25.3%

increase in purchasing influencers. Similarly a one unit increase in P3= Accessibility and P6= Brand Factors would lead to 21.4% and 10.1% increase in purchasing influencers respectively. Furthermore the beta coefficient of salaried showed that, P2=Affordability, P5=Relationship with Seller and P6=Brand Factors are the strongest predictors of purchasing influencers. Through this it can be implied that one unit increase in P2=Affordability, P5=Relationship with Seller and P6=Brand Factors leads to 23.1%, 19.9% and 18.5% rise in purchasing influencers respectively.

Overall, it implies that Occupation of the customers tends to moderate the relationship between IV (Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors) and DV (purchase Influencers) of the products, as the p value is less than 0.01 in majority of these cases. Hence, H3.1 is accepted.

H3.2: Income level of BoP Customer tends to moderate the relationship between Attitudinal Dimensions and their Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products.

Table 4.29: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients results on moderation of income between attitudinal dimensions and BoPC's purchase behaviour towards branded essential products

Income	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Below Rs 5,000											
Beta	0.078	0.033	0.353	0.083	1.185	-0.516	.811 ^a	.658	.453	3.210	.050 ^b
t	0.213	0.105	1.178	0.292	3.332	-1.454					
p	0.835	0.918	0.266	0.777	0.008	0.177					
5,001 to 10,000											
Beta	-0.028	0.159	0.114	0.228	0.065	0.338	.704 ^b	.496	.409	5.737	.000 ^c
t	-0.188	1.248	0.827	1.859	0.488	2.208					
p	0.852	0.22	0.414	0.045	0.629	0.034					
10,001 to 15,000											
Beta	0.01	0.189	0.225	0.071	-0.059	0.489	.774 ^a	.599	.490	5.475	.001 ^b
t	0.04	1.506	1.655	0.397	-0.338	3.222					
p	0.968	0.146	0.112	0.695	0.738	0.004					
15,001 to 20,000											
Beta	-0.215	0.045	0.246	-0.009	0.398	0.158	.534 ^c	.285	.172	2.524	.037 ^d
t	-0.953	0.356	1.975	-0.072	2.317	1.558					
p	0.347	0.724	0.049	0.943	0.026	0.127					
Above 20,001											
Beta	0.011	0.051	0.045	0.145	0.144	0.021	.368 ^d	.135	.069	2.031	.071 ^e
t	0.083	0.52	0.536	1.557	1.225	0.246					
p	0.934	0.604	0.593	0.124	0.224	0.806					

Predictor variable: P1-P6 (P1= Awareness, P2= Affordability, P3= Accessibility, P4= Visibility, P5= Relationship with Seller, P6= Brand Factors)

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Behaviour

To demonstrate the contribution that each dimension (P1 to P6) has on the dependent variable (Purchase Behaviour); the study referred beta Coefficients. The above table 4.29 shows that, P5=Relationship with Seller have statistically significant effect on the dependent in case of Below Rs 5,000 income; when it comes to 5,001 to 10,000, P4=Visibility and P6=Brand Factors is significant, since its p-value is below the alpha level which is 0.01. In case of 10,001 to 15,000, perception towards P6=Brand Factors found to be significant. As for 15,001 to 20,000, P3=Accessibility and P5=Relationship with Seller are statistically significant but for Above 20,001 income no independent variable showed significant effect. Referring to the beta coefficient it can be inferred that in case of Below Rs 5,000 income P5=Relationship with Seller (B=1.185), in case of 5001 to 10,000 P6=Brand Factors (B=0.338), in case of 10,001 to 15,000 P6=Brand Factors (B=0.489), in case of 15001 to 20,000 P5=Relationship with Seller (B=0.398) are the strongest predictor of purchasing influencers. It means increase of one unit in P5=Relationship with Seller in case of Below Rs 5,000 income, P6=Brand Factors in case of 5,001 to 10,000, Brand Factors (B=0.489) in case of 10,001 to 15,000 and P5=Relationship with Seller in case of 15,001 to 20,000 contributes to 118.5%, 33.8%, 48.9% and 39.8% increase in purchasing influencers.

Overall result shows that income tend to moderate the relationship between IV (Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors) and DV (purchase Influencers) of the products except above 20,001 income category, as majority of the p value is less than 0.05. Hence, H3.2 is accepted.

Overall, H3 is accepted as it is found that occupation and income moderate the relationship between IV (Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller, Brand Factors) and DV (Purchase Influencers) of the products but income does not moderate.

H4: Promotional strategies of the marketer have direct effect on the BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products.

Table 4.30: Model Summary of promotional strategies of the marketer and BoPC's Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.243 ^a	.059	.055	.4259	.059	13.534	1	216	.000	1.882

a. Predictors: (Constant), Promotional Strategies

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Product

As per the model summary table 4.30, Coefficient of correlation(R) (.243) illustrates that there is a relationship between Promotional strategies and purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products. R² value (.059) in the table represents the influential extent of Coefficient of determination on independent variable (Promotional strategies) to dependent variable (purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products). Moreover, the model summary demonstrates that Promotional strategies by the marketers contribute to purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products by 5.9%. Lastly, the adjusted R square (.055) highlighted the variation in the variables.

Table 4.31: ANOVA result of promotional strategies of the marketer and BoPC's Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	2.455	1	2.455	13.534	.000 ^b
	Residual	39.189	216	.181		
	Total	41.644	217			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Influencers

b. Predictors: (Constant), Promotional Strategies

Referring to the result of ANOVA table 4.31, it is evidenced that the model is significant, as the p value is below 0.01; which indicates statistical significant relationship of Independent variable (Promotional strategies) with the dependent variable (purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products) at 1% level of significance. Therefore, the Promotional strategies have direct effect on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products.

Table 4.32: Coefficients result of Promotional Strategies of the Marketer and BoPC's Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.430	.374		6.491	.000
	Promotional Strategies	.343	.093	.243	3.679	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Influencers

From the coefficient table 4.32 it is observed that coefficient of Promotional strategies is positive with the purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products. Promotional strategies are statistically significant at 99% confidence interval. In order to assess the impact of Promotional strategies on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products, beta coefficients have been referred. Which demonstrates that one unit of increase in the agreement level on Promotional strategies contributes to increase in the purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products by 34.3% (B=.343 units). Overall, considering Model summary, ANOVA and Coefficient results it can be inferred that Promotional strategies have direct effect on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products; hence H4 is accepted.

H5: Occupation and Income tends to moderate the relationship between Promotional Strategies and BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products.

H5.1: Occupation tends to moderate the relationship between Promotional Strategies and BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products.

Table 4.33: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients results on moderation of Occupation between Promotional Strategies and BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products

Occupation	Promotional Strategies	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
No Employment						
Beta	-.403	.282 ^a	.080	.018	1.300	.272 ^b
t	-1.140					
p	.272					
Daily Wage Labour						
Beta	.448	.310 ^a	.096	.090	14.372	.000 ^b
t	3.791					
p	.000					
Salaried						
Beta	.268	.201 ^a	.040	.025	2.614	.111 ^b
t	1.617					
p	.111					

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Behaviour

Contemplating the result of ANOVA table 4.33, it is observed that the model is significant, as the p value is below 0.01. Furthermore, to assess the impact of Promotional strategies on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to selected age occupations. The results revealed statistical significant impact of Promotional strategies on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products with respect to daily wage laborers, as the alpha value is less than 0.01. Referring to beta coefficients, Daily Wage Labor ($B=.448$) considers Promotional strategies as the highest predictor of purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products compared to No Employment ($B=-.403$) and Salaried ($B=.268$). This recommends that one unit of increase in Promotional strategies contributes to 44.8% increase in purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products for Daily Wage Labour; in case of No Employment, 1 unit increase in Promotional strategies leads to 40.3% decrease in purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products; while for Salaried, one unit increase in Promotional strategies would lead to 26.8% increase in purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products. Yet only daily labour shows significant it cannot be stated that Occupation tends to moderate the relationship between promotional strategies and purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products. Therefore, H5.1 is rejected.

H5.2: Income tends to moderate the relationship between Promotional Strategies and BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products.

Table 4.34: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients results on moderation of Occupation between Promotional Strategies and BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products

Income	Promotional Strategies	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Below Rs 5,000						
	.174	.116 ^a	.013	-.052	.205	.657 ^b
	.452					
	.657					
5,001 to 10,000						
	.484	.322 ^a	.104	.081	4.628	.038 ^b
	2.151					
	.038					
10,001 to 15,000						
	.874	.453 ^a	.205	.175	6.958	.014 ^b
	2.638					
	.014					
15,001 to 20,000						
	.285	.251 ^a	.063	.041	2.891	.096 ^b
	1.700					
	.047					
Above 20,001						
	.252	.182 ^a	.033	.021	2.827	.096 ^b
	1.681					
	.049					

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Behaviour

In order to assess the impact of Promotional strategies on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products, the study examined Beta coefficients from the above table 4.34 with respect to income of the respondents. The results revealed statistical significant impact of Promotional strategies on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products with respect to the income of 5,001 to 10,000 (p=.038), 10,001 to 15,000 (p=.014), 15,001 to 20,000 (.047) and Above 20,001 (.049) at 5% level of significance. Although statistical significant impact of Promotional strategies on purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products was not witnessed with respect to below Rs. 5000 (p=.657). The above table revealing ANOVA results show that, independent variable has statistical significant impact on Promotional strategies in majority of the income level, since its p-value is below the alpha level which is 0.05. Referring to the beta coefficients, Promotional strategies are considered to be the strongest contributor of purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products with respect to the income level of 10,001 to 15,000 (B=.874), followed by 5,001 to 10,000 (B=.484), 15,001 to 20,000 (B=.285) and Above 20,001

(B=.252). It implies that increase in one unit of Promotional strategies leads to 87.4% increases in purchasing behaviour of the respondents with the income of 5,001 to 10,000; in case of 5,001 to 10,000, 15,001 to 20,000 and Above 20,001 level of income, one unit hike in Promotional strategies contributes to 87.4%, 48.4%, 28.5% and 25.2% increase in purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products respectively. Overall, it implies that most of the categories of income level of the respondents does not tend to moderate the relationship between promotional strategies and purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products. Therefore H5.2 is rejected.

Overall, H5 is rejected as it is found that Occupation and Income does not moderate the relationship between promotional strategies and purchasing behaviour of the respondents towards branded essential products.

H6: The Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Product is highly influenced by the Seller Recommendation.

Table 4.35: Friedman Test for BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products and Seller Recommendation

Purchase Behaviour	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by credit availability	3.8119	.8832	3.42	4	27.111	P <0.01** Highly Significant
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by seller recommendation	4.0505	.7987	3.90	1		
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by product features	3.4679	1.2485	3.15	6		
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced brand image	3.8073	.8900	3.53	3		
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by promotion	3.7936	.7908	3.37	5		
Purchase of branded essential products is influenced by word of mouth	3.8899	.8296	3.64	2		

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

As per the above table 4.35 representing Friedman's test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 27.111 with the p value below 0.01 at 5 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking between the purchase influencers. Furthermore Purchase of branded essential products is highly

contributed by sellers recommendation (MR=3.90) compared to word of mouth (MR=3.64) and brand image (MR=3.53) followed by credit availability (MR=3.42). Purchase of branded essential products was lowly influenced by the product features (MR=3.15). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H6 is accepted which demonstrates There is significant difference in the mean ranking of customer perception on their Purchasing Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products and as per the mean ranking it can be inferred that the purchase Behaviour of customers towards Branded Essential Product is highly influenced by the seller recommendation.

Figure 4.1: Rating of the Purchasing Behaviour

H7: Lower Prices and Referral Purchase of the Branded Essential Product will have more influence on Promotional Strategies of Marketer.

Table 4.36: Friedman Test for BoP Customers’ Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products and Promotional Strategies of Marketer

Promotional Strategies	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Product Features	3.9954	.7650	5.54	5	48.486	P <0.01** Highly Significant
Attractive Prices	4.2339	.8005	6.30	1		
Free Offers	3.8761	.6977	4.95	9		
Credit facilities	3.8532	.6832	4.92	10		
Volume discounts	3.9450	.8989	5.44	6		
Return Policy	3.9495	.7325	5.33	8		
Small serving sizes	4.0596	.8038	5.67	4		
Referral purchases	4.1193	.7707	5.80	2		
Gifts	4.0872	.5970	5.72	3		
Coupons and lucky draws	3.9587	.7331	5.34	7		

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

As per the above table 4.36 representing Friedman's test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 48.486 with the p value below 0.01 at 9 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking between the customers perception on promotional strategies. Moreover, promotional strategies by the marketer is highly influenced by the Attractive Prices (MR=6.30) compared to Referral purchases (MR=5.80), and Gifts (MR=5.72) followed by Small serving sizes (MR=5.67). But Credit facilities (4.92) lowly contributes the promotional strategies by the marketers. Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H7 is accepted which demonstrates that There is significant difference in the mean ranking of customer perception towards marketing strategies by the marketers and also as per the mean ranking it can be inferred that Lower prices and offers of the branded essential product will have more influence on Promotional Strategies.

Figure 4.2: Rating of the Promotional Strategies

H8: Awareness and Affordability in the Attitudinal Dimension will have more effect on Purchase Behaviour of BoP Customer.

Table 4.37: Friedman Test for BoP Customers' Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products and Attitudinal Dimensions

Attitude	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Awareness	4.0562	.4198	4.38	1	69.249	P<0.01**
Affordability	3.8306	.4919	3.57	2		
Accessibility	3.7626	.5176	3.25	4		
Visibility	3.7772	.5955	3.22	5		
Relationship with Seller	3.7518	.4690	3.13	6		
Brand Factors	3.8284	.5387	3.44	3		

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

As per the above table representing Friedman's test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 69.249 with the p value below 0.01 at 5 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking between the overall attitudinal formations towards purchasing behaviour of BoP customer. Moreover purchase behaviour of BoP customer is highly effected by Awareness (MR=4.38) and Affordability (MR=3.57) compared to Brand Factors (MR=3.44), followed by Accessibility (MR=3.25). But Relationship with Seller (MR=3.13) lowly contributes the overall attitudinal formations towards purchasing behaviour of BoP customer. Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H8 is accepted which demonstrates that There is significant difference in the mean ranking of overall attitudinal formation towards the purchasing behaviour of BoP customer and also as per the mean ranking it can be inferred that Awareness and affordability in the attitudinal formation dimension have more effect on purchase behaviour of BoP customer.

Figure 4.3: Rating of the Attitudinal Dimensions

H8.1: Having seen and heard about the product and its popularity highly contributes to Brand Awareness as a Purchase Consideration.

Table 4.38: Friedman test for significant difference among mean Ranks of Brand Awareness as a Purchase Consideration

Awareness	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Popularity of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	4.0596	.80386	2.51	3	4.437	P >0.05 Not Significant
Having seen and heard about the product is important consideration in purchase decision	4.1193	.77072	2.57	1		
Other's opinion of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	4.0872	.59701	2.54	2		
Seller's/Brand reputation of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	3.9587	.73312	2.38	4		

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

As per the above table 4.38 representing Friedman's test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 4.437 with the p value below 0.01 at 3 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking between the awareness levels of customers. Furthermore, having seen and heard about the product (MR=2.57) and its Popularity (MR=2.51) highly contributes to the awareness level as a purchase consideration compared to Other's opinion of the product (MR=2.54). However, Seller's/Brand reputation has low effect on the customers awareness level as a purchase consideration (MR=2.38). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H8.1 is accepted which demonstrates There is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers awareness level dimensions and also as per the mean ranking it is clear that having seen and heard about the product and its popularity highly contributes to brand awareness as a purchase consideration.

Figure 4.4: Rating of the Awareness level

H8.2: Digital payment and Credit availability highly contributes to the customers' Perception on Affordability as their Purchase Consideration.

Table 4.39: Friedman test for significant difference among mean Ranks of Affordability as a Purchase Consideration

Affordability	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Price of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	3.7477	0.8345	2.33	4	10.492	P<0.012* Significant
Credit availability of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	3.9128	0.9390	2.60	2		
Digital payment is an important consideration in purchase decision	2.9725	1.4369	2.61	1		
Return, exchange and ease of buying process is an important consideration in purchase decision	3.8394	0.8834	2.45	3		

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

As per the above table representing Friedman's test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 10.492 with the p value below 0.01 at 3 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers' perception towards affordability as their purchase consideration. Furthermore, Digital payment (MR=2.61) and Credit availability (MR=2.60) highly contributes to the customers' perception on affordability as their purchase consideration compared to Return, exchange and ease of buying process (MR=2.45). However, Price of the

product has low effect on the customers' perception on affordability as their purchase consideration (MR=2.33). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H8.2 is accepted which shows that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers' perception towards affordability as their purchase consideration and also as per the mean ranking it is clear that Digital payment and Credit availability highly contributes to the customers' perception towards affordability as their purchase consideration.

Figure 4.5: Rating of the Affordability

H8.3: Small Quantity Purchase Availability and Convenience of place highly affects the accessibility dimension of purchase consideration.

Table 4.40: Friedman test for significant difference among mean Ranks of Accessibility as a Purchase consideration

Accessibility	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Availability of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	3.9679	.7703	2.59	3	85.359	P<0.01** Highly Significant
Convenience of place of purchase	4.0872	.6046	2.69	2		
Popularity of the store is important consideration in purchase decision	2.9174	1.4973	1.91	4		
Small quantity purchase availability is an important consideration in purchase decision	4.0780	.9495	2.82	1		

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

As per the above table 4.40 demonstrating Friedman’s test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 85.359 with the p value below 0.01 at 3 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers’ perception towards accessibility as their purchase consideration. Moreover, Small quantity purchase availability (MR=2.82) and Convenience of place (MR=2.69) highly contributes to the customers’ perception towards accessibility as their purchase consideration compared to Availability of the product (MR=2.59). However, Popularity of the store has low effect on the customers’ perception towards accessibility as their purchase consideration (MR=1.91). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H8.3 is accepted which shows that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers’ perception towards accessibility as their purchase consideration and also from the mean ranking it is clear that small quantity purchase availability and Convenience of place highly effects the accessibility dimension of purchase consideration.

Figure 4.6: Rating of the Accessibility

H8.4: Others’ opinion of the store and Taste/look of the product has high influence on customers’ perception towards visibility as a factor of purchase consideration.

Table 4.41: Friedman test for significant difference Among Mean Ranks of Visibility as a Purchase Consideration

Visibility	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Store appearance is an important consideration in purchase decision	3.9553	.5430	3.45	5	38.491	P<0.01** Highly Significant
Product visibility in store is an important consideration in purchase decision	3.9404	.7864	3.60	3		
Others' opinion of the store is an important consideration in purchase decision	4.0092	.9005	3.83	1		
Taste /look of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	3.9679	.7763	3.68	2		
Other's opinion of the product is important consideration in purchase decision	3.9128	.7897	3.48	4		
Seller's/Brand reputation is important consideration in purchase decision	3.2752	1.4802	2.95	6		

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

As per the above table 4.41 representing Friedman's test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 38.491 with the p value below 0.01 at 3 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers' perception towards visibility as a factor of purchase consideration. Furthermore, Others' opinion of the store (MR=3.83) and Taste/look of the product (MR=3.68) highly contributes to customers' perception towards visibility as a factor of purchase consideration compared to Product visibility in store (MR=3.60). However, Seller's/Brand reputation has low effect on the customers' perception towards visibility as a factor of purchase consideration (MR=2.95). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H₀ is rejected which shows that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers' perception towards visibility as a factor of purchase consideration and also from the mean ranking it is clear that Others' opinion of the store and Taste /look of the product has high influence on customers' perception towards visibility as a factor of purchase consideration.

Figure 4.7: Rating of the Visibility

H8.5: Offerings and services by seller majorly contributes to the customers' perception on their relationship with seller as factor of purchase consideration.

Table 4.42: Friedman test for significant difference among mean Ranks of relationship with Seller as a Purchase Consideration

Relationship with Seller	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Offerings by seller is important consideration in purchase decision	4.0505	.7003	3.91	1	82.184	P<0.01** Highly Significant
Service by seller is an important consideration in purchase decision	4.0000	.7559	3.82	2		
Seller's/Brand reputation is important consideration in purchase decision	3.2431	1.440	2.98	6		
Complete information given by seller	3.3394	1.278	2.99	5		
Personal rapport & friendliness of seller	3.8853	.6724	3.51	4		
Years of consumer seller association	3.9954	.6616	3.79	3		

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

As per Friedman's test, the calculated Chi-square value is 82.184 with the p value below 0.01 at 5 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers' perception on their relationship with seller as a factor of purchase consideration. Moreover, Offerings by seller (MR=3.91) and Service by seller (MR=3.82) highly contributes to customers perception on their relationship with seller as factor of purchase consideration compared to Years of consumer seller association (MR=3.79) followed by Personal rapport & friendliness of seller

(MR=3.51). However, Seller's/Brand reputation has low effect on the customers perception on their relationship with seller as factor of purchase consideration (MR=2.98). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H8.5 is accepted indicating there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers perception on their relationship with seller as factor of purchase consideration and also from the mean ranking it is clear that Offerings and services by seller majorly contributes to the customers perception on their relationship with seller as factor of purchase consideration.

Figure 4.8: Rating of the Relationship with seller

H8.6: Brand as offers and high price majorly contributes to Customer perception on brand being the factor of purchase consideration.

Table 4.43: Friedman test for significant difference among mean Ranks of brand factor as a purchase consideration

Brand Factors	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Brand means a well-known name, logo, packaging	4.0138	.7404	3.63	3	123.311	P<0.01** Highly Significant
Brand means the product is of repute	3.9495	.8326	3.59	5		
Brand means high quality	3.9954	.7828	3.62	4		
Brand means high price	4.0550	.7098	3.73	2		
Brand means higher social status	2.8853	1.4843	2.45	6		
Brand means offers	4.0688	1.0689	3.99	1		

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

As per Friedman’s test mentioned in the above table 4.43, the calculated Chi-square value is 123.311 with the p value below 0.01 at 5 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of Customer perception on brand being the factor of purchase consideration. Moreover, Brand as offers (MR=3.99) and Brand as high price (MR=3.73) highly contributes to Customer perception on brand being the factor of purchase consideration compared to Brand as well-known name, logo, packaging (MR=3.63) followed by Brand means high quality (MR=3.62). However, Brand as a higher social status has low effect on the Customer perception on brand being the factor of purchase consideration (MR=2.45). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H8.6 is accepted indicating there is significant difference in the mean ranking of Customer perception on brand being the factor of purchase consideration and also from the mean ranking it is clear that Brand as offers and high price majorly contributes to Customer perception on brand being the factor of purchase consideration.

Figure 4.9: Rating of the Brand Factors

H8.7: Frequent repurchase of same brand products and purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, powder highly contributes to customers' perception towards Brand Impact on Essential Products.

Table 4.44: Friedman test for significant difference among mean Ranks of brand impact on essential products

Brand Impact on Essential Products	Mean	S.D.	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
When purchasing daily need essentials such as rice, wheat, sugar I buy branded product	4.0459	.5495	5.55	3	227.697	P<0.01** Highly Significant
When purchasing daily need essentials such as tea/coffee powder, cooking oil, salt I buy branded product	3.0459	1.3771	3.83	8		
When purchasing daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, powder I buy branded product	4.1606	.9292	6.13	2		
I purchase loose products (unbranded) when price is lower	3.7615	.9147	4.94	5		
I buy loose products (unbranded) when credit facility is available	3.7752	.9056	4.97	4		
I buy loose products (unbranded) when customer relationship with seller is important to me	2.9266	1.4572	3.72	9		
I regularly repurchase same brand products	4.2018	.9579	6.27	1		
I will change the brand of purchase if offers are available	3.7064	.8934	4.76	7		
I will change the brand of purchase if seller recommends	3.6835	.8776	4.83	6		

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

As per Friedman's test mentioned in the above table 4.44, the calculated Chi-square value is 227.697 with the p value less than 0.01 at 8 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers' perception towards Brand Impact on Essential Products. Moreover, it was found that frequent repurchase of branded products (MR=6.27) and purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, powder (MR=6.13) highly contributes to customers' perception towards Brand Impact on Essential Products compared to purchasing branded daily need essentials such as rice, wheat, sugar (MR=5.55) followed by purchasing unbranded products when credit facility is available (MR=4.97). However, purchasing unbranded products when customer relationship with seller is important has low effect on the customers' perception towards Brand Impact on Essential Products (MR=3.72). Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less

than 0.01 (1% level of significance), H8.7 is accepted indicating there is significant difference in the mean ranking of customers' perception towards Brand Impact on Essential Products and also from the mean ranking it is clear that Frequent repurchase of same brand products and purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, powder highly determines customers' perception towards Brand Impact on Essential Products.

Figure 4.10: Rating of the Brand Impact on Essential Products

H9: Promotional Strategies of Marketer mediate the relationship between attitudinal dimension and purchasing behaviour of branded essential products by the BoP Customer.

Figure 4.11: Result of Mediating effect

Table 4.45: Estimate and Significant Value of promotional strategies of marketers in relationship between attitudinal dimension and BoPC's purchasing behaviour towards branded essential products

Particulars			Estimate	P	Label
Promotional Strategies	<---	Attitude	.131	***	HS
Purchase Behaviour	<---	Attitude	.242	***	HS
Purchase Behaviour	<---	Promotional Strategies	.247	.007	S

Note: HS-Highly Significant, S-Significant

The above table 4.45 represents the effect of three major constructs on each other. Firstly, customer attitude towards the products shows direct positive effect on promotional strategies (Estimate=.131, p=.000); which indicates increase in the customer attitude increases promotional strategies adopted by the marketers. Secondly, customer attitude also has direct significant effect on Purchasing behaviour of the customers (Estimate=.242, p=0.000). Lastly, Promotional strategies also has direct significant effect on purchasing behaviour (Estimate.247, p=.007). From the direct effect analysis it is observed that customer attitude has direct effect on promotional strategies; promotional strategies directly effects Purchasing behaviour. Furthermore customer attitude have direct effects on Purchasing behaviour. To analyse the mediation effect of promotional strategies to assess the indirect impact of customer attitude on Purchasing behaviour (Baron & Kenny, 1986; Pearl, 2012) the below table can be referred

Table 4.46: Standardized Estimation (SE) with Direct Effect, Indirect Effect and Total Effect

	Standardized Estimation (SE)	P value	Results
Effect (Total)	.337	0.000**	Statistically significant
Effect (Direct)	.297	0.000**	Statistically significant
Effect (Indirect)	.040	0.000**	Statistically significant

Promotional strategies as a mediator between customer attitude and Purchasing behaviour can be measured through standardized estimates. As per the above table 4.46, customer attitude has a total effect of (Estimate=.337, p=0.000) on Purchasing behaviour; where customer attitude has a direct effect on Purchasing behaviour (Estimate=.297, p=0.000). Moreover, from the indirect effect it is strongly observed that promotional strategies acts as a mediator between customer attitude and Purchasing behaviour (Estimate=.040, p=0.000). Consequently, it can be inferred that promotional strategies mediates the relationship between customer attitude and Purchasing behaviour. Therefore, H9 is accepted.

H10: Attitudinal Dimensions, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on Essential Product are influenced by Demographic Factors.

H10.1: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly different between the origin.

Table 4.47: Independent sample t-test for significant difference between Origins with respect to Attitudinal Dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	Localities	Migrant	t-test	P Value
Awareness	4.0619	3.9844	0.710	P>0.05
Affordability	3.8639	3.9219	0.453	P>0.05
Accessibility	3.7574	3.8281	0.525	P>0.05
Visibility	3.7802	3.7400	0.259	P>0.05
Relationship with Seller	3.7564	3.6938	0.514	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.8401	3.6813	1.136	P>0.05
Overall Attitudinal dimensions	3.8433	3.8082	0.599	P>0.05
Purchase Behaviour	3.8009	3.8319	0.272	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	4.0114	3.9625	0.466	P>0.05
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.6832	3.9236	2.234	P<0.05*

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

The above table 4.47 demonstrates t-test for independence on attitudinal dimension, purchase behaviour, promotional strategies of marketers and brand impact on essential product between origins. Observing the results, one can state that Localities show highest perception level on various attitudinal dimensions as the mean value is high (M=3.8433) compared to Migrant (3.808); however, in case of Purchase Behaviour (3.8319) and Brand Impact on Essential Products (3.9236) Migrants showed high perception level. Lastly Localities (M=4.0114) showed high perception level on Promotional Strategies. As per the Result of t-test for independence it was found that there is no significant difference between the origin of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers except Brand Impact on essential product, as the p value is more than 0.05 in all of these cases. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and are not significantly different between the origins. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.1 is rejected.

H10.2: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour; Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly influenced by the age category.

Table 4.48: ANOVA test for significant difference among Age Categories with respect to Attitudinal Dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	20 to 30	31 to 40	Above 40	F	P Value
Awareness	3.9500	3.9250	4.1095	4.279	P<0.05*
Affordability	3.8500	3.8300	3.8824	.223	P>0.05
Accessibility	3.4167	3.7350	3.8056	4.058	P<0.05*
Visibility	3.7553	3.6530	3.8200	2.849	P<0.05*
Relationship with Seller	3.7800	3.5740	3.8072	1.499	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.6800	3.7540	3.8673	4.852	P<0.01**
Overall Attitudinal Dimensions	3.7386	3.7451	3.8820	2.960	P<0.05*
Purchase Behaviour	3.7120	3.6930	3.8481	1.451	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	3.9867	3.9140	4.0405	2.755	P<0.05*
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.6370	3.7067	3.7052	3.232	P<0.05*

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The above table 4.48 demonstrates One-way ANOVA on attitudinal dimension, purchase behaviour, promotional strategies of marketers and brand impact on essential product among various age categories. Observing the results, one can state that above 40 age category show highest perception level on various attitudinal dimensions as the mean value is high (M=3.882) compared to other age categories; however, in case of Purchase Behaviour (3.8481) and Promotional Strategies (4.0405) Above 40 age category customers showed high perception level. But 31 to 40 age categories (M=3.7067) showed high perception level towards Brand Impact on Essential Products. As per the result it was deduced that there is significant difference among the age categories of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers, Brand Impact on essential product except Purchase behaviour, as the p value is less than 0.05 in all of these cases. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on Essential Products are significantly influenced by the age category. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.2 is accepted.

H10.3: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour; Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly different between the genders.

Table 4.49: Independent sample t-test for significant difference between Gender with respect to Attitudinal Dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	Male	Female	t-test	P Value
Awareness	4.1541	4.0069	2.472	P<0.05*
Affordability	3.9349	3.8345	1.426	P>0.05
Accessibility	3.7158	3.7862	0.948	P>0.05
Visibility	3.8218	3.7548	.435	P>0.05
Relationship with Seller	3.7932	3.7310	.922	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.9014	3.7917	1.421	P>0.05
Overall Attitudinal Dimensions	3.8868	3.8175	1.2706	P>0.05
Purchase Behaviour	3.8174	3.7960	0.340	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	4.0685	3.9772	2.063	P<0.05*
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.6986	3.7019	0.055	P>0.05

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The above table 4.49 demonstrates t-test for independence on attitudinal dimension, purchase behaviour, promotional strategies of marketers and brand impact on essential product between genders. Observing the results, one can state that Male show highest perception level on various attitudinal dimensions as the mean value is high (M=3.8868) compared to Female (3.8175); however, in case of Purchase Behaviour (3.8174) and Brand Promotional Strategies (3.8174) Male showed high perception level. Lastly Female (M=3.7019) showed high perception level on Brand Impact on Essential Products. As per the result of t-test for independence it was found that there is no significant difference between the genders of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, and Brand Impact on essential product except Promotional Strategies of marketers, as the p value is more than 0.05 in all of these cases. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Brand Impact on Essential Products are not significantly different between the genders. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.3 is rejected.

H10.4: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly influenced by the Education Level.

Table 4.50: ANOVA test for significant difference among Education Level with respect to Attitudinal Dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	No Formal Education	Purchase Behaviour	Graduate Level	F	P Value
Awareness	4.0625	4.0446	4.0870	.179	P>0.05
Affordability	3.9141	3.8286	3.9565	1.339	P>0.05
Accessibility	3.8203	3.7536	3.7500	.232	P>0.05
Visibility	3.8953	3.7533	3.7680	.746	P>0.05
Relationship with Seller	3.7625	3.7436	3.7696	.062	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.8406	3.8093	3.8783	.291	P>0.05
Overall Attitudinal dimensions	3.8825	3.8221	3.8682	0.4748	P>0.05
Purchase Behaviour	3.8175	3.7913	3.8293	.150	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	4.0250	4.0064	4.0000	.064	P>0.05
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.6562	3.6706	3.8237	2.568	P<0.05**

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The table 4.50 results demonstrate One-way ANOVA on Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product among the Education Level. Observing the results, one can state that respondents having No Formal Education show highest perception level on various attitudinal dimensions as the mean value is high (M=3.8825) compared to other education level; however, in case of Purchase Behaviour (3.8293) and Brand Impact on Essential Products (3.8237) respondents having Graduate Level education showed high perception level. But respondents having No Formal Education (M=4.0250) showed high perception level towards Promotional Strategies. As per the Result it was deduced that there is no significant difference among the education level of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers, Purchase Behaviour except Brand Impact on essential product, as the p value is more than 0.05 in all of these cases. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Purchase Behaviour are not significantly influenced by the education level of the respondents. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.4 is rejected.

H10.5: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly influenced by the employment status.

Table 4.51: ANOVA test for significant difference among Employment Status with respect to Attitudinal Dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	No Employment	Daily Wage Labour	Salaried	F	P Value
Awareness	4.0588	4.0347	4.1016	.552	P>0.05
Affordability	4.0441	3.8193	3.9258	2.226	P>0.05
Accessibility	3.7647	3.7372	3.8164	.508	P>0.05
Visibility	3.6759	3.7625	3.8358	.595	P>0.05
Relationship with Seller	3.9118	3.7117	3.7953	1.778	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.9059	3.7971	3.8750	.645	P>0.05
Overall Attitudinal dimensions	3.8935	3.8104	3.891	1.050	P>0.05
Purchase Behaviour	3.7847	3.7939	3.8280	147	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	4.0588	4.0036	4.0031	247	P>0.05
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.7451	3.6586	3.7795	1.945	P>0.05

**Significance at 1% Level *Significance at 5% Level

The above table 4.51 demonstrates One-way ANOVA on attitudinal dimension, purchase behaviour, promotional strategies of marketers and brand impact on essential product among the employment status. Observing the results, one can state that respondents having No Employment show highest perception level on various attitudinal dimensions as the mean value is high (M=3.8935) compared to other education level; however, in case of Purchase Behaviour (3.8280) and Brand Impact on Essential Products (3.7795) Salaried showed high perception level. But respondents having no Employment (M=4.0588) showed high perception level towards Promotional Strategies. As per the Result it was deduced that there is no significant difference among the employment status of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product, as the p value is more than 0.05 in all of these cases. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers, Brand Impact on Essential Products and Purchase Behaviour are not significantly influenced by the employment status of the respondents. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.5 is rejected.

H10.6: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly influenced by the Level of Income.

Table 4.52: ANOVA test for significant difference among Level of Income with respect to attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	Below Rs 5000	5001 to 10000	10,001 to 15,000	15001 to 20000	Above 20001	F	P Value
Awareness	4.0000	4.0655	4.0517	3.9556	4.1176	1.188	P>0.05
Affordability	3.6765	3.7202	4.0000	3.8778	3.9294	2.517	P<0.05*
Accessibility	3.9706	3.8155	3.8103	3.8444	3.6353	2.490	P<0.05*
Visibility	3.8324	3.7686	3.7648	3.6776	3.8275	.504	P>0.05
Relationship with Seller	3.8000	3.6357	3.8276	3.6956	3.8035	1.305	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.9118	3.7976	3.9414	3.8200	3.7929	.545	P>0.05
Overall Attitudinal dimensions	3.8652	3.8005	3.8993	3.8118	3.8510	1.4248	P>0.05
Purchase Behaviour	3.9424	3.7657	3.8386	3.8176	3.7741	.655	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	3.9824	3.9357	4.0828	3.9889	4.0329	1.203	P>0.05
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.7190	3.7593	3.5747	3.4988	3.8183	5.615	P<0.01**

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The table 4.52 demonstrates one-way ANOVA on Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product among the level of income. Observing the results, one can state that respondents having Rs.10,001 to 15,000 show highest perception level on various attitudinal dimensions as the mean value is high (M=3.8993) compared to other level of income; however, in case of Purchase Behaviour (3.9424) respondents having Below Rs.5,000 and in case of Brand Impact on Essential Products (3.8183) respondents having Above 20,001 showed high perception level. But respondents having Rs.10,001 to 15,000 (M=4.0828) showed high perception level towards Promotional Strategies. As per the Result it was deduced that there is no significant difference among the income level of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers except Brand Impact on essential product, as the p value is more than 0.05 in all of these cases. But Affordability and Accessibility dimensions of attitude is influenced by the level of income. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers, Purchase Behaviour are not significantly influenced by the level of income of the respondents. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.6 is rejected.

H10.7: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly influenced by the Number of Members in the Family.

Table 4.53: ANOVA test for significant difference among Number of Members in the Family with respect to Attitudinal Dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	Below 3	3 to 5	5 to 8	8 to 10	F	P Value
Awareness	4.1157	4.0496	3.9762	3.9643	.736	P>0.05
Affordability	3.8657	3.8971	3.7262	3.7500	.873	P>0.05
Accessibility	3.7454	3.7629	3.7976	3.7857	.056	P>0.05
Visibility	3.6631	3.8343	3.7538	3.6186	1.258	P>0.05
Relationship with Seller	3.7222	3.7875	3.6857	3.4857	1.228	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.8185	3.8456	3.7667	3.7571	.183	P>0.05
Overall Attitudinal dimensions	3.8217	3.8628	3.7843	3.7269	0.7223	P>0.05
Purchase Behaviour	3.7687	3.8181	3.7929	3.8100	.166	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	4.0241	4.0184	3.9286	3.9143	.767	P>0.05
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.6975	3.7116	3.6243	3.7460	.290	P>0.05

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The above results table 4.53 demonstrates one-way ANOVA on attitudinal dimension, purchase behaviour, promotional strategies of marketers and brand impact on essential product among the level of income. In the above ANOVA Result it was deduced that there is no significant difference among the number of members in the family of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product, as the p value is more than 0.05 in all of these cases. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers, Purchase Behaviour and Brand Impact on essential product are not significantly influenced by the Number of Members in the Family. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.7 is rejected.

H10.8: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product are significantly influenced by the Number of Earning Members in the Family.

Table 4.54: ANOVA test for significant difference among number of earning members in the family with respect to attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	Only One	2 to 3	Above 3	F	P Value
Awareness	4.0698	4.0522	4.0588	.030	P>0.05
Affordability	3.9128	3.8434	3.9853	.859	P>0.05
Accessibility	3.7326	3.7642	3.8235	.190	P>0.05
Visibility	3.7986	3.7559	3.9218	.628	P>0.05
Relationship with Seller	3.8674	3.7120	3.8294	2.129	P>0.05
Brand Factors	3.8186	3.8146	3.9824	.752	P>0.05
Overall Attitudinal Dimensions	3.8666	3.8237	3.9335	0.7646	P>0.05
Purchase Behaviour	3.8286	3.7951	3.8135	.103	P>0.05
Promotional Strategies	3.9837	4.0032	4.1118	1.101	P>0.05
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.7545	3.6920	3.6471	.528	P>0.05

***Significance at 1% Level*

**Significance at 5% Level*

The results depicted in table 4.54 demonstrate one-way ANOVA on Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product among the Number of Earning Members in the Family. In the above ANOVA Result, it was deduced that there is no significant difference among the number of earning members in the family of the respondents with respect to Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on essential product, as the p value is more than 0.05 in all of these cases. Overall, Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers, Purchase Behaviour and Brand Impact on essential product are not significantly influenced by the Number of Earning Members in the Family. Hence, considering the overall results, H10.8 is rejected.

Overall depicting the significant effect it was found that Brand Impact on Essential Products is influenced by the origins of the customers. Moreover, attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on Essential Products are significantly influenced by the age category. Genders have influence on Awareness and Promotional Strategies adopted by the marketers; also Brand Impact on Essential Products is affected by Education Level. Lastly Affordability, Accessibility and Brand Impact on Essential Products are significantly influenced by the level of income. However attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers, Purchase Behaviour and Brand Impact on essential product are not significantly influenced by the demographic factors except age category, as majority of the sub hypothesis under H10 is rejected. Therefore, H10 is rejected.

H11: Attitude level of BoP customer on Branded Essential Product will have impact on Promotional Strategies, Purchase Behaviour and Brand Impact on Essential Products.

Table 4.55: Levels of Attitudinal Dimensions

Attitude Level	Frequency	Percent
Low	27	12.4
Moderate	162	74.3
High	29	13.3
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.55 illustrates the frequency and percentage details of low, moderate and high level of attitudinal dimensions. When the attitude was measured into three levels, it was found that 74.3% of the respondents have moderate attitude level on BoP, 13.3% of have high attitude level and 12.4% of them possess low level of attitude.

Table 4.56: ANOVA test for significant difference among attitude level of BoP customer with respect to Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of Marketers and Brand Impact

Factors	Low	Moderate	High	F	P Value
Purchase Behaviour	3.6667	4.0179	4.2690	34.992	P<0.01**
Promotional Strategies	3.4993	3.7878	4.1717	19.777	P<0.01**
Brand Impact on Essential Products	3.8354	3.7078	3.5364	3.754	P<0.05*

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The above 4.56 demonstrate One-way ANOVA the impact that Attitude level of BoP customer preferring Branded essential product has on Promotional Strategies, Purchase Behaviour and Brand Impact on Essential Products. In the above ANOVA Result it was found that most of the BoP customers have high level of attitude on Purchase Behaviour (M=4.2690) and Promotional Strategies (M=4.1717) but most of them have Low level of attitude on Brand Impact on Essential Products (M=3.8354). Finally, the result showed significant difference among the various level of attitude with respect to Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies and Brand Impact on Essential Products, since the p value is below the significance level. It indicates that Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies and Brand Impact on Essential Products are significantly influenced by the attitude level of the BoP customer. Hence, considering the overall results, H11 is accepted.

4.2.3.1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis between Attitude Dimensions and Purchase Behaviour

The confirmatory model was run to see the correlation of each dimension on each other. The result depicted that Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors are strongly correlated with each other, which strongly ensures that all these dimensions can be taken under one constructs that is attitude. Hence all these indicators are considered to be the dimensions of attitude due to its strong correlation. Furthermore, goodness of fit of this model can be tested through the prescribed recommended value.

Figure 4.12: Unidimensional Analysis

Table 4.57: Goodness of fit results for CFA between attitude dimensions

Model-Fit Indices	Recommended Value	Obtained Value
x^2	-	8.382
Df	-	6
x^2 significant	$p \geq 0.05$	.057
x^2/df	$\leq 2- 5.0$	1.397
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.956
AGFI	>0.80	0.981
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.927
RMSEA	≤ 0.05	0.040

Source: Hu and Bentler (1999), Hair et al., (1998, 2010), Byrne (2001, 2010) and Ernest et al., (2008)

The results of confirmatory factor analysis depicted chi square significant value above 0.05 (.057); x^2/df within the range of 2-5 (1.397). Moreover, GFI was found to be above 0.90 (0.956), AGFI above 0.80 (0.981), NFI above 0.90(0.927) and RMSEA below 0.05 (0.040) which falls well with the prescribed range, hence model confirms its goodness of fit. Hence it is confirmed that Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors are the dimensions of Attitude.

4.2.3.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis between Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors on Purchase behaviour:

In order to confirm the contribution of each dimensions of independent variable i.e. Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors on purchase behaviour Confirmatory factor analysis has been run. The results indicated that in the dimension, awareness consisting of 4 items, having seen and heard about the product has been eliminated due to the low factor loading; in case of affordability consisting of 4 items, contribution of digital payment on purchase behaviour seemed to be low hence it is removed. In case of accessibility having 4 items, availability of the product has been eliminated; under visibility-Store appearance has been deducted, under relationship with seller-Seller's/Brand reputation and Complete information is eliminated whereas, under brand factor Brand means higher social status and Brand means offers has been eliminated due to low factor loading; The goodness of fit of which can be confirmed based on the recommended values.

Figure 4.13: CFA between Attitudinal Dimension and Purchase Behaviour

Table 4.58: Goodness of fit result for CFA between Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, and Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors on purchase behaviour

Model-Fit Indices	Recommended Value	Obtained Value
χ^2	-	36.129
Df	-	16
χ^2 significant	$p \geq 0.05$	.089
χ^2/df	$\leq 2- 5.0$	2.258
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.912
AGFI	>0.80	0.876
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.937
RMSEA	≤ 0.05	0.032

Source: Hu and Bentler (1999), Hair et al., (1998, 2010), Byrne (2001, 2010) and Ernest et al., (2008)

The results of confirmatory factor analysis depicted chi square significant value above 0.05 (.089); χ^2/df within the range of 2-5 (2.258). Moreover GFI was found to be above 0.90 (0.912), AGFI above 0.80 (0.876), NFI above 0.90 (0.937) and RMSEA below 0.05 (0.032) which falls well with the prescribed range, hence model confirms its goodness of fit. Hence, it is confirmed that Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors dimensions contributes to purchase behaviour.

4.3 BOTTOM OF THE PYRAMID RETAILERS

Bottom of the Pyramid Retailers are those who sell the goods to customers belonging to poorest socio-economic group. Through research instrument 2 BoPR data were collected and further analyzed using various statistical methods and tools. In this section it has been categorized into three sections- first section provides information on the demographic details of Bottom of the Pyramid Retailers, second section describes descriptive statistics on retailers' perception on selling branded essential products and retailers perception on brand awareness. Moreover, the last section under this is mainly focused to test the proposed hypotheses and based on which inference has been drawn. Totally, 100 respondents' data were analyzed and described into three categories as follows;

4.3.1 Demographic Factors

The demographic profile of the retailers includes Bottom of the Pyramid retailers' personal information like origin, age, gender, educational qualification, operating duration of the store, average number of walk-ins per day, government authorization of ration store, number of employee, number of stores in operation, percentage of transactions done per usage of paytm, google pay, phonepe etc, percentage of customers currently availing credit facility, percentage of known customers shopping at store, place of purchase, credit facility from the suppliers and frequency of stock purchases. The frequency and percentage details of each of the demographic factor are explained in the table 4.59 to 4.85.

Table 4.59: Origin Wise Distribution of the Retailers

Origin	Frequency	Percent
Localities	82	82.0
Migrant	18	18.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Based on the collected data, origin was divided into localities and migrants. The frequency and percentage table 4.59 presented the number of localities and migrants. As per the percentage, out of 100 respondents, 82% of the respondents are localities, whereas 18% of them are migrants.

Table 4.60: Age Wise Distribution of the Retailers

Age	Frequency	Percent
20 to 25 years	5	5.0
26 to 30 years	16	16.0
31 to 35 years	3	3.0
36 to 40 years	31	31.0
Above 40 years	45	45.0
Total	100	100

Source: Survey Data

The table 4.60 representing age wise distribution has been categorized into 20-25 years, 26-30 years, 31-35 years, 36-40 years and Above 40 years age categories. The frequency and percentage table presented that, out of 100 retailers, 45% of the retailers belong to above 45 age category; 31% of them belong to 36 to 40 years; 16% belong to 31 to 35 years age category; and 5% and 3% of the respondents belong to 20-25 years and 31-35 years age categories respectively.

Table 4.61: Gender Wise Distribution of the Retailers

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	11	11.0
Male	89	89.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.61 presents gender wise distribution of the retailers which consists of male and female retailers. The frequency and percentage results explain that, out of 100 respondents 89% of the retailers are male and 11% of them are female. This shows that female retailers are comparatively fewer retailers, but male are majority in numbers.

Table 4.62: Marital status Wise Distribution of the Retailers

Marital status	Frequency	Percent
Married	90	90.0
Unmarried	10	10.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Marital status wise distribution table 4.62 was categorized into married and unmarried. The frequency and percentage result presented majority of the retailers to be married. Out of 100 retailers, 90% (90) of the retailers are married and remaining 10% (10) are unmarried.

Table 4.63: Education level Wise Distribution of the Retailers

Education	Frequency	Percent
Graduate	52	52.0
No Formal Education	2	2.0
School Level	46	46.0
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.63 displayed education wise distribution of the retailers, where majority of them found to be graduates. The percentage and frequency result showed, out of 100 retailers, 52% of the retailers are graduates, 46% of them have only school level education and only 2% of the respondents had no formal education.

Table 4.64: Operating duration Wise Distribution of the store

Operating duration of the store	Frequency	Percent
2 to 5 Years	28	28.0
5 to 10 Years	36	36.0
Above 10 Years	36	36.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.64 presents operating duration wise distribution of the store categorized into 2-5 years, 5-10 years and above 10 years. As per the percentage and frequency calculations, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 36% of the respondents say that the operational duration of the store is 5-10 years; similarly 36% of the respondents say that the operational duration of the store is above 10 years and Remaining 28% said it is 2 to 5 years.

Table 4.65: Average Number of Walk-ins per Day Wise Distribution

Average Number of Walk-ins per Day	Frequency	Percent
10 to 20	22	22.0
20 to 30	41	41.0
30 to 50	23	23.0
Above 50	12	12.0
Below 10	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.65 presents average number of walk-ins per day wise distribution categorized into 10 to 20, 20-30, 30-50, above 50 and below 10. As per the percentage and frequency calculations, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 41% of the respondents said that average number of walk-ins per day is 20-30; similarly, 23% of the respondents said that average number of walk-ins per day is 30-50, 22% of them said 10-20 and 12% said it is above 50. Only 2% of them said that average number of walk-ins per day is below 10.

Table 4.66: Government Authorized Ration Store Wise Distribution

Government Authorized Ration Store	Frequency	Percent
Yes	23	23.0
No	67	67.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.66 presents Government authorized ration store wise distribution categorized into yes and no. As per the percentage and frequency table, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 67% of the respondents said that their store is not a Government authorized ration (PHRC/NPHRC/BPL/APL) store. Moreover only 23% of them said that their store is Government Authorized Ration (PHRC/NPHRC/BPL/APL) Store. It indicates that majority of the store does not fall under Government Authorized Ration (PHRC/NPHRC/BPL/APL) Store.

Table 4.67: Number of Employee Wise Distribution in the store

Number of Employees in the Store	Frequency	Percent
1	46	46.0
2	45	45.0
3	9	9.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.67 presents number of employee wise distribution categorized into 1, 2 and 3 employees. As per the percentage and frequency results, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 46% of the respondents said that they have only 1 employee in the store. Similarly, 45% of the respondents said they have 2 employees and only 9% of the retailers have 3 employees.

Table 4.68: Number of Stores owned by the BOPR

Number of Stores in Operation	Frequency	Percent
2	6	6.0
3	1	1.0
Only 1	93	93.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.68 presents number of stores in operation wise distribution categorized into 2, 3 and only 1 stores owned by the BOPR. As per the percentage and frequency results, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 93% of the respondents said that they have only 1 store in operation. However only few have 2 to 3 stores in operation. Particularly, 6% of them have 2 stores in operation and 1 % of them have 3 stores. Similarly, 45% of the respondents said they have 2 employees and only 9% of the retailers have 3 employees.

Table 4.69: Volume of Digital Transactions at the Retail Outlets

Volume of Digital Transactions at the Retail Outlets	Frequency	Percent
0%	31	31.0
1% to 10%	45	45.0
10% to 20%	19	19.0
20% to 50%	5	5.0
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.69 presents digital transactions at the retail outlets which was categorized into 0%, 1-10%, 10-20% and 20-50%. As per the percentage and frequency results, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 45% of the respondents said that 1-10% of transactions is done per usage of Paytm, Google Pay, PhonePe etc. However 0% of transactions is done per usage of Paytm, Google Pay, PhonePe etc. 19% of retailers said 10-20% and only 5% said 20-50%.

Table 4.70: Percentage of Customers currently availing Credit Facility

Percentage of Customers currently availing Credit facility	Frequency	Percent
0%	53	53.0
1 % to 10%	29	29.0
10% to 20%	7	7.0
20% to 50%	9	9.0
Above 50%	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.70 presents percentage of customers currently availing credit facility categorized into 0%, 1-10%, 10-20% and 20-50% customers. As per the percentage and frequency results, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 53% of the retailers said no customers are currently availing credit facility. But 29% of them said 1 % to 10% of customers are currently availing credit facility. 9% and 7% of them said 20-50% and 10-20% respectively. But only 2% of the retailers said more than 50% of the customers are currently availing credit facility.

Table 4.71: Percentage of known customers shopping at store

Percentage of known customers shopping at store	Frequency	Percent
Up to 25%	59	59.0
25% to 50%	18	18.0
50% to 75%	12	12.0
All	11	11.0
Total	218	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.71 demonstrates percentage of known customers shopping at store categorized into up to 25%, 25% to 50%, 50% to 75% and all the categories. As per the percentage and frequency results, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 59% of the retailers said up to 25% of known customers shop at store. But 18% of them said 25-50% of known customers shop at store. 12% and 11% of them said 50-75% and all the categories respectively.

Table 4.72: Place of purchase of stock by the BoPR

Place of Purchase	Frequency	Percent
Agents	20	20.0
Distributors	42	42.0
Wholesalers	38	38.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.72 presents place of purchase of stock by the BoPR is categorized into agents, distributors and wholesalers. As per the percentage and frequency results, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 42% of the respondents purchase from distributors; 38% of them purchase from wholesalers and remaining 20% of them make purchases from agents.

Table 4.73: Credit Facility availed by BoPR

Credit Facility from Suppliers	Frequency	Percent
Yes	36	36.0
No	25	25.0
Only a few	39	39.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.73 demonstrates credit facility availed by BoPR is categorized into credit facility availed, no credit facilities availed and only a few credit facilities availed from suppliers. As per the percentage and frequency table, it was found that out of 100 retailers, 39% of the respondents said that they have availed only few credit facilities from the suppliers. Moreover 36% of them have availed credit facilities from the suppliers. Lastly, 25% of them have not availed any credit facilities from the suppliers.

Table 4.74: Frequency of Stock Purchases by BoPR

Frequency of Stock Purchase	Frequency	Percent
Alternative Days	8	8.0
Daily	6	6.0
Weakly	24	24.0
Monthly	30	30.0
Other	32	32.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Survey Data

The table 4.74 depicts frequency of stock purchases by BoPR is categorized into alternative days, daily, weekly, and monthly and other times. The frequency and percentage table presented that, out of 100 retailers, 32% of the retailers prefer other times to purchase the stocks. 30% of the retailers make monthly stock purchases. 24% said weekly stock purchases and 8% said on alternative days. Only 6% prefer to purchase the stocks on a daily basis.

4.3.1.1 Retailers' Attitude towards Selling the Branded Essential Products

Retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products were obtained by categorizing it in terms of lower price, credit facility, profit, relationship with supplier and supplier recommendation as an important aspect to sell the branded essential products. The table demonstrates the retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products.

Table 4.75: Retailers' Attitude towards Selling the Branded Essential Products

Particulars	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	DA (%)	SDA (%)
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3	53	24	16	4
Credit Facility is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	3	47	25	22	3
Profit is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	4	56	24	15	1
Relationship with Supplier is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	5	46	27	21	1
Supplier Recommendation is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	5	59	27	8	1

Source: Survey Data

The table 4.75 depicts frequency of agreement level on retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products. As per the first statement, 53% agreed that Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products but 24% of them gave neutral perception. Moreover, 47% agreed that they prefer Selling loose Products because your Supplier provide Credit facility, 25% of them showed neutral perception. In addition, 56% of them agreed that they prefer selling loose Products because they get Higher Profit and 24% of them give neutral perception. Furthermore, 46% of them agreed that they prefer selling loose Products because you have a long-term Business Relationship with the Supplier and 27% of them. Lastly, 59% of the respondents agreed that Supplier Recommendation is Important when selling Branded Essential Products and 27% of them gave a neutral perception.

4.3.1.2 Retailers' Perception on Brand Awareness

Retailers' perception on brand awareness were obtained by categorizing it in terms of Customer differentiation on brand, perception on brand as a name, logo, packaged product, preference to sell low priced product over branded products and packaged products etc. The below table provides detailed demonstration of Retailers' perception on brand awareness.

Table 4.76: Retailers' Perception on Brand Awareness

Particulars	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	DA (%)	SDA (%)
Your Customers are Capable of differentiating between Branded and Un-Branded Product	5	59	27	8	1
Branded Product means a familiar Name, Logo, and Packaging	4	73	18	16	1
Branded Product means a Packaged Product	7	68	19	6	0
Branded Product means a Product Originated from a Reputed Place	3	44	38	0	0
Prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Branded Product	8	52	35	5	0
Prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Packaged Product	9	53	28	10	0
Prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Product Originated from a Reputed Place	8	34	36	22	0
Prefer Recommending Products to your Customers for which you get Higher Profit from the Supplier	25	48	5	22	0
Believe that the Store will Lose existing Customers by Displaying Branded Products	0	28	14	52	6
Believe that Displaying Branded Products Attracts new Customers to Your Store	7	68	19	6	0

Source: Survey Data

The table 4.76 depicts frequency of agreement level on retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products. As per the first statement, 59% of the respondents agreed that their customers are capable of differentiating between Branded and Un-Branded Product and 27% of them give neutral perception on this. Moreover majority (73%) of the retailers agree that Branded Product means a familiar Name, Logo, and Packaging and 18% have neutral perception on this statement. As per the next statement, 68% of the respondents agree that Branded Product means a Packaged Product and 19% gave neutral perception with this regard. 44% agree that Branded Product means a Product Originated from a Reputed Place and 38% give neutral perception. Furthermore, 52% of the retailers agree that they prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Branded Product and 35% of them have neutral perception on it. 53% of the retailers agreed to the statement that they prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Packaged Product and 28% of them give neutral perception. In addition, 36% of the respondents have a neutral perception on preferring Sales of Lower Priced Product over a Product Originated from a Reputed Place but 30% of them agreed to it. 48% of the retailers prefer Recommending Products to your Customers for which you get Higher Profit from the Supplier and

25% of them strongly agree to it. But 22% disagree with this statement. 52% of the respondents disagree that the store will lose existing customers by displaying branded products whereas 28% of the respondents agree to it. Lastly, 68% of the respondents agree that displaying branded products attracts new customers to their store and 19% gave neutral perception with this regard.

4.3.2: Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.77: Descriptive Statistics on Retailers' Attitude towards selling the Branded Essential Products

Particulars	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	2.00	5.00	3.6300	.70575
Credit Facility is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	1.00	5.00	3.2500	.93609
Profit is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	2.00	5.00	3.7600	1.0647
Relationship with Supplier is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	1.00	5.00	3.3300	.8995
Supplier Recommendation is Important when selling Branded Essential Products	2.00	5.00	3.6100	.7900
Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB	1.00	5.00	3.5160	.5722

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.77 demonstrates the descriptive statistics concerning the Attitude on Branded Essential Products by BoPR. It includes 5 indicators with the mean value ranging from 3.2500 to 3.7600. As a result all the indicators showed above average values confirming the retailers' attitude on Branded Essential Products. As per the descriptive statistics, Profit is Important when selling Branded Essential Products (3.7600), Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products (Mean=3.6300) and Supplier Recommendation is Important when selling Branded Essential Products (Mean=3.6100) tends to be the highly preferred factors with regard to retailers' attitude on Branded Essential Products, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. The least preference for retailers' attitude towards selling the branded essential products was given to Credit Facility is Important when selling Branded Essential Products (Mean=3.2500). However, Profit is Important when selling Branded Essential Products found to be the majorly preferred. Overall, the perception level on retailers' attitude on Branded Essential Products shows the mean and S.D. as $3.5160 \pm .5722$.

Table 4.78: Descriptive Statistics on Brand Awareness

Particulars	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Your Customers are Capable of differentiating between Branded and Un-Branded Product	1.00	5.00	3.5900	.7533
Branded Product means a familiar Name, Logo, and Packaging	1.00	5.00	3.7500	.6415
Branded Product means a Packaged Product	2.00	5.00	3.7300	.6005
Branded Product means a Product Originated from a Reputed Place	2.00	4.00	3.2600	.7469
Prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Branded Product	2.00	5.00	3.6300	.7057
Prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Packaged Product	2.00	5.00	3.6100	.7900
Prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Product Originated from a Reputed Place	2.00	5.00	3.2800	.8998
Prefer Recommending Products to your Customers for which you get Higher Profit from the Supplier	2.00	5.00	3.7600	1.0647
Believe that the Store will Lose existing customers by Displaying Branded Products	1.00	4.00	2.6400	.9589
Believe that Displaying Branded Products Attracts new Customers to Your Store	2.00	5.00	3.7600	.6684

Source: Survey Data

Table 4.78 demonstrates the descriptive statistics concerning retailers' attitude on Brand Awareness. It includes 10 indicators with the mean value ranging from 2.6400 to 3.7600. As a result all the indicators showed above average values confirming the retailers' perception on Brand Awareness. As per the descriptive statistics, believe that displaying branded products attracts new customers to your store (3.7600), prefer recommending products to your customers for which you get higher profit from the supplier (Mean=3.7600), branded product means a familiar name, logo, and packaging (3.7500) and branded product means a packaged product (mean=3.7300) tends to be the highly preferred factors with regard to retailers' perception on brand awareness, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences. The least preference for retailers' perception towards branded products was given to believe that the store will lose existing customers by displaying branded products (Mean=2.6400). However, they believe that displaying branded products attracts new customers to your store and prefer recommending products to your customers for which they get higher profit from the supplier found to be the majorly preferred. Overall, the perception level on retailers' perception on Brand Awareness shows the mean and S.D. as $3.7600 \pm .6684$.

4.3.3: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing has been obtained to answer research questions concerning Bottom of the Pyramid retailers to draw an inference; to understand the link between various selected constructs. Under hypothesis testing of BoP Retailers the researcher used independent sample Friedman's test, Fisher's exact test or chi square test, t-test, one-way ANOVA, correlation, to evaluate hypotheses. In order to analyze the data concerning Bottom of the Pyramid Retailers, 2 developed hypothesis were tested; which is discussed as follow;

H12: Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influence by tenure of business, number of walk-ins per day, duration of stock purchase and percentage of known customer.

H12.1: Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influence by the tenure of business.

Table 4.79: ANOVA test depicting the relationship among the tenure of business and Attitude of BoPR towards BoPB

Factors	2 to 5 Years	5 to 10 Years	Above 10 Years	F	P Value
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.6429	3.7778	3.4722	1.718	P>0.05
Credit Facility is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.1786	3.3611	3.1944	.394	P>0.05
Profit is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.9643	3.8333	3.5278	1.471	P>0.05
Relationship with Supplier is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.2143	3.5556	3.1944	1.801	P>0.05
Supplier Recommendation is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.6071	3.6667	3.5556	.175	P>0.05
Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB	3.5214	3.6389	3.3888	1.746	P>0.05

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The above table 4.79 depicts One-way ANOVA results concerning attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among tenure of business. As per the above table, the retailers having 2-5 years of business (3.9643) and 5-10 years of business (3.8333) showed highly perceived attitude towards profit as important factor in selling branded essential products. But the retailers with more than 10 years of business showed highest perceived attitude towards Supplier Recommendation is Important in selling Branded Essential Products (3.5556). Overall result demonstrated that the retailers having tenure of 5-10 years of business showed highest attitude of BoPR toward BoPB compared to 2-5 years (3.5214) and above 10 years of business (3.3888). The result of one-way Anova revealed that there is no significant difference in all the items under

attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among the tenure of business, as the p value is more than 0.05. It indicates that, attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is not influence by the tenure of business. Hence, H12.1 is rejected.

H12.2: Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influence by the number of walk-ins per day.

Table 4.80: ANOVA test depicting the relationship among the frequency of walk-ins per day and Attitude of BoPR towards BoPB

Factors	Below 10	10 to 20	20 to 30	30 to 50	Above 50	F	P value
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	5	3.4091	3.6829	3.7391	3.4167	3.143	P<0.05*
Credit Facility is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.5	2.8182	3.561	2.913	3.5833	3.863	P<0.01**
Profit is Important selling Branded Essential Products	2	3.5455	3.7317	4.1304	3.8333	2.441	P<0.05*
Relationship with Supplier is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.5	2.9091	3.4878	3.5217	3.1667	1.972	P>0.05
Supplier Recommendation is Important selling Branded Essential Products	5	3.4091	3.8293	3.4348	3.3333	3.710	P<0.01**
Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB	3.8	3.2182	3.6585	3.5478	3.4666	2.421	P<0.05*

***Significance at 1% Level*

**Significance at 5% Level*

The above table 4.80 depicts One-way ANOVA results concerning attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among number of walk-ins per day. As per the above table, the retailers having below 10 walk in per day showed highly perceived attitude towards lower price (5.000) and suppliers recommendation (5.000) as important factor in selling branded essential products. Moreover, retailers having 10 to 20 (3.5455), 30 to 50 (4.1304) and Above 50 (3.8333) walk in per day showed highly perceived attitude towards profit as important factor in selling branded essential products. But the retailers having 20-30 walk in per day showed highly perceived attitude towards suppliers' recommendation (3.8293) as important factor in selling branded essential products. Overall result demonstrated that the retailers having Below 10 (3.8) showed highest attitude of BoPR toward BoPB compared to 20 to 30 (3.6585), 30 to 50 (3.5478), above 50 (3.4666) and 10 to 20 (3.2182) walk in per day. The result of one-way ANOVA revealed that there is significant difference in majority of the items under attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among the average no. of walk ins per day, as the p value is less than 0.05. It indicates that, attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is significantly influence by the average no. of walk in per day. Hence, H12.2 is accepted.

H12.3: Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influence by duration of Stock purchase.

Table 4.81: ANOVA test depicting relationship among duration of Stock Purchase and Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB

Factors	Daily	Alternative Days	Weekly	Monthly	Others	F	P Value
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.3333	3.25	3.7083	3.7	3.6563	1.004	P>0.05
Credit Facility is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.1667	2.75	3.625	3.0667	3.2813	1.91	P>0.05
Profit is Important selling Branded Essential Products	4.1667	4.25	3.875	3.3333	3.875	2.099	P>0.05
Relationship with Supplier is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.5	3.125	3.9167	2.9333	3.2813	4.842	P<0.01**
Supplier Recommendation is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.8333	3	3.7083	3.6667	3.5938	1.475	P>0.05
Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB	3.6	3.275	3.7666	3.34	3.5375	2.386	P<0.05*

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The above table 4.81 depicts One-way ANOVA results concerning attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among duration of Stock purchase. As per the above table, the retailers purchasing the stocks on Daily (4.1667), Alternative Days (4.25) and other times (3.875) showed highly perceived attitude towards profit as important factor in selling branded essential products. Moreover, retailers purchasing the stocks on weekly basis (3.9167) showed highly perceived attitude towards relationship with suppliers as important factor in selling branded essential products. But the retailers purchasing the stocks on monthly basis (3.6667) showed highly perceived attitude towards suppliers' recommendation (3.6667) as important factor in selling branded essential products. Overall result demonstrated that the retailers purchasing the stocks on daily basis (3.6) basis showed highest attitude of BoPR toward BoPB compared to others times (3.5375), Monthly (3.5478) and Alternative Days (3.275). The result of one-way Anova revealed that there is significant difference in the attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among duration of stock purchases, as the p value is less than 0.05. It indicates that, attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is significantly influence by the duration of stock purchases. Hence, H12.3 is accepted.

H12.4: Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influence by the percentage of known customer.

Table 4.82: ANOVA test depicting relationship among the percentage of known customers and Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB

Factors	Up to 25%	25-50%	50-75%	All	F	P value
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.7458	3.7222	3.1667	3.3636	1.004	P>0.05
Credit Facility is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.322	3.5	3.6667	2	1.91	P>0.05
Profit is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.7797	4	4.5	2.4545	2.099	P>0.05
Relationship with Supplier is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.3559	3.6667	3.8333	2.0909	4.842	P<0.01**
Supplier Recommendation is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.5932	4	3.3333	3.3636	1.475	P>0.05
Attitude of BoPR toward BoPB	3.5593	3.7777	3.7	2.6545	2.386	P<0.05*

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The above table 4.82 depicts One-way ANOVA results concerning attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among percentage of known customer. As per the above table, the retailers having Up to 25% (3.7797), 25-50% (4) and 50-75% (4.5) of known customers showed highly perceived attitude towards profit as important factor in selling branded essential products. Overall result demonstrated that the retailers having 25-50% (3.7777) of customers showed highest attitude of BoPR toward BoPB compared to 50-75% (3.7) and up to 25% (3.5593). The result of one-way Anova revealed that there is significant difference in the attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among percentage of known customer, as the p value is less than 0.05. It indicates that, attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is significantly influence by the percentage of known customer. Hence, H12.4 is accepted.

H13: Attitude of BoPR toward Branded Essential Products is Negative.

Table 4.83: Karl Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient with attitude of BoPR towards Branded Essential Products

Particulars	Pearson’s r	P	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	0.513	P<0.01**	0.352	0.644
Credit Facility is Important selling Branded Essential Products	0.741	P<0.01**	0.638	0.818
Profit is Important selling Branded Essential Products	0.580	P<0.01**	0.433	0.697
Relationship with Supplier is Important selling Branded Essential Products	0.824	P<0.01**	0.748	0.878
Supplier Recommendation is Important selling Branded Essential Products	0.566	P<0.01**	0.416	0.686

** Denotes significance at 1% level

* Denotes significance at 5% level

It is found that the attitude of BoPR is positive toward Suppliers and the lower-priced loose products over the branded essential products and this relation are statistically significant with moderate and strong positive correlation as detailed in table 4.83.

Table 4.84 Friedman test for significant difference among mean ranks of Attitude of BoPR toward Branded Essential Products

Particulars	Mean Rank	Rank	CSTV	P value
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.13	3	36.662	P<0.01**
Credit Facility is Important selling Branded Essential Products	2.58	5		
Profit is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.47	1		
Relationship with Supplier is Important selling Branded Essential Products	2.67	4		
Supplier Recommendation is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.17	2		

** Denotes significance at 1% level

* Denotes significance at 5% level

As per Friedman’s test mentioned in the above table 4.84, the calculated Chi-square value is 36.662 with the p value less than 0.01 at 99 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking of retailers’ attitudes of BoPR toward branded essential products. Moreover, it was found that profit as important selling branded essential products (MR=3.47) and Supplier Recommendation is Important selling Branded Essential Products (MR=3.17) highly contributes to retailers’ attitude of BoPR toward branded essential products compared to other statements. Since asymptotic significant (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), there is significant difference in the mean ranking of retailers’ attitudes of BoPR toward branded essential products.

Table 4.85: Significance Test Summary of BoPR

Particulars	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Lower Price is Important in selling Branded Essential Products	3.6300	.70575	99	P>0.05
Credit Facility is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.2500	8.927	99	P<0.01**
Profit is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.7600	2.671	99	P<0.01**
Relationship with Supplier is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.3300	7.138	99	P<0.01**
Supplier Recommendation is Important selling Branded Essential Products	3.6100	3.668	99	P<0.01**

**Significance at 1% Level

*Significance at 5% Level

The significance test (One sample t-test) is detailed in table 4.85 which indicates that the calculated p-values for all the components are less than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, at a 95% confidence level the alternate hypothesis the ‘attitude of BoPR toward Branded Essential Products is Negative’ is accepted. It is also noticed that the effect size of all the components is above 0.80 which means the effect size is ‘Large’. Overall, it was found that attitude of BoPR toward branded essential products is negative. Hence, H13 is accepted.

CHAPTER-V

ABCD QUANTITATIVE FRAMEWORK AND DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The ABCD analysis framework is a business model evaluation tool that takes into account all parameters of a business. This technique evaluates a business model, strategy, or operational strategy from the standpoint of the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages arising out of it. Further, it streamlines the data to identify the critical constituent elements in each determinant factor to narrow critical elements that need to be looked at to overcome the constraints and focus on the advantages to give the benefits.

5.2 BACKGROUND

Business models are defined as a set of unique process or activity which results in sustainable profit through desired revenue and customer value. It spells out the strategy of the organization for business growth and development. Thus, a business model in management is a simplified representation of an operation or a process in which only the most important aspects of the activity under discussion are Thus a business model in management is a simplified representation of an operation or a process in which only the most important aspects of the activity under discussion are gauged and the model is developed for further usage.

A new analysis technique namely ABCD analyzing framework adopted to study a business model, business strategy, concept, idea, or a business system. ABCD is an acronym that stands for Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages. The application of ABCD analysis results in obtaining an organized set of business constructs called advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages in a systematic matrix [185-186]. This displays the various issues that can be identified for models/concepts/systems based on a generalized framework and then how to derive a specific framework for either a business model or a concept or a system specifically. A general guideline is given on how to identify various factors affecting these determinant issues based on the four constructs of advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages [187-192].

Aithal *et al.*, (2016) [186] developed ABCD analyzing framework to analyze any business model/concept and to study its effectiveness in providing value to its stakeholders and sustainable profit through expected revenue generation. This is in line with what the BoP market strategy also asks multinationals to do as per mentioned

in the works of Prahalad, Hart and others. The application of this ABCD analysis technique results in an organized list of a business advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages in a systematic matrix. The entire framework is divided into various issues/areas of focus and various business deployment factors affecting the business/concept can be identified and analyzed under each issue by identifying the suitable critical effective element [189-190]. This analyzing technique being simple gives guidelines to identify and analyze the effectiveness of any business model or strategy and new concepts developed.

ABCD analysis framework is also used for the analysis of the Black Ocean strategy concept. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the black ocean strategy on organizational issues, administrative issues, employee issues, business issues, external environmental issues, and operational issues for an organization have been identified and analyzed by studying various affecting factors and their constituent critical elements [191-194]

Multinationals and Indian companies would need to adapt business models to suit the fast-changing economy. If they aim at volumes then they would require developing new products and services with features appealing to the emerging market consumers-high functionality on features and stripping away features that add only cost without any value addition to the end consumer [187-188]. These products and services will then need to be supported by distribution logistics and service networks across the country with low infrastructure. Therein, distribution costs will spiral and put further pressure on thin margins.

5.3 OBJECTIVES

The present study is to analyze the concept of whether it is possible to generate revenue profitably by selling in BoP segments of emerging markets and its effectiveness in adding value to companies and generating revenues by using the ABCD analyzing framework. This includes:

- Finding various determinant issues related to the general business strategy to operate in BoP markets.
- Listing affecting factors under constructs-advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages for identified key attributes.

- Identifying the critical constituent elements for each construct using its elemental analysis technique.
- Finally discuss and suggest how the ABCD framework is an optimum methodology in analyzing the business opportunity for a company in BoP segments of emerging markets and its effectiveness in adding values and generating revenues.

5.4 REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

A review of the literature is an important part of the research process. It is a review of relevant literature conducted to develop a better understanding of what is known about a specific case, phenomenon, or issue and to identify knowledge gaps. Another reason for conducting a literature review is to assist the researcher in understanding how well the results of the study fit into the existing knowledge. As a result, this study reviewed various articles related to the study. This section is divided into four sections: 1) Review of literature on the BoP market, 2) Review of related articles on ABCD Listing, 3) Review of related articles on ABCD analysis depicting influencing factors and critical constituent elements, and 4) Review of related articles on Quantitative ABCD analysis with construct weightage.

5.4.1 Review of Literature on the BoP Market

Since this study is primarily concerned with the BoP Market, referring to pertinent previous studies is essential. Few of the scholarly publications on management practices, case studies on BoP markets, BoP marketing, growth, corporate imperialism etc. have been discussed below in table 5.1

Table 5.1: Selected papers that discussed BoP Market

SL. No.	Area/Focus	Purpose/Outcome	Reference
1	Indigenous Management Practices	Through networks, value propositions, effective word-of-mouth marketing, adaptability, critical need identification, localized productions or sourcing, proximity, and flexible terms of purchase, street vendors manage the competition. It would be possible for huge firms and big wholesalers to try and get into these markets if they had a thorough understanding of the rural and semi-urban areas as well as some of the subsistence markets in cities.	Keerthan, R. (2017)[187]
2	Study on Hindustan Unilever Limited	The key to success in an extremely diverse market like India would be to partner locally, connect with the average consumer, and localize both the goods and the sales strategies. The BoP sector won't be open to trying out innovative goods and services until they see there is a sustainable value in them.	Keerthan, R. & Aithal, P. S. (2017) [188]

3	Creating Mutual Value	Eleven agricultural initiatives were examined in-depth to gain insight into the approaches they take to deal with obstacles and improve value creation and capture by BoP producers. According to the results, removing obstacles benefits not just regional producers but also the businesses involved.	London, T., Anupindi, R., & Sheth, S. (2010) [49]
4	Corporate Imperialism	Multinational corporations will increasingly need to change their resource bases, cost structures, product development procedures, and assumptions about the cultural diversity of their senior management to compete successfully in the major emerging markets. To be globally competitive in the post-imperial era, they will need to adopt new business strategies and create a new attitude.	Prahalad, C. K., & Lieberthal, K. (1998) [2]
5	BoP Market to Tap	In the BoP context, business owners must consider how to create markets and how to do it in a setting that presents special difficulties.	Simanis, E. (2011) [196]
6	BoP Marketing	Due to its wealth density, closeness, homogeneity, and modernity, the urban BoP market offers large businesses greater profitability than the rural BoP. Multilevel channels and inclusive pricing, as opposed to the BoP marketing strategies of rock low prices, novel items, and sachets, resulted in a substantial increase in BoP sales for the reputable middle-class.	Ireland, J. (2008) [197]
7	Market Growth BoP Markets.	The study's goal was to create a methodology that guides the creation of marketing plans for BoP segment market expansion. To create expanding markets, several tactics outside the purview of marketing strategy are required	Nagy, M., Bennett, D., & Graham, C. (2019) [60]
8	Branding on Base of the Pyramid Markets	If sustainability and loyalty are to be built, branding in BoP segments needs to involve consumers from the segment from the product inception stage to the end delivery and after-sales stages. This cannot be achieved by simply extending products and services marketed in other markets using creative local media and word of mouth.	Raj, Keerthan and Aithal, P. S., (2018) [101]
9	Generating Wealth at BoP	To advance business strategies and adapt successful models to operate in BoP marketplaces, it will be highly helpful to use the amount of information that has been categorized under determinants and impacting variables. The most important success component will be made feasible by turning the negative effects of the restrictions into positive possibilities that will aid the businesses' expansion, growth, and profitability.	Raj, Keerthan and Aithal, P. S., (2018) [198][199]
10	Digitization of India	The socioeconomic lives of those at the base of the pyramid have already been significantly impacted by India's digital endeavors, and this impact will only grow in the coming years.	Raj, K., & Aithal, P. S. (2018) [200]
11	Big Data Effect on Base of the Pyramid	The beginning point for obtaining in-depth information on the mostly ignored BoP segment, even if they represent an attempt to comprehend and analyze the aspects of big data from the perspective of the base of the pyramid marketplaces. The BoP	Raj, K., & Aithal, P. S. (2018) [201][202]

		market processes are greatly strengthened by big data.	
12	Cockroach Theory	A wide range of different business models, business strategies, and learnings have all been incorporated into the BoP opportunity area to create crucial success elements that have fuelled development and sustainability. Different opinions on what constitutes the essential elements for sustaining and growing may emerge throughout time as a result of newer techniques, successes, and failures. It is not necessary to locate riches at the base of the pyramid; international corporations and even domestic companies can successfully exploit this mostly untapped market to create wealth and design a strategy geared toward everyone's socioeconomic growth.	Raj, K., & Aithal, P. S. (2018) [203][204][205]
13	Sustainable Development in India 2.0	This conceptual paper examines India's steady growth during the India 2.0 era (1992 to the present), which was further fueled by the Modi government's numerous initiatives. It also considers ways to achieve sustained development from the BoP's point of view, with a particular emphasis on economic development, social development, environmental protection, and industry development.	Raj, K., & Aithal, P. S. (2018) [206]
14	Impact of COVID-19 on the Bottom of the Pyramid	To comprehend the intensity and effects of the epidemic and its accompanying limitations and governmental actions on the population, the researchers used a mixed methodology to investigate a sample of this population at the base of the pyramid.	Raj, K., & Aithal, P. S. (2020) [207]

5.4.2 Review of Literature on the ABCD Analysis Framework

Aithal, P. S. *et al.*, (2015) [185] proposed the ABCD analysis framework to provide a simple and organized method for identifying a variety of problems that are harming a system and opening up opportunities for solutions. The review of the ABCD analysis is used to determine the topic, focus, and outcome of the research article, as well as the author's references. Because it considers other strategic methods of analysis including "SWOC, EFE & IFE Matrices, BCG matrix, Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM) analysis, PESTLE Analysis and Porter's Five Forces Model" [190-191][208], many research-based publications have been produced based on this analysis framework. As far as ABCD analysis is concerned, three different applications of the ABCD analysis framework are found in the literature: (1) ABCD listing, (2) ABCD analysis with affecting factors and critical constituent elements, and (3) quantitative ABCD analysis with construct weighting. According to current scholarly research methodologies, ABCD analysis is suggestible for industry analysis,

company analysis, product analysis, service analysis, patent analysis, etc. A system of producers or businesses working together with the common objective of producing a certain range of goods or services is known as an industry. Industry analysis can also be done using the ABCD paradigm [209]. The numerous business difficulties that affect a firm or group of companies can be analysed utilizing internal and external factors that influence the managers' choices regarding the issues. The ABCD listing was used in a prior study to analyse a company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and restraints [210–211]. This framework employs traits or elements to analyse data using structures or parameters [212]. The ABCD framework can be used for patent analysis in addition to studying companies, industries, and several other concepts and phenomena [213]. The researcher has chosen to use ABCD analysis to assess the feasibility of doing business in the BoP sector and has used this technique in a quantitative format to evaluate its efficacy considering the technique's varied applications. The review of literature on ABCD analysis is further categorized as a) Literature review on ABCD listing, b) Literature review on ABCD analysis depicting influencing factors and critical constituent elements, and, c) Literature review on Quantitative ABCD analysis with construct weightage.

Using the framework, one might list important advantages, benefits, restrictions, and downsides of each discovered determining issue after doing the qualitative study. Additionally, it introduces the idea of ABCD listing, which is a necessary step before performing quantitative ABCD analysis [214][190]. A qualitative approach can be used to compile a list of significant benefits, limitations, and drawbacks for each identified determining issue after a large number of issues have been chosen for investigation. This will provide an of how ABCD analysis, also known as ABCD listing, works. Table 5.2 displays a few academic works that have listed advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages from the general or author's point of view:

Table 5.2: Selected papers that used ABCD listing

Sl. No.	Area/Focus	Purpose/Outcome	Reference
1	Online Campus Placement Model	This study identified the online campus placement model's practical viability, utility, resourcefulness, and universal applicability to recruiters, pupils, parents, society, and institutions.	Varun Shenoy, & Aithal P. S., (2016) [214]
2	Choice-Based Credit System	The traditional classroom-based education model and the ubiquitous online education model supported by technology both aim to redefine the curriculum in line with the liberalization and globalization of education. Students are given easy access through CBCS to a variety of educational institutions located all over the world, as well as the option to transfer their earned credits.	Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2016) [215]
3	Private universities in India.	Private universities' advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages for many stakeholders, including students, faculty, parents, businesses, and society, are explored.	Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2016) [216]
4	Online Education	Online education is one of the potential developments in the next generation of educational systems. The study highlighted the role of online learning in higher education as the future generation of learning and its effects on the advancement of science and society. There is a discussion of the various online education models and their significance.	Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2016) [217]
5	On-line Office Administration	A group of online office managers can oversee and manage office operations from their homes, eliminating the need for physical locations for online global education providers and universities. It has been discovered that such a model lowers costs for employers and service providers in terms of office space and maintenance as well as for employees in terms of travel, better home-cooked food, etc.	Reshma, P. S., Acharya, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2015) [218]
6	International Business and its Environment.	To analyze international strategic plans and environmental analysis frameworks, the study employed the ABCD listing approach to determine the advantages, benefits, restrictions, and downsides of various frameworks.	Aithal P. S. (2017) [219]
7	ABC Model of Annual Research Productivity	This study used the ABCD analysis method on the ABC model of higher education institutions' annual research productivity.	Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T. & Suresh Kumar, P. M., (2016) [220]
8	New Research Indices	Utilizing the qualitative method of ABCD analysis/listing, five indices—the ARP Index, RC-Index, RE-Index, Project Productivity Index, and Cost Index—were analysed.	Aithal, P. S. (2017) [221]

9	Six Thinking Hats Based Analysis	Six thinking hats was analysed through assessing the Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages for taking risk Decisions.	Rangi, P. K., & Aithal, P. S. (2020) [222]
10	Organizing the Unorganized Lifestyle Retailers	ABCD listing was used to compare the organized and unorganized lifestyle.	Ganesh H. R., & Aithal, P. S. (2020) [223].
11	Student Centric Learning Though Planned Hard work	The repercussions of shifting the curriculum from the state to the national level can be addressed by a college by creating an inventive model for students to follow.	Aithal, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2016) [224]
12	Innovation in B.Tech. Curriculum as B.Tech. (Hons)	ABCD listing is an effective tool to analyse STEAM & ESEP based B.Tech. (Hons) Model	Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2019) [225]
13	Green Education	In this paper, the significance of the educational system and the design of the curricula was explored in the context of future prospects.	Aithal, P. S., & Rao, P. (2016) [226]
14	Green Energy and Global Warming	Green energy lessens the extraction of carbon from the ground, reducing geological imbalance. For the best results, energy generation and use can be decentralized. The installation of renewable energy sources on rooftops to accommodate individual needs satisfies home energy needs. This lessens radiation from the sun's rays on the rooftop as well as energy waste. However, the needs of the industry might not be satisfied by this adoption strategy.	Aithal, P. S., & Acharya, S. (2016) [227]
15	Smart Library Models for Future Generations	Technology improvements are causing a revolution in the library system. The majority of resources are currently accessible online, therefore a click-and-mortar library system is the way of the future.	Aithal, P. S. (2016) [228]
16	MUDRA	The study looked at how much MUDRA's financial requirements contributed to cash flow in the agricultural sector. Entrepreneurship in agriculturally related industries to expand employment possibilities in rural and urban India. The advantages, benefits, limitations, and drawbacks of MUDRA support to SMEs, MSMEs, and agriculture are illustrated through study.	Aithal, P. S., & Sharma, K. R. S. (2022) [229]
17	PPP Model of MIA	The MIA's PPP Model shows promise for enhancing service delivery professionalism, efficacy, and expertise in accordance with worldwide norms.	Kumari, P., & Aithal, P. S. (2020) [230]
18	Performance Evaluation of Dabur India Ltd.	This section covers the significance of the profitability ratio, modifications to the profitability components, analysis of the profitability ratio, CSR programmes, and the ABCD listing of Dabur Company.	Bharathi, & Suresh Ramana Mayya. (2022) [231]

19	Grading In Higher Education	By analysing competency level performance indicators and identifying the major variables leading to competency, their purposes, and consequences, it was possible to identify the factors that aid in predicting performance in a work setting. The intervention strategies for higher education institutions are also covered in this article.	Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2019) [232]
20	Online E-Campus Recruitment Process	Due to the use of cutting-edge automated technology and super process excellence approaches in the corporate context, even employing new personnel has been organised as an online flow system for consistent results.	Shenoy, V., Aithal, P. S., & Pai, R. (2018) [233]
21	Livestream as an Innovative Marketing Medium	Livestream is a great tool for recruiting internal team members and allies for the company. A persistent trend in retail and e-commerce is livestreaming. The live feed was an excellent way to reach customers and boost engagement during the outbreak	Rajasekar, D. & Aithal, P. S. (2022) [234]
22	Online Pharmacy Model	Examined customer perceptions, opinions, and worries regarding the internet's role in the drug supply chain. Examinations of the numerous issues and factors affecting online pharmacies have been done using the ABCD listing approach.	Aithal, A., & Shabaraya, A. R. (2018) [235]
23	Furniture Manufacturing Companies	This investigation discovered a number of fine facts related to furniture price, customization, and unique selling proposition through segmentation/segments that they are operating in.	Amin, V. S., & Kumar, A. (2022) [236]
24	Srinivas University B.Com Model In Corporate Auditing	To overcome the difficulty of simultaneously studying two disciplines with distinct curricula, Srinivas University launched a B.Com programme in Corporate Auditing with a CA intermediate syllabus. The program's special characteristics, perks, and advantages for obtaining a Dual degree/certification have been covered in detail.	Aithal, P. S., & Noronha, S. (2016) [237]
25	IT-Virtualization	By using virtualization, the physical server footprint can be reduced. The data centers will run at their highest levels of energy and floor space efficiency. A smaller server will operate more efficiently, produce more heat, necessitate more cooling equipment, and take up less floor space, therefore its size is a significant concern. Virtualization will enable the removal of all of these restrictions.	Lathika, K. (2016) [238]
26	Social Media	Through virtual meetings, the company created the metaverse, which enables people to select their preferred style. Fashion brands and companies have created their own digital collections for millions of players worldwide using internet sites (meta platforms), new items, and partnerships with video games.	Madhura, K., & Panakaje, N. (2022) [239]

27	Ideal Software	The topic of debate is the characteristics of hypothetical software, or ideal software, and the potential application of such software for any kind of system automation and networking, or Universal Automation.	Aithal, P. S., & Pai T, V. (2016) [240]
28	Electricity from microbial fuel cell in rural India.	Investigated the challenges in creating MFCs for rural India. MFCs must be developed at a high cost in order to provide the population of the rural area with adequate electricity. The ABCD listing for use in rural India was used to evaluate this.	Acharya, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2017) [241]

The above discussed papers have clearly demonstrated the usage of ABCD listing. There many articles apart from the above articles which has listed various advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of Role of ICCT Underlying Technologies [242], Women Entrepreneurship in Food Processing Sector [243], Holistic Integrated Student Development Model & Service Delivery Model [244], Online E-Campus Interview Training [245], Mobile Information Communication Technologies [246], Innovations & Business Opportunities [247], Student Centric Curriculum Design and Implementation [248], Retrieval Time of Manual and Electronic Medical Records [249], new attitude-behaviour (AB) theory [250], Block chain [251] and Indian Pharmaceutical Sector [252]. All of the aforementioned articles on ABCD listing have provided examples of how to list out advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages and have assisted researchers in their evaluation of the efficacy of various business models, phenomena, concepts, etc.

5.4.3 Review of Literature on the ABCD Analysis with Affecting Factors and Critical Constituent Elements

To delve further deeper into factor and basic analysis using the ABCD paradigm, some academic papers are cited. The determinant concerns found in academic articles employing the ABCD framework are displayed in the tables below.

Table 5.3: Selected papers that used ABCD Analysis with Affecting Factors and Critical Constituent Elements

Sl. No.	Area/Focus	Determinant issue	Reference
1	BoP	Operational issues, Stakeholder issues, Business issues, Users/customer issues.	Raj, Keerthan and Aithal, P. S., (2018) [198]
2	The well-being of Care takers	Psycho education and Jacobson's muscle relaxation therapy.	PV, A. H., & Kotian, S. (2022) [253]
3	Work from home	Employers/ Employees issues, Environmental & Social issues, Customer/Student issues, and Organizational issues.	Reshma, Aithal, P. S., & Acharya, S. (2015) [254]
4	Dye-doped Polymers for Photonic Applications	Commercialization Issues, Customer Issues, Material Issues, Application Issues, Production/Service providers Issues, Environmental/Society Issues	Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Kumar, P. M. (2016) [255]
5	Private University System in India.	Financial Resources, Image, Programs, Faculty Profile.	Aithal, P. S., and Shailashree, V. T., and Kumar, P. M. Suresh. (2015) [256]
6	Black Ocean Strategy.	Administrative Issues, Business Issues, External Issues, Employee Issues, Operational Issues.	Aithal, P. S., and Shailashree, V. T., and Kumar, P. M. Suresh. (2016) [5]
7	NAAC Accreditation System	Organizational Issues, Student support progression Issues, Faculty Performance Issues, Issues on Infrastructure, Learning resources and Research, Governance, Leadership & Innovations Issues.	Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M., (2016) [9]
8	National Institutional Ranking System and Higher Education.	Organizational issues, Student Issues, Academic issues, Faculty Issues, Other Stakeholders Issues, Issues on Administration Infrastructure and Learning resources.	Aithal, P. S., and Shailashree, V. T., and Kumar, P. M. Suresh. (2016). Aithal, P. S., (2017) [257][258]
9	Business model and systems	Organizational issues, Business operation issues, Stakeholders issues, Environment/society issues, Technology issues.	Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016) [259]
10	Theory A	Organizational issues Employees issues, Managers issues, Ideological issues, Societal and Stake Holder issues.	Aithal, P. S., Kumar, P. M., & Shailashree, V. (2016) [260]
11	Six Thinking Hat Technique	Organizational issues, Conceptual issues, Operational issues, Managerial issues, and Societal & stakeholders issues.	Aithal, P. S., VT, S., & Kumar, P. M. (2016) [261]
12	Research Productivity	Organizational Issues, other stakeholders issue, Students issue and Academic issue.	Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Kumar, P. M. (2016) [262]
13	Industrial Internship Programme	Student Issues, Institute Issues, Society Issues and Host Company Issues.	Frederick, D. P., & Shailashree, V. T. (2022) [263]

14	Online food delivery system	Customer Issues, Supplier Issues, Food Delivery Technology Issues and Delivery Partner Issues.	Frederick, D. P., & Bhat, G. (2022) [264]
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Multiple studies on ABCD analysis have explored identifying the concerns that make up its determinants, allowing for further discovery of numerous aspects influencing the specific issue. The aforementioned articles used ABCD analysis while taking determinant factors into account. In addition to these, many other studies have also discussed ABCD analysis while taking determinant factors into account, including those on the Multifactor Authentication Model [265], Fingerprint Biometric Attendance [266], Institutional Ranking System [267].

5.4.4 Literature Review on Quantitative ABCD Analysis with Construct Weightage

To comprehend the direction for quantitative ABCD analysis, numerous other studies that have applied the quantitative ABCD analysis techniques have also been reviewed, these articles are mentioned herein regarding online food delivery services, organic food products, education for corporate sustainability, new research indices, stress coping mechanisms and work force studies reviewed in table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Selected papers that used Quantitative ABCD Analysis with Construct Weightage

Sl. No.	Area/Focus	Purpose/Outcome	Reference
1	Online Food Delivery Services.	Quantitative ABCD research of Online Food Delivery Services indicated that Advantages aspects contribute considerably to the success of the firm. The outcome of the ABCD study supports the premise that online food delivery services are effective.	Frederick, D. P., & Bhat, G. (2022) [268]
2	Organic Food Product and Purchase Intention.	Studying the ABCD Analysis Framework for Online Shopping and identifying the key factors that influence it are the study's main objectives. According to study findings, of the four components, the advantages factor has a greater positive impact on the country's development.	Frederick, D. P., Sujaya, H., & Salins, M. (2022) [269]
3	Education for Corporate Sustainability	Examined the ABCD analysis to determine whether the study of education for corporate sustainability reporting was appropriate. Furthermore, it was shown that the higher educational institutions' idea of education for business sustainability disclosures offers significant benefits to the stakeholders.	Nayak, P., & Kayarkatte, N. (2022) [270]
4	IEDRA Model	The study's goal was to understand the IEDRA Model of Campus Placement Determination's applicability, resourcefulness, and Universal Applications to Concerned Stakeholders.	Shenoy, V., & Aithal, P. S. (2017) [271]

5	Task Shifting	This research does the ABCD analysis of task-shifting by taking into account six determining issues. Twenty-one main characteristics, eighty-four influencing aspects, and 172 essential constituent elements are what make this analysis process successful.	Aithal, A., & Aithal, P. S. (2017) [272]
6	Stress Coping Mechanisms	Examines the stress coping mechanisms related to cabin crew in international airlines in India.	Pavithra Kumari, & Aithal P. S. (2022) [273]

5.5. APPLICATION OF THE ABCD ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE TO STUDY BoP MARKETS STRATEGIES AND MODELS

Based primarily on secondary data of the successes and failures, modus operandi of various multinationals and large corporations who have ventured to do business in the base of the pyramid markets, and on the basis of focus group studies conducted the researcher has developed a list of the key determinant issues affecting the proposition of doing business and the study has classified the main factors as per ABCD analysis as either advantages, benefits, constraints or disadvantages in the prime issues considered [255][262][275].

The various issues considered at a macro level are as mentioned in the block diagram below

Figure 5.1: Application of ABCD analysis to study the feasibility study of BoP Markets (2018)

Source: Aithal, P. S. (2017) [259]

The followings are the determinants of a general business strategy to operate in BoP markets:

1. Stakeholders Issues-profitable business-Stakeholders will always be concerned about the profitability of the new market or segment entry strategy. When new products need to be developed, as in today's scenario when large businesses are looking at 'beyond greening', on creating a value chain proposition, the financial resources required will be very huge, if it fails it cannot just be hived off into a charitable foundation arm, the stakeholders will have a constant lookout on this aspect.
2. Business Issues-New market entry-to look for increased income by selling in emerging markets where there is a huge opportunity to sell products and services to low-income groups. Even though in the low-income category of consumers the essentials are not yet available to the consumers, new needs can be tapped and addressed profitably.

Strategy to adapt to these markets-the biggest challenge is to create or feature existing products in a way that meets the requirements of the market while not being too expensive to produce and sell. The infrastructure in most emerging markets of the world is not substantive, hence, distribution logistics are going to eat into the financial resources thus maybe creating a drop in margins. Overcoming this with unique strategies is a critical success determinant.

3. Operational Issues-Distribution, reach, and existing knowledge or expertise-working on the product features and distribution network could need significant changes. If they have been successful across the globe, multinationals need to ensure that they do not carry this baggage because this could blind their view of strategizing newer ways, and additionally, there could be challenges in the bureaucratic policies of the countries that the firms might want to enter.
4. Users/customer Issues-Strategizing businesses around emerging market needs and responding to their unique specific consumer behaviours. It needs a deeper understanding of what drives businesses here.
5. Technological Issues-Technological expertise and the need to create environmentally safe products and co-creation are critical-Most large corporations, whether home or foreign have built a technological strength. This is something that can be very useful to recreate features, and products to suit the needs of the

consumers at the base of the pyramid segments.

Global scale and local reach-multinationals having global scale have to adopt local techniques and localize productions and sales. Evolving sustainable business solutions is the success criterion.

6. Environmental & Social Issues-Beyond greening sustainable solutions-As, Hart has been addressing issues around greening and beyond greening in the recent past, environmental and social concerns are predominant among the emerging markets. Especially, since there is also the argument that multinationals should not arm twist and take undue advantage of the base of the pyramid consumers and exploit them for profits. Hence, value co-creation while involving them in the process is important.

Analysis of generating revenues profitably (extracting wealth) by operating in BoP markets using ABCD framework by considering above discussed determinant issues to choose affecting factors for identified key attributes under the constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are listed in table 5.5.

Table 5.5: Determinant Issues and the ABCD analysis of each issue

Key Attributes	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
I – Stakeholder Issues				
High Costs of entry	Bigger market share globally	Global leadership	Leveraging costs	Lack of local knowledge
Profitability	Mover advantage	Increased revenue in the long run	Initial low margins	Unsuccessful product sets
Brand dilution concern	Extended brand and flagship products	Diverse product portfolio	Niche customer valuations	Loss of Unique product segment leadership
II – Business Issues				
New market strategies	Fresh outlook	Untapped revenue sources	Global Knowledge	Lack of local knowledge
Functional Capabilities	Adaption to Local community	Increased revenues	Costs of reaching customers	Company myopia
Strategic decisions on the P's of marketing	New opportunity to experiment	Vast untapped needs and Product suites	Acceptability and sustenance	Failure to understand consumers
III – Operational Issues				
Bureaucratic issues in Market Access	Entry issues, no easy access to all	Better local understanding	Problems and high entry costs	Appears unattractive
Product Policies	Grassroots study	Wider productsuite	Local acceptance & information sharing	An experimental approach could lead to heavy losses

Distribution reach	Vast opportunity	Build strong logistics	Infrastructure	Scalability
Current company strategy and business outlook	New business arena	Create diverse model	Existing knowledge and experience	High costs of implementation and operation
IV – Customer Issues				
Acceptance	Expansive market	Word of mouth publicity	Close-knit communities	Negative repercussions
Sustainability	Growth	Market share	Short-sighted approach	Too much focus
Approach	First mover advantage	Difficult to copy	Needs in-depth understanding	Expensive and extensive
V – Technological Issues				
Co-creation	Successformula	Value creation	Bottlenecks	Lack of long-run planning
Eco friendly	Positive affect	Better acceptance	Production technology	High Costs
Maintaining Lowcosts	Eases pricing issues	Lower price offerings	Operational issues	Better margins
VI – Environmental and Social Issues				
Beyond greening	Friendly technology	Sustained value	Associated Cost	Low margins initially
CSR	Philanthropic in outlook	Positive image	Administrative	Long gestation
Sustainable valuecreation	Global technology	Market value and brand image	Local players	Lack of local knowledge

Source: Author

5.6. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF CONSTITUENT CRITICAL ELEMENTS AS PER ABCD MODEL

As per the ABCD framework for the aspect of considering the strategies of extracting wealth at the base of the pyramid markets by multinationals and large corporations affecting Stakeholder issues, Business issues, Operational Issues, Customer Issues, Technological Issues, and Environmental/Social Issues are identified [272]. The critical constituent elements of these factors are listed under the four constructs- advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the ABCD technique and tabulated in tables 2 to 5. The critical constituent elements were identified by a focus group discussion with industry representatives who are operating in the BoP segments across various product categories. The quantitative methodology developed for the study was by assigning appropriate weightage for the critical constituent elements after focused discussions with industry experts. The ratings were arrived at by eliciting responses for the CCEs from the BoP partners, and retailers through a systematic primary data collection for the CCE with the weighted scores.

5.6.1 Weights

Each element in the CCE of each key attribute has been assigned a weight ranging from 1.0 (low importance) to 10 (high importance) in total. The number indicates how important the factor is if a company wants to succeed in this segment. If there were no weights assigned, all the factors would be equally important, which is an impossible scenario in the real world. The sum of all the weights of each key attribute must equal 10. Separate key attributes are all given equal emphasis in weightage assignment (assigning a total weight of 10 each) because the framework looks at the equal importance of key attributes identified in an industry.

5.6.2 Ratings

The ratings in ABCD Quantitative Matrix refer to how strong or weak each factor is in a firm. The numbers range from 5 to 1, where 5 means a Highly important factor, 4 – Moderately important factor, 3 – Averagely important factor, 2 – Not very important, and 1 – Least important. The process of assigning ratings is based on experts opinion using a benchmarking tool with existing business situations and published literature.

5.6.3 Weighted Score

The score is the result of weight multiplied by the rating. Each factor of the key attributes must receive a score. The totalled score is simply the sum of all individual weighted scores. The total score of <75 is poor and can be interpreted as weak attributional factors that can be easily overcome with a suitable strategy. A total score of $>75 <150$ is considered a key attribute that has significant importance and needs adequate attention. A total score of $> 150 < 300$ is considered very important from the standpoint of strategizing and the analysis framework score. Here, it can be seen that the advantages and benefits have received a total score of 227 and 218 respectively, while constraints have received a total score of 83, which can be interpreted as the total advantages and benefits of doing business in the BoP segment outweigh the constraints, and as it can be studied the disadvantages have a total score of 155, hence the firm has to work rigorously to take stock of its inherent advantages and benefits to formulate strategies to enter, operate and sustain in the market in such a way that that the inherent disadvantages are considered carefully to convert them into to opportunities.

Table 5.6: Advantages of operating in the BoP market

Particulars	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Elements	Weightage	Average Rating Scores	Weighted Score
Stakeholder Issues	Entry Strategy	First mover advantage	2	5	10
	Profits	Scalability	3	4	12
	Brand Image	Extended brand line	2	3	6
	Nascent Market	Product differentiation	3	4	12
Business Issues	Fresh Outlook by adopting new strategies	Develop workable models	2	4	8
	Adaption to the local community	Sustainability	2	3	6
	Untapped market	Value creation	2	4	8
	Possibility of failure	Failed strategy and unacceptability	2	4	8
	Operation Costs	Leveraging on existing value points	2	5	10
Operational Issues	Limited Knowledge Market	Economic and Socio-cultural understanding	3	4	12
	Distribution	Infrastructure	2	3	6
		Inventory	2	2	4
	New business arena	In-depth Market research	3	4	12
Customer Issues	Market acceptance	Adaption to local needs	3	4	12
		Co-partnering - Tie up with the local community and existing players	3	4	12
	Growth	Sustained value creation through partnership	2	4	8
	Approach	Create first mover advantage	2	3	6
Technological Issues	Co-creation	Possible sharing of technological expertise	2	4	8
	Eco friendly	Beyond greening technologies	3	3	9
	Cost vs. profits	Keep costs low	3	4	12
	Tech savviness of BoP	Digital transactions	2	4	8
Environmental and Social Issues	CSR	Community Support	3	4	12
		Provide socio-economic development	3	4	12
	Beyond greening	Sustained value	2	3	6
	Global technology	Focus on strengths	2	4	8
Total			60	94	227

Source: Author

Table 5.7: Benefits of operating in the BoP market to generate higher revenues

Particulars	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Element	Weightage	Average Rating Scores	Weighted Score
Stakeholder Issues	Global leadership	Local adaptability	2	5	10
	Profits	Scalable and sustainable success	4	5	20
	Diverse product portfolio	Create niche brands for specific markets	4	4	16
Business Issues	Untapped revenue sources	Researched entry	4	3	12
	Increased revenues	Lowering costs	2	5	10
	New strategies	Adaptability	4	4	16
Operational Issues	Challenges of new markets	Operational flexibility	2	4	8
	New Strategies	Strengthen existing brands	2	3	6
		Leverage on global image	1	3	3
		Local manufacturing	1	2	2
	Reach	Infrastructure	1	2	2
		Partner locally	1	4	4
	Create diverse model	Dilution and disorientation	2	4	8
Customer Issues	Socio-psychological Impact	Outreach and Acceptance	4	4	16
	Growth	Local adaptability	3	3	9
	Sustainability and Scalability	Affordability, Awareness and Acceptance	4	4	16
Technological Issues	Cost of operations	Value Chain Creation	3	2	6
	Acceptance	Understanding of local conditions	4	4	16
	Pricing	Strategic models	3	2	6
Environmental and Social Issues	Sustained value	Co-creation	2	2	4
	Positive image	Partnering locally	4	3	12
	Market value and brand image	Global leader –local server	4	4	16
Total			61	76	218

Source: Author

Table 5.8: Constraints of operating in BoP markets to generate higher revenues

Particulars	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Elements	Weightage	Average Rating Scores	Weighted Score
Stakeholder Issues	Leveraging costs	Entry and operating costs	4	3	12
	Initial low margins	Product suite	3	2	6
	Niche segment	Value creation in a niche segment	3	2	6
Business Issues	Global Knowledge	Study local markets	2	2	4
	Distribution and logistics	Tie-up's	2	3	6
	Acceptability and sustenance	Creation of critical Need-based product suites	3	3	9
		Diverse Marketing partnerships	3	2	6
Operational Issues	High entry costs	Local manufacturing tie-ups	1	3	3
		Fear of losing technological expertise	2	2	4
	Partnerships	Local acceptance and information sharing	3	4	12
	Infrastructure	Outreach through community entrepreneurs	2	3	6
	Global knowledge and position	Enter small	2	2	4
Customer Issues	Close-knit communities	Market segmentation	2	3	6
		Market targeting	2	2	4
		Market positioning	2	2	4
	Short-sighted approach	Long run strategy	2	2	4
Needs in-depth understanding	Gain knowledge from the local community	2	2	4	
Technological Issues	Bottlenecks	Economic and political awareness	3	2	6
	Technology	Sustainable and eco-friendly	3	2	6
	Beyond greening	Local best practices	4	2	8
Environmental and Social Issues	Overall image and costs	CSR initiatives	3	3	9
	Administrative	Partner locally to build communities	4	4	16
	Local players	Partnerships of competitors	3	2	6
Total			34	31	83

Source: Author

Table 5.9: Disadvantages of operating in BoP markets to generate higher revenues

Particulars	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Elements	Weightage	Average Rating Scores	Weighted Score
Stakeholder Issues	Lack of local knowledge	Gaining acceptance	2	3	6
	Unsuccessful product sets	Researched approach	3	2	6
	Loss of Unique product segment leadership	Maintain global leadership	2	2	4
		Create diverse flagship brands	3	3	9
Business Issues	Poor community knowledge	Gaining understanding and acceptance	4	3	12
	Large informal economy	Develop diverse business models	3	3	9
	Failure to understand	Short term vision	3	2	6
Operational Issues	Cost-benefit analysis	Long-term business strategy	3	3	9
	Un-researched strategies	Time to market	2	2	4
	Scalability	Focus on building strong partnerships	2	3	6
		Distribution	2	3	6
	High costs of implementation and operation	Operational leverage	1	2	2
Customer Issues	Negative repercussions	Poor local understanding	3	3	9
	Poor acceptance	Localizing global knowledge	4	3	12
	Expensive and extensive	Co-creation and Manufacturing	3	2	6
Technological Issues	Poor technology	Sustenance	4	3	12
	Gestation period	Focus on margins gradually	2	3	6
	Availability and acceptability	Customer class	4	2	8
Environmental and Social Issues	Short-sighted approach	The long-term vision for the segment	3	3	9
	Political interference	Local lobbying	4	2	8
	Lack of local knowledge	Extensive market research	3	2	6
Total			60	54	155

Source: Author

The ABCD quantitative analysis has a unique advantage if applied through the focus group study, as it gives immense insights into industry-specific attributes and critical constituent elements with weights vetted by experts making it consistently less subjective and an objective quantitative technique of analysis. These results can be combined with grassroots-level customer studies to discuss new strategies for business. They are especially useful when building business models for nascent business areas and domains. Depicted below is a graphical representation of the quantitative analysis of the ABCD analysis of the BoP market.

Figure 5.2: Graphical representation of ABCD Analysis

Source: Developed by the Researcher

5.7 ABCD FINDINGS

The researcher has studied the prime issues and various factors affecting the strategy of doing business in the base of the pyramid markets based on the ABCD quantitative analysis framework. Various factors affecting the issues of this strategy or business decision along with their critical constituent elements are identified and analyzed. It is found that the factors supporting advantages and benefits are more effective as compared to constraints and disadvantages of this business decision while keeping aside other factors that could be specified relative to the country under consideration. The study finds that it is feasible for companies to do business profitably at the base of the pyramid markets, but certain critical constituent elements that have been identified in each determinant is needed to be studied closely and given due importance while strategizing the plan of action and prioritizing the steps going forward. As articulated by Prahalad and Hart, the BoP initiative was proposed to enable multinationals and large corporations to

contribute to overall socio-economic development. Poverty alleviation and societal development were and could not continue to be the agenda of the government and aided agencies alone. As such market-based approaches have been used to address the profitability of these ventures.

An analysis of the BoP markets based on the ABCD quantitative analyzing framework has brought out dominant determinant issues and inherent key affecting factors with weighted scores. The benefits that can be attained while working on the advantages in this situation can be a large extent help in overcoming or negating the disadvantages brought in by the constraints, the study considered in each factor mentioned above.

The constraints are the bottlenecks that would or have prevented many corporations from attaining success in reaching out to and serving the vast BoP markets. The opportunities are huge but many corporations have been grounded by a myopic vision which is not possible in these markets. While initially they are attracted by the huge expanse of the untapped market, there are ample unmet needs at the most basic levels that can be addressed profitably and with a mutual value creation strategy. Multinationals and corporations have to devise strategies to operate there long enough to address these unmet societal needs, create competitive advantage, and realize that the long-term sustainability of these ventures will arise only by establishing mutually beneficial partnerships at the local level.

CHAPTER-VI

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

India is the largest BoP market constituted of 379 million adults in 2015 [182]. The BoP market is characterized by constraints like poverty, low literacy, and computational ability resulting in peculiar consumption patterns in form of loose unbranded products, cheaper brands, branded pouched, and second-hand durables [183]. Serving the BoP market mandated understanding the unusual consumption patterns and revisiting the marketing mix for peculiar BoP consumers. A previous study thesis conducted across different parts of rural and urban Punjab has elicited a lot of information on the basic consumption pattern of BoP in India [184]. The findings of this earlier study in Punjab exhibited certain basic consumption patterns of edible oil, food essentials, durables, and nondurable items, and the type of product consumed. The present study conducted on BoP market has also revealed some of the supporting and new findings which is discussed in this chapter.

This chapter is divided as mentioned below into the following four sub-heads:

Section 1: Findings related to BoP Customers - This section demonstrates the thorough understanding developed from the data gathered on urban BoP customer behaviour. Various descriptive statistics tools and observational methods are used to achieve this. This section pertains to the first objective of the research.

Findings related to Purchase influencers of BoP Customers - This section covers the findings related to the purchase influencers that define the behavioural dimensions of the BoPC. It is oriented to the third objective of the research.

Findings related to Attitudinal Dimensions of BoP Customers - This section demonstrates the perception levels of the attitudinal dimensions that influence the purchase behaviour during the buyer purchase decision process of the target market. It is aligned with the second objective of the research study.

Section 2: Hypothesis Testing - This section tests the various hypothesis developed for the study and the results are presented about the second and third objectives of the study.

Section 3: Findings related to BoPR - This section puts forth the work on BoP Retailer that substantiates the fulfillment of the fourth objective of the study.

Section 4: Findings Concerning Quantitative ABCD Analysis of BoP Market Strategies and Models – This section draws out the macro level quantitative analysis pertaining to the BoP market from the various stakeholder’s perspective.

To comprehend and describe the base pyramid's properties, this study examined consumer perceptions of market behaviour. This study evaluated the impact of BoPC attitude toward the various aspects of BoPC’s buying behaviour concerning branded essential products by comprehending the many dimensions of BoPC’s purchase behaviour. Finally, the research offers a quantitatively evaluated framework for BoPR to effectively interact with BoPC. To gather data while keeping in mind the study's stated goal, a survey method was employed. Bottom of the pyramid consumers and retailers were taken into account. Using various statistical tools, the data was assembled, coded, categorised, and evaluated. The main conclusions of the study are outlined in this chapter, along with information on the BoPC purchase behaviour, several attitudinal dimensions, and the effects of these attitudinal dimensions on purchase behaviour about branded necessities. Additionally, it provides the study's ramifications, conclusions, and recommendations for further research.

6.2 FINDINGS RELATED TO BoP CUSTOMERS

6.2.1 BoP CUSTOMERS PROFILE

BoP customer profiles included their Origin, Age, Education, Occupation, and Income level. It also consists of the Number of their family members and the number of Earning Members in their family. Furthermore, questions on the purchase preference of BoP customers were also included in the next section. The summarized finding of BoP customer profile and their purchase preference for branded essentials is discussed below;

- As per the results, 92.7 percent of the respondents are localites and 7.3 percent are migrants.
- As far as the age category of the BoP customers is concerned, 70.2 percent of the respondents are above 40 years, 22.93 percent are between the ages of 31 to 40 years, and 6.9 percent are between the ages of 20 to 30 years.
- Out of the 218 respondents, 66.5 percent of the respondents were female and 33.50 percent were male respondents.

- The findings also demonstrate that 64.22 percent of the respondents have school-level education, 14.67 per cent have no formal education, and 20.64 percent have education up to the undergraduate level.
- 62.84 percent of respondents are daily wage labourers, and they are comprised of varied occupations such as house helpers, odd jobs in shops, contract laborers, and so on. While salaried composed of 29.358 respondents, the majority were in private employment as sub-staff and so on, further, 7.79 percent have no employment.
- 39.0 percent of respondents have a monthly family income of above INR 20,000. 20.6 percent have an income of INR 15,000 to 20,000 and 17.3 percent have a monthly family income of INR 5,000 to 10,000.
- 62.4 percent of respondents have 3 to 5 members in their family, 24.8 percent of respondents have below 3 members in their families, and 9.6 percent of families have 5 to 8 members in their families.
- 72.5 percent of respondents have 2 to 3 earning members in the family, while 19.7 percent alone have only 1 earning member and 7.8 percent have above 3 earning members in the family.

6.2.2 PURCHASE PREFERENCE OF BRANDED ESSENTIAL PRODUCT

BoP customer's purchase preferences also have been obtained through the survey which contained the details on Place of purchase of Rice Wheat, Place of purchase of tea/coffee powder, cooking oil, salt, and Place of Purchase of Tooth Paste, Shampoo, Soap, Face Powder/Cream

- 93.1 percent of respondents purchased their requirements of rice, and wheat from government ration stores and 6.9 percent visited neighborhood Kirana stores.
- Findings on the place of purchase of essential grocery items such as tea/coffee powder, cooking oil, and salt, showed that 60.1 percent of respondents visited the neighborhood Kirana store to purchase daily use essentials, and 39.9 percent purchased their essential grocery items from the weekly open market.
- 77.5 percent of the respondents purchase their daily need FMCG essentials from neighborhood Kirana stores considering the proximity to purchase and availability, and 22.5 percent of respondents purchase it in the weekly open market.

6.2.3 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON INFLUENCERS OF PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR

Purchase influencer consists of 6 items with a mean value ranging from 3.4679 to 4.0505. As a result, all the items showed above-average values affirming the agreement level among the various purchase influencers. By analyzing the agreement level of respondents towards the various purchase influencers on their purchase behaviour, the following findings were revealed;

- As per the descriptive measures, seller recommendation (Mean=4.0505), word of mouth (Mean=3.8899), and credit availability (Mean=3.8119) tend to be the highest agreed purchase influencers by the respondents as their mean value is higher compared to other purchase influencers.
- As far as the lowest mean is concerned product feature being the purchase influencer (Mean=3.4679) was found to be the least agreed item.

6.2.4 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON ATTITUDINAL DIMENSIONS

Attitudinal dimensions consist of Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, and Relationship with Seller and brand factors were the variables of attitude formation towards purchase behaviour that was considered. The perception level on each dimension of attitude has been assessed using descriptive statistics which is discussed below sequentially:

6.2.4.1 PERCEPTION LEVEL OF AWARENESS

The perception level of awareness includes 4 indicators with the mean value ranging from 3.9587 to 4.1193. As a result, all the items showed above-average values confirming the awareness level of various purchase consideration factors.

- As per the descriptive statistics, having seen and heard about the product (Mean=4.1193), Other people's opinion of the product (Mean=4.0872), and Popularity of the product (Mean=4.0596) tend to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors by the respondents as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences.
- The last preference for purchase consideration was given to the Seller's/Brand reputation of the product (Mean= 3.9587).

6.2.4.2 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON AFFORDABILITY

The attitudinal dimension, affordability includes 4 items with a mean value ranging from 2.9725 to 4.4828. As a result, all the items showed above-average values confirming the attitude level on the affordability of the products.

- As per the descriptive statistics, Credit availability of the product (Mean=4.4828), Price of the product (Mean=3.9477), and Return, exchange, and ease of buying process (Mean=3.9194) tend to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors concerning affordability, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences.
- The last preference for purchase consideration concerning affordability of the product was given to Digital payment (Mean=2.9725).
- However, Credit availability of the product was found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration under affordability.

6.2.4.3 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON ACCESSIBILITY

It includes 4 items with a mean value ranging from 2.9174 to 4.0872. As a result, all the items showed above-average values confirming the attitude level on the Accessibility of the products.

- As per the descriptive statistics, Convenience of the place of purchase (Mean=4.0872), Small quantity purchase availability (Mean=4.0780), and Availability of the product (Mean=3.9679) tend to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors concerning Accessibility, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences.
- The last preference for purchase consideration concerning the Accessibility of the product was given to the Popularity of the store (Mean=2.9174).
- However, Convenience of the place of purchase was found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration under accessibility.

6.2.4.4 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON VISIBILITY

It includes 6 items with a mean value ranging from 3.2752 to 4.0092. As a result, all the items showed above-average values confirming the attitude level on the Visibility of the products.

- As per the descriptive statistics, Others' opinion of the store (Mean=4.0092), Taste/look of the product (Mean=3.9679), and Store appearance (Mean=3.9553) tend to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors concerning Visibility, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences.
- The last preference for purchase consideration concerning the Visibility of the product was given to Seller's/Brand reputation (Mean=3.2752).
- However, Others' opinions of the store were found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration.

6.2.4.5 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON RELATIONSHIP WITH SELLER

It includes 6 indicators with a mean value ranging from 3.2431 to 4.0505. As a result, all the indicators showed above-average values confirming the attitude level of the Relationship with the Seller.

- As per the descriptive statistics, Offerings by the seller (Mean=4.0505), Service by the seller (Mean=4.0000), and Years of consumer seller association (Mean=3.9954) tend to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors concerning customer Relationship with the Seller, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences.
- The last preference for purchase consideration concerning customer Relationship with Seller was given to Seller's/Brand reputation (Mean=3.2431).
- However, Offerings by sellers were found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration.

6.2.4.6 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON BRAND FACTORS

It includes 6 indicators with a mean value ranging from 2.8853 to 4.0688. As a result, all the indicators showed above-average values confirming the attitude level on Brand Factors.

- As per the descriptive statistics, Brand means offers (Mean=4.0688), Brand means high price (Mean=4.0550) and Brand means a well-known name, logo, and packaging (Mean=4.0138) tend to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors concerning Brand Factors, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences.
- The last preference for purchase consideration concerning Brand Factors was given to Brand means higher social status (Mean=2.8853).

6.2.5 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR

Purchase influencer consists of 6 items with a mean value ranging from 3.4679 to 4.0505. As a result, all the items showed above-average values affirming the agreement level among the various purchase influencers.

- As per the descriptive measures, seller recommendation (Mean=4.0505), word of mouth (Mean=3.8899), and credit availability (Mean=3.8119) tend to be the highest agreed purchase influencers by the respondents as their mean value is higher compared to other purchase influencers.
- As far as the lowest mean is concerned product feature being the purchase influencer (Mean=3.4679) was found to be the least agreed item.
- However, seller recommendations were found to be the major purchasing influencer of branded essential products.

6.2.6 PERCEPTION LEVEL OF PROMOTIONAL STRATEGIES

As a result, all the items showed above-average values confirming the preferential level of the various Promotional Strategies of Marketers.

- As per the descriptive measures, Attractive Prices (Mean=4.2339), Referral purchases (Mean=4.1193), and Gifts (Mean=4.0872) tend to be the highly preferred Promotional Strategies of Marketers by the respondents as their mean value is higher compared to other Promotional Strategies.
- As far as the lowest mean is concerned, Credit facilities by the marketers were found to be the least influential Promotional Strategy (Mean=3.8532).
- However, attractive prices offered by the marketers were found to be the major influential promotional strategies by the marketers.

6.2.7 PERCEPTION LEVEL ON BRAND IMPACT ON ESSENTIAL PRODUCTS

It includes 8 indicators with a mean value ranging from 2.9266 to 4.2018. As a result, all the indicators showed above-average values confirming the attitude level on Brand Impact on Essential Products.

- As per the descriptive statistics, Frequent repurchase of same brand products (Mean=4.2018), purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, and powder (Mean=4.1606), and purchasing branded daily need essentials such as rice, wheat, sugar (Mean=4.0459) tends to be the highly preferred purchase consideration factors concerning Brand Impact on Essential Products, as its mean value is higher compared to other preferences.

- The last preference for purchase consideration concerning Brand Impact on Essential Products was given to purchasing unbranded products when customer relationship with the seller is important (Mean=2.8853).
- However, purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, and powder was found to be the majorly preferred purchase consideration.

Customer perception and attitude on Awareness (M=4.0562), Affordability (M=3.8681), Accessibility (M=3.7626), Visibility (M=3.7772), Relationship with Seller (M=3.7518), Brand Factors (M= 3.8284), Purchase Behaviour (M=3.8032), Promotional Strategies (M=4.0078), Brand Impact on Essential Products (M=3.7008) showed a mean values above average. The highest perception or attitude level was shown in Awareness (M=4.0562), Promotional Strategies (M=4.0078), and Affordability (M=3.8681) compared to other constructs.

6.2.8: SUMMARY OF HYPOTHESIS TESTING RESULTS

Table 6.1: Findings of Chi-Square Test results

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Demographical Variable	P Value	Result
1.	H1.1: Demographic factors of BoP customers will influence the purchase behaviour of branded Essential products in the food grains category (Rice, Wheat, and Sugar)	Origin	P<0.05*	H1.1 is Rejected
		Age	P>0.05	
		Gender	P>0.05	
		Education Level	P>0.05	
		Occupation	P<0.05*	
		Monthly Family Income	P<0.05*	
		Number of Members in the Family	P>0.05	
		Number of Earning Members in the Family	P>0.05	
2.	H1.2: Demographic factors of BoP customers will influence purchasing behaviour about Essential products category of daily consumables (Tea/Coffee Powder, Cooking Oil, and Salt)	Origin	P>0.05	H1.2 is rejected
		Age	P<0.05*	
		Gender	P>0.05	
		Education Level	P>0.05	
		Occupation	P<0.05*	
		Monthly Family Income	P<0.05*	
		Number of Members in the Family	P>0.05	
		Number of Earning Members in the Family	P>0.05	
3.	H1.3: Demographic factors of BoP customers will influence purchase behaviour concerning Essential product categories of FMCG (Tooth Paste, Shampoo, Soap, Face Powder/Cream).	Origin	P>0.05	H1.3 is accepted
		Age	P<0.05*	
		Gender	P>0.05	
		Education Level	P<0.05*	
		Occupation	P<0.05*	
		Monthly Family Income	P<0.05*	
		Number of Members in the Family	P<0.05*	
		Number of Earning Members in the Family	P>0.05	

Table 6.2: Findings of Simple and Multiple Regressions

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Variable	Test	Result
1.	H2: Attitudinal dimension factors have an impact on purchase behaviour towards branded essential products.	Awareness	P>0.05	H2 is accepted
		Affordability	P<0.05*	
		Accessibility	P<0.05*	
		Visibility	P<0.01**	
		Relationship with Seller	P<0.05*	
	Brand Factors	P<0.05*		
2.	H3: Occupation and income level of BoP Customers tend to moderate the relationship between Attitudinal dimensional factors and purchase behaviour towards branded essential products.	Occupation	P<0.05*	H3 is accepted
		Income	P<0.05*	
3.	H4: Promotional strategies of the marketer have a direct effect on the purchase behaviour of branded essential products by the BoP Customer.	Promotional strategies	P<0.01**	H4 is accepted
4.	H5: Occupation and income tend to moderate the relationship between promotional strategies and purchase behaviour of branded essential products by the BoP Customer.	Occupation	P>0.05	H5 is rejected
		Income	P>0.05	
5.	H6: The Purchase Behaviour towards Branded Essential Products is highly influenced by the seller's recommendation.	Purchase Behaviour	P<0.01**	H6 is accepted
6.	H7: Lower prices and Referral purchases of the branded essential product will have more influence on the Promotional Strategies of the marketer.	Promotional Strategies	P<0.01**	H7 is accepted

Table 6.3: Findings of Friedman's Test Results

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Variable	Test	Result
1.	H8: Awareness and affordability in the attitudinal dimension will have more effect on the purchase behaviour of BoP customers.	Attitude	P<0.01**	H8 is accepted
2.	H8.1: Having seen and heard about the product and its popularity highly contributes to brand awareness as a purchase consideration.	Awareness	P<0.01**	H8.1 is accepted
3.	H8.2: Digital payment and Credit availability highly contribute to the customers' perception of affordability as their purchase consideration.	Affordability	P<0.01**	H8.2 is accepted
4.	H8.3: Small quantity purchase availability and Convenience of place highly affect the accessibility dimension of purchase consideration.	Accessibility	P<0.01**	H8.3 is accepted
5.	H8.4: Others' opinion of the store and the Taste/look of the product has a high influence on customers' perception of visibility as a factor of purchase consideration.	Visibility	P<0.01**	H8.4 is accepted

6.	H8.5: Offerings and services by sellers majorly contribute to the customer's perception of their relationship with the seller as a factor of purchase consideration	Relationship with Seller	P<0.01**	H8.5 is accepted
7.	H8.6: Brand as offers and high price majorly contributes to Customer perception of the brand being the factor of purchase consideration.	Brand Factors	P<0.01**	H8.6 is accepted
8.	H8.7: Frequent repurchase of same brand products and purchasing branded daily need essentials such as toothpaste, shampoo, and powder highly determines customers' perception of Brand Impact on Essential Products.	Brand Impact on Essential Products	P<0.01**	H8.7 is accepted

Table 6.4: Findings of Structural Equation Modeling Results

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Estimates	P	Result
1.	H9: Promotional Strategies of Marketer mediate the relationship between the attitudinal dimension and purchasing behaviour of branded essential products by the BoP Customer.	PS<---A = .131	HS	H9 is accepted
		PB<---A = .242	HS	
		PB<---PS = .247	S	
		Effect (Total) = .337	S	
		Effect (Direct) = .297	S	
		Effect (Indirect) = .040	S	

Note: PB=Purchase Behaviour, PS=Promotional Strategies, A=Attitude, HS-Highly Significant, S-Significant

Table 6.5: Findings of One-way Anova and t-test

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Variable	Test	Result
1.	H10: Attitudinal dimension, Purchase Behaviour, Promotional Strategies of marketers, and Brand Impact on the essential product are influenced by demographic factors.	Origins	P>0.05	H10 is rejected
		Age Category	P<0.05*	
		Genders	P>0.05	
		Education Level.	P>0.05	
		Employment Status	P>0.05	
		Level of Income	P>0.05	
		Number of Members in the Family.	P>0.05	
		Number of Earning Members in the Family	P>0.05	
2.	H11: The attitude level of BoP customers toward Branded essential products will have an impact on Promotional Strategies, Purchase Behaviour, and Brand Impact on Essential Products	Purchase Behaviour	P<0.01**	H11 is accepted
		Promotional Strategies	P<0.01**	
		Brand Impact on Essential Products	P<0.05*	

6.3 BoP RETAILERS

6.3.1 RETAILERS PROFILE

- 82% of the respondents are localities, whereas 18% of them are migrants.
- 45% of the retailers belong to the above 45 age category, 31% of them belong to 36 to 40 years and 16% belong to 31 to 35 years.
- 89% of the respondents are male and the remaining are female.
- 90% of the retailers are married and the remaining 10% are unmarried.
- 52% of the retailers are graduates, and 46% of them have only school-level education.
- 36% of the respondents say that the operational duration of the store is 5-10 years and above 10 years each. The remaining 28% said it is 2 to 5 years.
- 41% of the respondents said that the average no. of walk-ins per day is 20-30, and 23% say 30-55.
- 67% of the retailers said they don't have Government Authorized Ration (PHRC/NPHRC/BPL/APL) Store and the remaining said yes.
- 46% of the retailers said they have only one employee in their store and 45% of them said 2 employees and the remaining said 3 employees.
- 93% of the respondents said that they have only one store in operation.
- 45% of the respondents said that 1-10% of the transaction is done using Paytm, Google Pay, Phone Pe, etc., and 31% said 0%.
- 53% of the retailers said that 0% of customers are currently availing of Credit facilities and 29% of them said 1-10%.
- 59% of the respondents state that up to 25% of known customers shop at their store. 18% said 25-50%.
- 42% of the respondents said that they purchase all the products from distributors, 38% from the wholesaler and 20% from agents.
- 32% of the respondents preferred other options for stock purchase, 30% said monthly and 24% said weekly.

6.3.2 RETAILERS' ATTITUDE TOWARD SELLING THE BRANDED ESSENTIAL PRODUCTS

Retailers' attitude toward Branded Essential Products was measured using 5 indicators with the mean value ranging from 3.2500 to 3.7600. As per the descriptive statistics, Profit is Important when selling Branded Essential Products (3.7600), Lower Price is

Important in selling Branded Essential Products (Mean=3.6300) and Supplier Recommendation is Important when selling Branded Essential Products (Mean=3.6100) tends to be the highly preferred factors concerning retailers' attitude on Branded Essential Products. The last preference for retailers' attitude toward selling the branded essential products was given to Credit Facility as an Important factor when selling Branded Essential Products (Mean=3.2500). Apart from descriptive statistics results, percentage analysis of retailers' attitudes was also analyzed and discussed below;

- 53% of BoPR agreed that lower price is important in selling Branded Essential Products yet 24% of them have a neutral perception of lower price.
- 47% of the BoPR agreed that they prefer Selling loose Products because their Supplier provides a Credit facility but 25% of them showed a neutral perception regarding this statement.
- 56% of the respondents agreed that they prefer selling loose products because they get higher profit however 24% of them gave a neutral perception on this.
- 46% of the retailers agreed that they prefer selling loose products because they have a long-term Business Relationship with the Suppliers besides 27% of them showed a neutral attitude toward the above statement.

6.3.3 BoP RETAILERS' PERCEPTION OF BRAND AWARENESS

Retailers' attitude toward Brand Awareness includes 10 indicators with a mean value ranging from 2.6400 to 3.7600. As per the descriptive statistics, believing that displaying branded products attracts new customers to their store (3.7600) and recommending products to their customers for which they get higher profit from the supplier (Mean=3.7600) tends to be the highly preferred factors of retailers' perception on brand awareness. The last preference for retailers' perception towards branded products was given to the statement of losing existing customers by displaying branded products (Mean=2.6400). However, they believe that displaying branded products attracts new customers to their store and prefer recommending products to their customers for which they get higher profit from the supplier found to be the majorly preferred. Overall, the perception level of retailers' perception of Brand Awareness shows the mean and S.D as $3.7600 \pm .66848$. The percentage analysis of BoP retailers' perception of brand awareness is discussed below:

- As per percentage analysis, 59% of the retailers agreed that their customers are Capable of differentiating between Branded and Un-Branded Products yet, 27% of them showed neutral perception in this regard.
- The majority (73%) of the retailers agree that Branded Product means a familiar Name, Logo, and Packaging and 18% have a neutral perception of this statement.
- 68% of the respondents agree that Branded Product means a Packaged Product but 19% gave a neutral perception in this regard.
- The majority (44%) of the retailers agreed that Branded Product means a Product Originated from a Reputed Place and 38% have a neutral perception of this.
- 52% of the retailers agree that they prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Branded Product and 35% of them have a neutral perception of the preference of selling a lower-priced product over a branded product.
- 53% of the retailers agreed with the statement that they prefer Selling a Lower Priced Product over a Packaged Product and 28% of them give a neutral perception.
- 36% of the respondents have a neutral perception of preferring Sales of Priced products over a Product Originating from a Reputed Place but 30% of them agreed to it.
- 48% of the retailers prefer Recommending Products to your Customers for which you get Higher Profit from the Supplier and 25% of them strongly agree with it.
- 22% disagree with this statement. 52% of the respondents disagree that the store will lose existing customers by displaying branded products whereas 28% of the respondents agree to it.
- 68% of the respondents agree that displaying branded products attracts new customers to their store and 19% gave a neutral perception in this regard.

Table 6.6: Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results of BoPR

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Demographical variable	Test	Result
1.	H12: The attitude of BoPR toward BoPB is influenced by the tenure of business, number of walk-ins per day, duration of stock purchase, and percentage of the known customer.	Tenure of Business	P>0.05	H12 is accepted
		Number of Walk-Ins Per Day	P<0.05*	
		Duration of Stock Purchase	P<0.05*	
		Percentage of Known Customer	P<0.05*	
2.	H13: Attitude of BoPR toward Branded Essential Products is Negative	Pearson's Correlation	P<0.01**	H13 is accepted
		Friedman Test	P<0.01**	
		One sample t-test	P<0.01**	

6.4 FINDINGS CONCERNING QUANTITATIVE ABCD ANALYSIS OF BoP MARKET STRATEGIES AND MODELS

Table 6.7: Quantitative ABCD Analysis of BoP Markets Strategies and Models

Factors	Weighted Score	Inference
Advantageous factors	227	BoP Markets Strategies and Models remarkably advantageous
Benefiting factors	218	
Constraint factors	83	
Disadvantageous factors	155	

The inferences in alignment with the stated objectives are discussed with suitable recommendations drawn after considering the macro-level ABCD analysis and micro-level statistical tools results analysis, thus using hybrid-mixed method approach are presented in the next chapter.

CHAPTER-VII

RECOMMENDATIONS, SUGGESTED MODEL AND CONCLUSION

7.1 INTRODUCTION

The attitudinal and behavioural dimensions of the bottom of the pyramid customers towards branded essential products has been studied by the researcher through analysis & study of previous research in the same area, the sighting of the gaps in the previous studies has led to the narrowing of the study to the purchase of only branded essential products. Herein, the linkage of various independent variables and mediating variables that lead to the formation of attitudes to the purchase of branded essential products among BoP consumers and the BoP retailers is elaborated. Path analysis has been implied to check the fit of the suggested conceptual framework for BoP customers. Different relationships between the variables have been tested through path analysis using structural equation modeling, total thirteen hypotheses were tested. The fulfillments of the study are presented below:

Objective 1: To understand the effect of demographics of the base of the pyramid customers towards branded essential products concerning the area under study.

Hypothesis tested using ANOVA and Fischer's exact test was conducted and interpretations can be derived from the explained below:

Age: Age has significant influence on purchasing behaviour of BoPC with regard to daily consumable fast moving goods category as well as daily consumables food items, however when essential products of rice, wheat purchase is considered, age has no significant influence on the purchase behaviour.

Occupation: Occupation tends to have a significant influence on purchasing behaviour of BoPC with regard to daily consumable fast moving goods category as well as essential foodgrains and daily consumables food items.

Education: Education level has a significant influence on purchasing behaviour only on daily consumable fast moving goods category only. Hence, it can be inferred that level of education influences purchase of branded essential products of the toothpaste, toothpowder, soap, shampoo category. Marketer can primarily focus on these categories before foraying to other essentials such as food grains and edible primary consumables used in food preparation like oil, salt, etc.

Income Level: Income also has a significant influence on purchasing behaviour of BoPC about daily consumable fast moving goods category as well as essential

foodgrains and daily consumables food items. It can be noted from observations also during the study that income level has a significant influence on purchase behaviour of branded essential products and this leads the BoPC to look at other associated factors such as credit availability, gifts, offers, discounts etc.,

Occupation: The association between occupational influence on the purchase of branded essential products of all three categories under study is significant. The occupation of the various respondents are predominantly daily wage earners in odd jobs as drivers, blue collar jobs in local private establishments, sub staffs, house maids etc., Occupation places them in reference points of social influences and hence influences their attitude and purchase behaviour of branded essential products, while those in more access to social networks and accessibility tend to develop a more favorable purchase behaviour, creation of more awareness and affordability and brand impact factors may further enhance the occupational influence on the creation of a favourable attitudinal dimension.

Gender: Influence of gender on purchase behaviour of branded essential products is not demonstrated, the reason could be attributed to the fact of an unequal distribution of sample between the groups.

Origin: The analysis revealed irrespective of the origin of the respondents whether localites or migrants there is significant association between purchase behaviour of food grains category and origin of the BoPC.

Objective 2: To study the impact of the attitude of BoP consumers towards branded essential products.

The influence of six attitudinal dimension formation variables were studied and confirmatory model was run to see the correlation of each dimension on each other. The result depicted that Awareness, Affordability, Accessibility, Visibility, Relationship with Seller and Brand Factors are strongly correlated with each other, which strongly ensures that all these dimensions can be taken under one construct that is attitude. Hence all these indicators are the dimensions of attitude due to its strong correlation. Improvement in the one unit of visibility contributes to 17.9% increase in the purchase influencers among the customers. Moreover, one unit increase in the customers perception on Relationship with Sellers, Brand Factors, Accessibility and Affordability would contribute to 14.1%, 13.2%, 11.1% and 9.2% increase in the

customers perception of purchase influencers respectively.

Influence of demographic variables:

Origin: Brand Impact on Essential Products is influenced by the origins of the customers.

Age: Attitudinal dimension, Promotional Strategies of marketers and Brand Impact on Essential Products are significantly influenced by the age category.

Gender: Genders have influence on Awareness and Promotional Strategies adopted by the marketers.

Education: Brand Impact on Essential Products is affected by Education Level.

Occupation: Contemplating the influence of no employment, the strongest predictor of the purchase behaviour is awareness and brand factors respectively. From this result, one can infer that, one unit increase in the perception of customers towards Awareness would lead to 58.1% increase in purchase behaviour. Similarly, one unit increase in brand factors would lead to 50.9% increase in purchase behaviour. Amongst daily wage labourers, the strongest predictor of purchase behaviour is visibility, accessibility and Brand Factors respectively. Amongst salaried segment showed that affordability, relationship with seller and brand factors are the strongest predictors of purchase behaviour.

Income Levels: Affordability, Accessibility and Brand Impact on Essential Products are significantly influenced by the level of income. In case of below Rs.5,000 income Relationship with Seller is the strongest predictor of purchase behaviour, in case of income Rs.5,001 to 10,000 and next higher level of income Brand Factors is a larger influencer and in case of Rs.15,001 to 20,000 Relationship with Seller is the strongest predictor of purchase behaviour.

Objective 3: To study the influencers on BoPC towards the purchase of branded essential products.

The results of the Friedman's test, showed that calculated Chi-square value is 27.111 with the p value below 0.01 at 5 degrees of freedom. It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking between the purchase influencers. Purchase of branded essential products is highly contributed by sellers recommendation

(MR=3.90) compared to word of mouth (MR=3.64) and brand image (MR=3.53) followed by credit availability (MR=3.42). Purchase of branded essential products was lowly influenced by the product features.

While understanding the Customers' purchase behaviour towards branded essential products is considered from the perspective of the impact of the various promotional strategies of marketer, it indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ranking between the customers perception on promotional strategies. Moreover, promotional strategies by the marketer is seen to be highly influenced by attractive prices (MR=6.30) compared to referral purchases (MR=5.80), and gifts (MR=5.72) followed by small serving sizes (MR=5.67). However, credit facilities (4.92) lowly contributes as a purchase influencer amongst the promotional strategies by the marketers.

Hence, it can be concluded that the seller and marketer should focus on increasing and incentivising the seller in ways to influence him to recommend the products of the marketer/manufacturer. A BoP customer always relied heavily on seller recommendation, word of mouth and credit availability to make his purchase decisions compared to other purchase influencers. Also, attractive prices, referral purchases and gifts are a major purchase influencer as against others. The purchase behaviour of BoP customer is highly affected by Awareness and Affordability compared to Brand Factors, followed by Accessibility among the attitudinal dimensions.

Objective 4: To explore the driving factors of BoPR to serve the BoPC market.

Another perspective of this study was also to study the attitudes of the seller/retailer towards selling branded essential products and what are the influencing or driving factors herein.

- Retailers' perception on brand awareness: Seller/retailer has a fair idea of brands, their meaning and what they communicate similar to their customers. A larger share of them believed that their customers can differentiate between branded and un-branded Products.
- Retailers attitude towards branded essential products: Profit is the important factor when selling Branded Essential Products, lower price and supplier recommendation is considered important in selling branded essential products with regard to

retailers' attitude towards stocking and selling branded essential products. The seller at the BoP market has access to a large number of loose saleable products which not only give them credit facilities but also higher margins and are convenient to push through to the customer.

- Influence of retailers' business demographical variables to attitude towards branded products: It was seen in initial instance that retailers having tenure of 5-10 years of business showed highest attitude of BoPR toward BoPB compared to 2-5 years and above 10 years of business. However, the overall results of Friedman's test, Fisher's exact test or Chi-square test, t-test, one-way ANOVA, correlation, showed that there is no significant difference in attitude of BoPR toward BoPB among the tenure of business.
- Influence of walk-ins per day to the attitude of BoPR toward BoPB; The average number of walk-ins per day significantly influenced the BoPR attitude towards BoPB. Further, retailers having 10-20, 30-50 and above 50 walk in per day showed highly perceived attitude towards profit as important factor in selling branded essential products while sellers with 20-30 walk in per day showed highly perceived attitude towards suppliers' recommendation as a dominant factor in stocking and selling BoPB.
- It was also found that the attitude of BoPR/seller is positive toward Suppliers and the lower-priced loose products over the branded essential products. Moreover, it was found that profit is an important selling motive for the retailer while intending to sell branded essential products and supplier recommendation is important in deciding to sell Branded Essential Products as it is seen to highly contributes to retailers' attitude towards branded essential products compared to other factors. Hence, the study can infer that the attitude of retailer/seller by itself towards branded essential products is negative, the marketer has to create a lot of peripheral supportive conditions to enable them to recommend the marketers goods, make it available and affordable as well as provide other promotional measure to influence and create loyalty amongst the BoPR. By themselves the seller/retailer is not having much means to provide heavy visibility, awareness, affordability, gifts, any kind of incentives to new purchasers who were referred by existing customers etc.

Objective 5: To develop a tested model for BoPR to successfully engage BoPC.

The conceptual model developed for the study has been tested through the macro level ABCD analysis and the micro level statistical analysis.

Figure 7.1: Conceptual Model of BoPC Attitude Toward Brands Influencing Purchase Behaviour

Figure 7.2: Conceptual Model of Consumer Attitude, Purchase Behaviour, and Promotional Strategies

Further, in view of the various findings of the observations noted during the phases of interviews, the one on one interactions from the company representatives during identification of the critical constituent elements in the ABCD analysis, the analysis using the various statistical and quantitative tools, a model of consumer adoption at the BoP for the marketer and retailer is recommended.

Figure 7.3: S-C A-B Model for BoP Market Adoption, Sustenance and Augmentation
 Source: Developed by the Researcher

Based on the inferences of the above four objectives, it has been seen that the consumer attitude towards branded essential products is mediated by income and occupation in the BoP market. The purchases wherever regulated and guided by the governmental bodies or institutions overpowers and other brand interference as in the case of subsidized food grains supplied by the public distribution system in India. Social factors such as cultures, values, family influences, family size, household decision maker all are the BoPC influencers. These aid in creating the BoP consumer attitude towards branded essential products that is directly formed by the factors of awareness, accessibility, affordability, visibility, relationship with seller, brand factors, and promotional strategies. The promotional strategies by the seller and/or the marketers greatly pushes the creation of the BoPC attitude towards

branded essential products. It could be gifts, offers, and so on. The factors that will influence the creation of attitudes and behaviours towards purchase of branded essential products are driven by the marketers whose prime responsibility it is to see to it that if he wishes to gain entry to the BoP market he has to create awareness on the product, usage, need, availability, create accessibility to it through distribution networks or backward integration and cross buy-sell strategies. All of these will be influenced by competitors' strategies and their decisions. Credit facilities is important in ensuring affordability and distributor recommendations are seen to give momentum to the BoPR attitude towards BoPB.

At the seller/retailer driven factors are primarily the profit motive, higher margins that can be received, lower prices that can be offered while keeping profits and margins competitive. Supplier recommendations are seen to be a driving factor in ensuring the BoPR has a positive attitude towards BoPB. Other brand factors in terms of brand image, recognition, brand reputation with respect to quality, product need fulfillment, brand recall, brand associations were seen to be important factors elicited during discussions. Finally, while BoPC is always looking at small serving sizes, the seller/ BoPR is always interested in higher sales volumes which is a factor that need ot be strategized by the seller with the support of the marketer. This is a Seller-Customer Attitude-Behaviour Model for the BoP which would enable the creation of a value chain in itself that will optimize entry and involvement for the seller/marketer, engagement and value fulfillment for the customer and seller/retailer and strategized delivery for business enhancement and growth for the marketer at the BoP market.

7.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Marketers looking to serve in the BoP markets need to understand that this is a large market with huge opportunities which will open if only the approach is strategized with the end customer in mind. Many global giants failed in these markets because they overlooked the need to understand these customers better before serving here. The study has proven that while the BoPC may be willing to and interested in availing of the products if available within his limitations, the BoPR/seller is not lured by the BoPB. The BoPR has to be approached through marketers efforts of making his product affordable, creating a long-lasting distributor- retailer- customer value model

to be able to penetrate this market as the study has shown that the BoPC is largely dependent on seller recommendations, word of mouth and community influence in this market is very high. Companies/marketers launching and serving these markets have to provide awareness, easy access, and liaison with existing sellers to stock, and sell their products, though serving sizes may be small, the marketer has to help the seller to increase sales volumes by providing mobile technologies to reach to customer doorsteps if need be at no extra cost. Finding this seller at the BoP market who has significant customers under his belt who could be operating in non-descript weekly markets, dainty little roll and shut stalls, or neighborhood kirana stores is indeed an effort worth taking up for the marketer since these retailers/sellers will give the much-needed market share for the marketer immediately if handled well.

- The study found that traditional marketing media mainly influence low-consumers. However, the retailer should take steps to spread more word-of-mouth advertising by improving relationships with sellers.
- Most of the families own at least one mobile, and they use them primarily for voice calling and messaging. An initiation in sending voice or text messages to these prospective customers on offers, gifts, price drops weekly discount sales, etc can attract such consumers at this point using an online mobile platform.
- To improve the local business presence, firms should extend a flexible credit facility, and drop shipping facility (from FMCG companies) at the local vendors (retailers, wholesalers). Firms should provide some structural support (like a small fridge or racks) to store the company's front-end display items.
- The company should look for offering more value (utility) at a lower price as affordability is very important, most of the BoPC buy at very short intervals and cannot go for bulk quantities, hence matching pricing with small volume purchases which would give value for money proposition to the BoPC increasing loyalty to the store and brand.
- Besides price, product availability, and word of mouth reference strongly influence low-income consumers' purchase intentions. Hence, the national and international marketers who aim to increase market share in this market should create a loyal customer base through enhanced product offerings at a lower price.
- They take purchase decision in consultation with family members/friends. Hence, the approach should always be to target the head of the family or the decision maker or reference groups.

- Firms could endeavor to develop personal touch (through awareness campaigns) with these low-income consumers so that they easily connect themselves with products.
- BoPR is influenced by the profitability in the business, he is not lured if the branded product does not fetch high margins. The company should incentivise distributors to get small retailers to stock their wares and market them by either incentivising the distributor or the retailer.
- Most of the BoPR do not keep huge stock, they purchase it weekly or rarely monthly basis, this should be an opportunity for large cash-rich firms to provide weekly credit facilities to reach this market.
- The study further recommends that the BoP markets need approach and study from not just customers but also the existing seller networks thorough successful liasoning and partnering with them.
- Bottom of the pyramid market still believe in a tangible, physical transactions and relationships rather than the virtual world, hence to penetrate these markets more efforts are needed on physical infrastructure and strategy and not only short term virtual arrangement and this physical infrastructure along with government agencies can be created in a PPP model and would go a long way to create a much needed presence, recall and build a closer philanthropic oriented social service model as well in these markets.

7.3 FUTURE SCOPE

The research offers important directions for future research:

1. The research was successful in identifying both facets of BoP as in the customer and retailer perspective in their attitudinal and behavioural dimensions to branded essential products, researchers in future tailor it to suit different categories of products such as aspirational products, negative products, etc.,
2. The study enlisted certain variables under attitudinal dimensions, though exhaustive as far as this study is concerned, it is suggested that more variables could be studied.
3. The research has been carried out in one urban location, further studies can be conducted in rural locations. Larger sample size and more demographical variables and inter-regional diversities can be studied.

4. Further studies can consider the BoPC across socio-economic variations such as tribal populations, migrant occupational dwellers and so on.
5. The largest slum in the world, Dharavi in Mumbai can be an interesting new area to study to understand BoPC.
6. The study has also utilized the ABCD analysis framework to identify various key stakeholders and the advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages in serving BoP markets, future studies can identify other quantitative and qualitative measurable vectors to other dimensions of the study and apply the ABCD analysis technique.
7. The researcher has considered the data of the ration card holders, further study can consider upcoming census data and variations under various ministries of the government of India, if available.

7.4 CONCLUSION

The BoP Customer has varied needs and his attitudinal formation is unique in its approach towards the influence of purchase behaviour, it has thrown up an interesting relationship between the variables under consideration. It can be concluded that BoPC and his/her attitudinal dimensions along with the promotional strategies influence purchase behaviour on branded essential products positively. The predominant goal of this study was to identify the characteristics and attitudinal and behavioural dimensions of branded essential factors and the objectives have been addressed with scope for further study as well. The fact that the seller/retailer in the BoP market is not influenced directly by brands to stock and sell the branded products but the decision to stock and display branded products is influenced and attitude towards branded products by itself is negative is an interesting and undiscovered phenomena in the BoP market in India in earlier studies and this will open up new forums for furthering this topic to unravel the distributor management chain and new strategies and approaches can be developed. In an American Marketing Association address, Philip Kotler, often referred to as the 'father of marketing' emphasized that one of the most neglected areas in marketing is that of marketing to the poor. He noted that the poverty market emerged over a period as one of the biggest growth sectors, also since this is the segment where maximum growth of population is happening hence this study is significant in the vastness of the depth of taking this discussion forward in the right steam. Further, the essentiality of developing a better and clear understanding of this

important and enlarged, but often neglected, this segment of the world population can make contributions to public policy design and formulation. A thorough understanding of the low-income consumer, and consumers in general, would also facilitate the design of consumer policies not only from a business perspective but also to provide solutions to societal problems with the goal of socio-economic preservation and development at large.

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